

ESREIN
Economic and Social
Research Institute

Journal of Economics, Law & Society

Advancing Ethical and Socially
Responsible Finance

Vol. 2 - No. 1 - June 2025

Published by:

Economic and Social Research Institute (ESREIN)

Blagovac 192,

71320 Vogošća

Bosnia and Herzegovina

<https://jels.esrein.org>

jels@esrein.org

ISSN (Online): 3029-3189

JELS

JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS, LAW & SOCIETY

Advancing Ethical and Socially Responsible Finance

Volume 2 | Number 1 | June 2025

Published by

ESREIN
Economic and Social
Research Institute

JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS, LAW AND SOCIETY

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

Dr. Edib Smolo
Co-Founder & Effat University, KSA

JOURNAL MANAGERS

Dr. Admir Mešković
Co-Founder, University of Tuzla, Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH)

Dr. Alija Avdukić
Co-Founder, Al-Maktoum College of Higher Education & University of Dundee, Dundee, UK

ASSOCIATE EDITORS

Dr. Adnan Trakic
Malaysia School of Business, Monash University, Malaysia

Dr. Aida Hanić
Institute of Economic Sciences, Serbia

Dr. Emil Knezović
Faculty of Business and Administration,
International University of Sarajevo, (BiH)

Dr. Mirzet Seho
Malaysia School of Business, Monash University, Malaysia

Dr. Norashikin Ismail
Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM), Johor Bahru, Malaysia

EDITORIAL BOARD

Dr. Alam Asadov
Prince Sultan University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Dr. Burhan Uluyol
Istanbul Sabahattin Zain University

Dr. Hakimah Yaacob
Sultan Sharif Ali Islamic University, Brunei Darussalam

Dr. Hashim Jusoh
Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin, Malaysia

Dr. Salman Ahmed Shaikh
International Islamic University Malaysia, Malaysia

Dr. Šejma Aydin
International University of Sarajevo, (BiH)

ADVISORY BOARD

Dr. Adel M Sarea
Ahlia University, Bahrain

Dr. Ahmet F. Aysan
Hamad Bin Khalifa University, Qatar

Dr. Fazrihan Bin Mohamed Duriat
Pôle Universitaire Euclide, Singapore

Dr. Mohamed Eskandar Rasid
Hamad Bin Khalifa University - Qatar

Dr. M. Kabir Hassan
University of New Orleans, USA

Dr. Obiyathulla Ismath Bacha
INCEIF University, Malaysia

Dr. Ramo Palalić
Sultan Qaboos University - Oman

Dr. Suad Bećirović
International University of Novi Pazar - Serbia

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

The Journal of Economics, Law, and Society (JELS) is a pioneering academic platform dedicated to the comprehensive exploration of economics, law, and society, with a distinct focus on Islamic economics, banking, and finance. Our mission is to foster interdisciplinary dialogue, cultivate a deep understanding of these interconnected disciplines, and promote the exchange of innovative research to advance both theoretical knowledge and practical applications.

CONTRIBUTIONS AND EDITORIAL CORRESPONDENCE

Comments, suggestions and requests to:

editor@esrein.org
jels@esrein.org

Online journal:

<https://jels.esrein.org/>

ISSN

ISSN (Online): 3029-3189

Published by:

Economic and Social Research Institute (ESREIN)
Blagovac 192,
71320 Vogošća
Bosnia and Herzegovina

Design & Layout by

Dr. Edib Smolo

Contents

Editorial	1-3
Wasatiyah Optimization in Sustainable Wealth Management	5-28
<i>Tariqullah Khan</i>	
Total Factor Productivity and Foreign Human Capital: Evidence from the Western Balkans	29-45
<i>Haris Lloyd</i>	
Profitability and Resilience: Comparative Analysis of the Performance of Islamic and Conventional Insurance Companies in the GCC Region	51-72
<i>Abdulrahim Amrullah</i>	
Structuring Islamic Financial Literacy Construct to Measure Islamic Banking Products Adoption in Uganda: Content Validation of the Survey Instrument	73-83
<i>Yusuf Kaweesa and Romzie Rosman</i>	
Crowdfunding: The End of an Era or a Course Correction? A Bibliometric Analysis	85-117
<i>Shadi Al Shebli</i>	

Editorial

Volume 2, Issue 1 – Journal of Economics, Law and Society (JELS)

It is with great pleasure that we present the first issue of the second volume of the *Journal of Economics, Law and Society* (JELS), published by the [Economic and Social Research Institute \(ESREIN\)](#). Now entering its second year of publication, JELS continues to grow in both substance and reach. We remain steadfast in our mission to provide a dynamic, interdisciplinary platform for scholarly dialogue, critical analysis, and research dissemination at the intersection of economics, law, finance, and broader social issues.

Despite being a relatively young publication, JELS has made remarkable progress in building its academic presence. The journal is now indexed and abstracted in reputable platforms such as [Google Scholar](#), [CrossRef](#), [ResearchBib](#), [Index Copernicus](#), [Scilit](#), [Zenodo](#), and [OpenAIRE](#). Our goal remains to further elevate the journal's visibility and academic recognition by seeking inclusion in leading citation indices such as Scopus and the Web of Science. This commitment reflects not only our internal dedication but also the quality of submissions we continue to attract from researchers around the world.

This issue showcases five diverse and timely contributions that reflect the broad aims and scope of the journal. Each article addresses contemporary challenges and proposes informed perspectives grounded in empirical evidence or theoretical innovation. Below, we offer a brief overview of each contribution:

1. Wasatiyah Optimization in Sustainable Wealth Management

Author: Prof. Dr. Tariquillah Khan

In this compelling paper, Prof. Khan introduces a novel framework for Islamic Wealth Management based on the principle of *Wasatiyah* (moderation). He presents the concept of **Normalized Balance Coordinates** (NBCs) as a multidimensional performance metric that balances ethical, environmental, and economic considerations. The paper provides practical strategies through the STO (Substitutions, Transformations, Offsets) model and challenges the paradigm of wealth maximization, proposing instead a holistic, values-driven approach to financial sustainability. This contribution represents an important theoretical and practical advancement in Islamic economics and finance.

2. Total Factor Productivity and Foreign Human Capital – Evidence from the Western Balkans

Authors: Daria Hukic and Faruk Hadzic

This empirical study investigates the relationship between foreign human capital and innovation in the Western Balkans, with a focus on Total Factor Productivity as a measure of innovation. Employing instrumental variable techniques to control for endogeneity, the authors provide nuanced insights into how diaspora and immigration patterns influence productivity across sectors. Their findings are especially valuable for policymakers striving to bridge human capital gaps and leverage migration as a catalyst for development in transitional economies.

3. Profitability and Resilience: Comparative Analysis of the Performance of Islamic and Conventional Insurance Companies in the GCC Region

Author: Abdulrahim Amrullah

Against the backdrop of a rapidly growing global *Takaful* industry, this paper offers a rigorous comparative analysis of Islamic and conventional insurance firms in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) region. Utilizing a decade of panel data and SGMM estimation, the author identifies key performance differences, revealing that while *Takaful* firms generally operate with lower capitalization and solvency, they exhibit stronger premium growth. This work not only deepens our understanding of the region's insurance landscape but also highlights the sector's adaptability in the face of macroeconomic challenges, including COVID-19.

4. Structuring Islamic Financial Literacy Construct to Measure Islamic Banking Products Adoption in Uganda: Content Validation of the Survey Instrument

Authors: Yusuf Kaweesa and Romzie Rosman

With Islamic banking still in its infancy in Uganda, this study contributes to foundational knowledge by developing and validating a survey instrument to measure Islamic financial literacy. Using a structured five-stage validation process and expert panels, the authors establish content validity for a tool that will be crucial in understanding adoption trends of Islamic financial products in emerging markets. The study lays the groundwork for future empirical work and highlights the importance of localized, context-specific measures in Islamic finance research.

5. Crowdfunding: The End of an Era or a Course Correction? A Bibliometric Analysis

Author: Shadi Al Shebli

In this bibliometric investigation, the author examines the lifecycle of crowdfunding research, tracing its rise from 2010 and the notable decline since 2020. Utilizing co-authorship and citation network analyses within a Kuhnian theoretical framework, the study identifies three distinct research phases and suggests that the decline may signal a paradigm shift rather than a loss of interest. The paper also advocates for greater use of network science to enhance future bibliometric studies. This is a significant contribution for researchers and editors tracking scholarly trends and intellectual evolution within financial innovation.

Together, the articles in this issue reflect the broad vision of JELS—to bridge disciplines, regions, and methodological approaches in the pursuit of knowledge that addresses real-world challenges. We are deeply grateful to all contributing authors for entrusting us with their work and to our anonymous reviewers, whose insightful and constructive feedback helped refine and strengthen each submission. Their expertise and dedication remain critical to maintaining the academic standards of this journal.

As Editor-in-Chief, I take this opportunity to thank all authors for choosing JELS as the platform for disseminating their important work. We also extend our deepest appreciation to our dedicated peer reviewers, whose valuable and constructive feedback ensured the academic rigor and integrity of each published paper. Your commitment is vital to the success and credibility of this journal.

We encourage researchers and scholars from all relevant disciplines to consider submitting their original research, reviews, and case studies for the [second issue of Volume 2](#), scheduled for publication at the end of this year. As we continue to improve and build our international reputation, your contributions play a central role in shaping the academic dialogue that JELS strives to foster.

We remain committed to our mission and look forward to continued collaboration with the global scholarly community.

Sincerely,

Edib Smolo

*The Co-Founder & Editor-in-Chief
Journal of Economics, Law & Society (JELS)*

Wasatiyah Optimization in Sustainable Wealth Management

Tariqullah Khan^{1*}

¹ INCEIF University, Malaysia

*Email: tariqullah.khan@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Wealth generation and management are pivotal for sustainability. This paper explores the crucial role of wealth management in achieving regenerative sustainability, advocating for wealth optimization over maximization. It introduces a novel framework for Islamic Wealth Management (IWM) centered on regenerative and sustainable wealth creation, guided by the Islamic principle of Wasatiyah (moderation). This framework aims to integrate financial success with ethical responsibilities and spiritual well-being. A key innovation is the Normalized Balance Coordinates (NBCs), a generalized, unified measure applicable to various contexts involving tensions and trade-offs. The NBCs, initially conceived as Normalized Wasatiyah Coordinates (NWCs) for IWM, employ a two-dimensional Cartesian system with axes normalized between -1 and 1. This system provides a unified measure of performance across competing priorities, such as economic growth vs. balance of natural systems, efficiency vs. equity, quality vs. quantity, and full employment vs. price stability. In the context of IWM, the NBCs assess both ethical and financial performance, where positive coordinates reflect adherence to Wasatiyah principles, while negative coordinates highlight areas for improvement. The paper outlines regenerative transition strategies for each quadrant, using Substitutions, Transformations, and Offsets (STOs) to guide decision-makers through diverse situations. By integrating ethical considerations with financial strategies (or, more broadly, balancing competing priorities), the NBCs framework offers a holistic model that views wealth (or any resource under consideration) as a sacred trust with inherent social, environmental, and spiritual dimensions. The paper concludes by emphasizing the transformative potential of the NBCs approach in promoting holistic balancing optimization, as opposed to singular maximization, and fostering a more equitable, sustainable, and ethically grounded global system.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received: Februar 17, 2025

Accepted: June 2, 2025

Published: June 30, 2025

KEYWORDS

Sustainable Wealth Management; Normalized Wasatiyah Coordinates; Normalized Balanced Coordinates; Islamic Economics; Regenerative Transition

JEL CODES

O44; P4; Q2; Q5

HOW TO CITE

Khan, T. (2025). Wasatiyah Optimization in Sustainable Wealth Management. *Journal of Economics, Law and Society*, 2(1), 5-28. <https://doi.org/10.70009/jels.2025.2.1.1>

1. INTRODUCTION

The prevailing maximization paradigms of generating and managing wealth have delivered a dual-edged legacy for humanity. As documented in the United Nations Human Development Report (UNDP 2024), on one side, unprecedented advancement in technology and economic development have significantly improved global life expectancy and quality of life, lifting millions out of poverty and providing access to better education, healthcare, and living standards. Yet, this progress has not come without profound costs. Persistent challenges, such as absolute poverty, hunger, inadequate health services, stark inequalities, and widespread social exclusion, continue to plague societies. Compounding these socio-economic dilemmas is the alarming degradation of natural systems upon which human survival depends (IPCC 2023). Rampant resource depletion, biodiversity loss, and the escalating impacts of climate change (SRC 2023, GFN (2024), underscore the urgent need for a

reorientation of our wealth creation and management strategies, ensuring their compatibility with intergenerational sustainability.

The current global context is simultaneously fraught with challenges and ripe with opportunities for transformation (Elkington 2020). A growing consciousness driven by data accessibility, stringent sustainability regulations (European Union 2024), greener technologies (Arbib and Seba 2020), and shifting consumer and investor preferences (Costanza, R., et. al. 1997, Cohen-Shacham et al. 2016, NZAMI 2024) offers a window of opportunity for regenerative thinking such as circular economy (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2013, Hawken 2017 and 2021, Raworth 2017, Stahel 2019, Khan 2024), as alternatives to traditional open loop linear paradigms. In this evolving environment, Islamic Wealth Management (IWM) stands as a significant stakeholder, uniquely poised to offer a holistic and balanced perspective rooted in the enduring Islamic principle of *Wasatiyah* - moderation.

Wasatiyah embodies the essence of balance, moderation, and the avoidance of extremes. It is a guiding principle that underscores the need for harmonious coexistence between competing priorities - material, social, and spiritual. In the realm of wealth management, it challenges the conventional dichotomy between profit maximization and ethical responsibility, advocating for an integrative approach that harmonizes financial prosperity with the preservation of societal, environmental, and spiritual well-being.

Kamali (2015) presents an authoritative and comprehensive compendium of *Wasatiyah* in the Islamic thought and civilization. Azid et. al. (2022) invite their readers to think about the behavioral and religious issues related to the different dimensions of wealth management. There is an exhaustive literature on IWM. Most of these works focus on wealth maximization given the *Halal* parameters. *Wasatiyah* is not a subject in discussions. However, *Wasatiyah* has been discussed in areas of consumption and lifestyle as *Israf* (wastage) and *Tabzeer* (squandering) are strongly abhorred in Islamic teachings (Biplob and Abdullah 2021). Haneef and Imon (2024) examine this entanglement of Islamic wealth creation and management within conventional financial narratives of profit maximization and advocate a realignment with the broader Islamic economic vision of *Wasatiyah*.

In the present paper we call for wealth optimization instead of wealth maximization. The paper introduces the Normalized *Wasatiyah* Coordinates (NWCs) framework, a conceptual tool designed to operationalize *Wasatiyah* within IWM. The NWCs is an extension of Normalized Sustainability Coordinates (NSCs) as expounded by Khan (2024). The framework draws upon multidimensional considerations, providing a structured yet adaptable model for aligning wealth management practices with the *Wasatiyah* ethos. By doing so, it offers a pathway for IWM practitioners to address contemporary challenges while fostering a sustainable and equitable wealth ecosystem. This exploratory framework invites further scholarly discussion, refinement, and empirical validation, with the goal of advancing Islamic wealth management as a leading proponent of moderation and sustainability in the global financial landscape.

2. CORE PRINCIPLES OF ISLAMIC WEALTH MANAGEMENT

The set of principles guiding Islamic wealth management are visualized in [Figure 1](#). These principles guide a broad spectrum of Islamic businesses, household behaviors, organizations and policies including wealth management.

2.1. Khalifa and Stewardship

In Muslim economic thinking (Siddiqi 1981), the principle of *Khalifa* and stewardship emphasizes that Allah (swt) is the ultimate owner of all creation, including wealth and property. Humans are appointed as trustees (*Khalifa*) on Earth, entrusted with specific moral responsibilities. Stewardship

implies ethical and sustainable use of resources, ensuring that wealth and assets are utilized responsibly for the benefit of all, including future generations. It highlights the responsibility of humans to act as caretakers, preserving resources and maintaining ecological balance as a divine mandate.

On the other extreme, opposing this vicegerency role, Al-Quran (Chapter 28, verses 76-82) talks about the story of Qarun. He was a historical personality from the nation of Prophet Musa, characterized as an excessively materialistic, highly wealthy, ungrateful, and arrogant individual who boasted that his wealth was the result of his knowledge. He was destroyed by Allah (swt) for his attitude of arrogance, unbridled acts of material pursuits and corrupt practices.

Figure 1: Core principles of Islamic wealth management

Source: Drawn by author.

2.2. Meezan (Universal Balance)

As opposed to Qarun's unbalanced regime, *Meezan* refers to justice and a balance between economic, social, and natural systems as discussed by several Islamic scholars and researchers (Al-Mubarak and Goud 2018). Humans, as trustees, are instructed not to transgress this balance, which is seen as part of Allah's will. As visualized in [Figure 2](#), *Meezan* underscores the interdependence of environmental, societal, and economic dimensions, promoting policies and practices that do not harm one aspect while benefiting another. It also calls for fairness and justice in transactions and resource distribution, avoiding exploitation or overconsumption.

IWM encourages investments in sectors that promote health, wellness, *halal* and organic Agri and dairy products, renewable energy, water, and nature-friendly businesses, aligning with the emphasis on preserving creation's natural equilibrium. Demographic equilibrium through business strategies aligned with preservation of families and future generations and intergenerational wealth distribution through inheritance and balancing the long-term perspective of sustainability with short-term efficiency.

The holistic framework of *Meezan*, or universal balance, imparts to IWM several important moral sentiments that are worth exploring further. At the core is a deep reverence for the delicate equilibrium and harmony ordained by the Creator within the various systems of the cosmos - economic, social, environmental, biological, and so on. This instills a profound sense of humility and responsibility in the human being as owner or manager of wealth, who is viewed not as the owner or master, but rather as a trustee and caretaker tasked with maintaining their balance.

This moral sentiment manifests in a heightened awareness of the interconnectedness of all things. One’s IWM actions and decisions cannot be evaluated in isolation but must be considered in the context of their broader impacts on the intricate web of natural and societal relationships. There is an ethical imperative for the owner and manager alike to think holistically and long-term, anticipating how one’s wealth management pursuits, for example, might have downstream effects on social justice or the environment.

Figure 2: Meezan: Justice, Balance and Dynamic Equilibrium

Source: Drawn by author based on Al-Mubarak, T. and Goud, B. (2018)

Closely related is the sentiment of balance and moderation, just as the divine plan has established an ideal equilibrium, the virtuous path for the human is one of avoiding extremes - whether that be excessive asceticism or unchecked materialism. There is a moral beauty in finding the middle way, the point of harmony where neither the individual nor the collective is shortchanged.

Furthermore, the *Meezan* principle instills a sense of humility and limits. While wealth owners are granted stewardship over creation, they must recognize that they do not have the wisdom or authority to transgress the balance the Almighty sets. There is an ethical duty to operate within the prescribed boundaries, not seeking to arrogate godlike powers of manipulation and control.

Lastly, this framework of balance cultivates a moral sentiment of justice and inclusion. The equilibrium envisioned is not merely a technical or ecological one but must extend to the social and economic realms as well. Wealth, resources, and opportunity cannot be allowed to become concentrated in the hands of the few at the expense of the many. True balance requires a just circulation and distribution that uplifts the whole of society.

2.3. Maqasid Al-Shari’ah

The overarching objectives of Islamic law aim to enhance the welfare of society across multiple dimensions: religion, life, intellect, progeny, and wealth. This is pursued in a multidimensional

system where economy, society and nature are embedded. *Maqasid Al-Shari'ah* provides a framework for ensuring holistic development (Chapra 2007), where economic activities are aligned with ethical and spiritual goals. It integrates well-being at individual and societal levels, emphasizing justice, equity, and sustainability. Siddiqi (2013), Dasuki and Bouheraoua (2011), Asutay and Harningtyas (2015) and several scholars call for Islamic finance – wealth creation and management to align with the *Maqasid Al-Shari'ah*.

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) standards have become increasingly important in wealth management in recent years. As investors and clients seek to align their investments with their values, ESG factors have emerged as key considerations. Wealth managers must now demonstrate how they incorporate ESG principles into their investment strategies and decision-making processes. This includes evaluating the environmental impact, social responsibility, and corporate governance of potential investments. By adhering to ESG standards, wealth managers can appeal to a growing segment of the market that prioritizes sustainable and ethical investing.

For Islamic wealth management, it is important to not only comply with ESG standards, but to also align investments and practices with the principles of *Maqasid Al-Shari'ah*. This includes ensuring investments are *halal* and promoting family values as emphasized by Siddiqi (2013) and Khan (2024b) and upholding religious and moral obligations. Wealth managers catering to Muslim clients must demonstrate how their offerings fulfill the higher objectives of Shari'ah law, such as preserving faith, life, lineage, intellect, and wealth. By integrating ESG and *Maqasid Al-Shari'ah*, Islamic wealth management can provide a holistic approach that meets the financial and spiritual needs of clients. **Figure 3** visualizes representation of the key principles and considerations regarding the adaptation of family values and *Maqasid Al-Shari'ah* aligned ESG standards in Islamic wealth management.

The intertwined concepts of *Meezan* and *Maqasid Al-Shari'ah* provide a profound framework for sustainable wealth management by emphasizing the interconnectedness of economic, social, spiritual and environmental systems. Unlike traditional approaches that prioritize short-term financial gains, the *Meezan* and *Maqasid* principles demand a holistic perspective where wealth creation is intrinsically linked to maintaining ecological balance, social justice, and long-term sustainability. By viewing wealth managers as trustees rather than absolute owners, this approach encourages investment strategies that generate value not just financially, but also in terms of societal well-being and environmental preservation. The balance inherent in *Meezan* ensures that wealth generation does not come at the cost of depleting natural resources, undermining social structures, or compromising the potential for future generations. This means evaluating investments not merely by their immediate financial returns, but by their broader impact on systemic equilibrium - considering how each economic decision ripples through social networks, ecological systems, and intergenerational potential. Such a comprehensive approach transforms wealth management from a purely extractive model to a regenerative practice that actively contributes to maintaining and enhancing the delicate interconnected systems that sustain human and planetary prosperity.

2.4. Values and Compliance

Compliance with Shari'ah principles and the laws of the jurisdiction, alongside adhering to universal ethical values in business and governance, is an imperative. This principle promotes transparency, accountability, and fair dealing in wealth management. It ensures that financial activities respect both divine laws and the state's regulatory standards, creating trust and integrity within markets.

2.5. Offsets and Purification

Wealth must be purified from negative externalities, including social inequalities and environmental pollution, through mechanisms such as: *Zakah* (purification), *Sadaqah*, *Awqaf*, *Infaq*,

inheritance, free loans, etc. This principle ensures that wealth creation aligns with social justice, reducing disparities and addressing the harm caused by business activities. It serves as a corrective tool, redirecting excess wealth to uplift marginalized groups and protect the environment.

Figure 3: Aligning the ESG framework with Family and Maqasid Al Shari’ah

Source: Drawn by author

3. NORMALIZED WASATIYAH COORDINATES

Wasatiyah advocates for a balanced lifestyle, integrating and unifying material (*Dunya*) and spiritual (*Akhirah*) dimensions and requiring a unified measure. It promotes a middle path in all activities, including personal habits, business practices, and governance. Wasatiyah avoids extremes, whether in consumption, investment, or social interactions, ensuring harmony between individual needs, societal welfare and environmental balance. In practice, it calls for sustainable and regenerative development models where economic growth is aligned with ethical considerations and environmental preservation.

From the perspective of *Khalifa* and Stewardship, we can see a strong sense of responsibility and accountability emerging. The idea that wealth and resources ultimately belong to Allah, and humans are merely trustees or caretakers, implies a moral duty to manage these assets in a way that pleases the Creator and benefits society. This sentiment of being a steward rather than an owner shapes one's mindset and ethical orientation

The principle of *Meezan*, or Universal Balance, points to a moral sentiment around the importance of harmony and equilibrium. There is an ethical imperative to avoid upsetting the delicate balance between economic, social, and natural systems that Allah has ordained. This calls for considering the broader, systemic impacts of one's wealth management decisions, rather than just narrow self-interest.

In the realm of Offsets and Purification, we see moral feelings around the need for atonement and cleansing. The recognition that wealth can become impure or tainted by negative externalities motivates the use of tools like *Zakah*, *Sadaqah*, and other offsets to rectify these harms. This reflects a sentiment of seeking purity and social justice. The *Maqasid Al-Shari'ah* objectives of enhancing religion, life, intellect, progeny, and wealth points to an expansive, holistic moral vision. Wealth is not merely for personal gain but must be managed in service of these higher purposes ordained by the divine. This cultivates a sentiment of stewardship over a narrow individualistic mindset.

Finally, the principle of, or moderation, gestures towards a moral sentiment of balance and avoiding extremes. The path of virtue lies in the middle, rejecting both excessive asceticism and unbridled materialism. This promotes an ethical orientation of balance, temperance, and equilibrium in one's lifestyle and relationship to the material world. Collectively, these Islamic economic principles reveal a treasure of moral sentiments - responsibility, harmony, purity, holistic higher purpose, and moderation.

The Islamic worldview is perfectly encapsulated in this supplication: "Our Lord! Give us in this world that is good and in the Hereafter that is good and protect us from the punishment of the Fire." Al-Qur'an (2:201).

Figure 4: The Balanced (Wasatiyah) framework of Islamic Economics

Source: Drawn by author

This is juxtaposed to behaviors like Qarun's behavior as mentioned above. In [Figure 4](#), by conceptualizing the *Akhirah*/Ethics dimension on one axis and the *Dunya*/Profits dimension on the other, it becomes possible to represent their relationship within a two-dimensional Cartesian framework. Each axis is normalized to range from -1 to 1, ensuring a consistent and comparable scale regardless of the underlying metrics or indicators chosen. In this setup, the sign and magnitude of the coordinates reflect the quality and intensity of each dimension: positive coordinates indicate alignment

with *Wasatiyah* principles, such as moral soundness and financial viability, while negative coordinates highlight areas in need of improvement. The resulting four quadrants formed by these two perpendicular axes then serve as a diagnostic map. A subject's position within one of these quadrants provides immediate insights into its overall state: whether it is ethically strong but financially weak, financially robust but ethically compromised, balanced and regenerative, or lacking on both fronts.

With a view to present a robust conceptual framework for Islamic wealth management, we extend Khan's (2024) framework of Normalized Sustainability Coordinates (NSCs). We illustrate that Normalized *Wasatiyah* Coordinates (NWCs) can serve as diagnostic tools across the four quadrants, and Substitutions, Transformations, and Offsets (STOs) can be employed as tailored regenerative transformation strategies for the wealth portfolio. The approach is rooted in Islamic ethical principles (*Akhirah* dimension) and sound financial stewardship (*Dunya* dimension), striving for a state of *Wasatiyah* - moderation and balance - consistent with the *Maqasid Al-Shari'ah*.

3.1. Defining NWCs:

X-Axis (Ethics - *Akhirah*): Reflects adherence to Islamic ethical norms and Shari'ah principles.

$x = 1$: The investment portfolio or wealth strategy fully aligns with Islamic principles - no involvement in haram activities (including *Riba*, *Gharar*, *Maysir*, unethical sectors), transparency, justice, and stewardship of Allah's resources.

$x = -1$: The approach is ethically compromised and violates Shari'ah, involving impermissible transactions, exploitation, harm to society or the environment, or neglect of *Zakah* and *Sadaqah* obligations.

Y-Axis (Profits - *Dunya*): Reflects material and financial performance within the guided Islamic framework.

$y = 1$: Wealth is growing sustainably, ensuring *halal* earnings, risk diversification aligned with Shari'ah, and delivering stable returns for stakeholders.

$y = -1$: The investment is unprofitable or unsustainable, leading to losses, wealth erosion, or financial instability that inhibits fulfilling obligations such as family welfare or charitable giving.

By plotting an Islamic wealth management strategy's NWCs (x, y), we identify four distinct quadrants:

3.2. Four Quadrants (4Q):

Quadrant I ($x \geq 0, y \geq 0$): Ethically and Shari'ah-wise sound and profitable. This is the *Wasatiyah* ideal - wealth management that is Shari'ah-compliant, socially responsible, and financially sustainable.

Quadrant II ($x \geq 0, y < 0$): Ethical and Shari'ah integrity is maintained, but profitability is lacking. The portfolio or strategy is Shari'ah-compliant but struggles financially.

Quadrant III ($x < 0, y < 0$): Both ethical and Shari'ah standards and profitability are compromised. The approach involves impermissible or dubious activities and is also financially detrimental, failing Islamic fiduciary and moral obligations.

Quadrant IV ($x < 0, y \geq 0$): Profitable but ethically and Shari'ah-wise tarnished. Although returns are generated, methods may involve haram sectors, violation of stewardship responsibilities, environmental harm, unjust practices, or neglect of other moral duties - contradicting Islamic wealth principles.

Although the NWCs framework categorizes states into four broad quadrants, it is essential to recognize that each quadrant encompasses a spectrum of possible normalized coordinates, and thus, varying levels of intensity or severity within that state. For example, in Quadrant II, a subject might hover just below the profit-neutral line with $(x=0.8, y=-0.1)$, indicating strong ethical performance but only slightly negative financial returns, while another subject in the same quadrant could be deeply embedded at $(x=0.9, y=-0.8)$, signifying a robust ethical standing but severe financial underperformance. Similarly, Quadrant IV might contain entities barely straying into unethical territory at $(x=-0.1, y=0.7)$, where only minor Substitutions might restore moral alignment, whereas entities further along at $(x=-0.9, y=0.9)$ would require more comprehensive Transformations to rebuild their ethical foundations. Even within Quadrant I, moving from a marginally positive position $(x=0.1, y=0.2)$ to an ideal regenerative scenario $(x=1.0, y=1.0)$ might entail progressively more nuanced Offsets and structural modifications. In all such cases, different intensities within the same quadrant will naturally demand tailored combinations of Substitutions, Transformations, and Offsets to effectively recalibrate toward a balanced and regenerative *Wasatiyah* state.

3.3. Transformation Strategies

To move toward Quadrant I or maintain the regenerative state, we employ three categories of interventions:

Substitutions (S): Replacing impermissible or harmful elements with permissible and morally sound alternatives.

Transformations (T): Implementing fundamental changes to the underlying wealth management structure - investment policies, governance, and long-term vision - in line with Islamic values.

Offsets (O): Taking compensatory steps to mitigate residual harms or imbalances, ensuring a path toward positive net ethical and financial gain.

3.3.1. Quadrant I: Positive Ethics, Positive Profits

The Islamic wealth strategy is both aligned with Shari'ah and financially stable. Investments uphold justice, transparency, and community welfare, and profits enable further good works - such as *Zakah*, *Waqf*, and charitable distributions. Though this quadrant represents the ideal *Wasatiyah* state, continuous improvement is essential to maintain resilience and spiritual growth. The regenerative transformation STO strategies for this state of wealth management will include the following.

Substitutions: Even when in an ideal state, subtle improvements can be made. For example, replace ethically neutral holdings with even more positive-impact Islamic financial instruments (e.g., moving from a basic *Sukuk* to a green *Sukuk* funding sustainable projects).

Transformations: Strengthen the Islamic governance framework by implementing Shari'ah advisory boards with more robust oversight. Adopt long-term Islamic sustainable investment strategies that foster environmental stewardship and reduce systemic financial risks (e.g., gradually shifting more capital into renewable energy or socially impactful ventures that align with Islamic social finance).

Offsets: In this positive state, offsets are proactive rather than corrective, allocating a portion of profits to innovative *Sadaqah Jariyah* projects (endowments in education, healthcare, or community uplift). Reinforce community ties by supporting local Islamic microfinance initiatives to help others achieve financial inclusion and stability.

As a result of these strategies a continuously improving, self-reinforcing virtuous cycle of *halal* wealth accumulation and ethical distribution, strengthening the Ummah and safeguarding future generations can be expected.

3.3.2. Quadrant II: Positive Ethics, Negative Profits

The portfolio is Shari'ah-compliant but underperforming financially. Although the manager avoids *Riba*, unethical industries, and speculative trades (*Gharar*, *Maysir*), economic returns are insufficient to sustain long-term goals or fulfill social responsibilities adequately. The STO strategies will entail the following.

Substitutions: Replace underperforming *halal* investments with equally ethical but more financially viable options. For instance, if certain Islamic funds are consistently under-delivering, substitute them with more competitive Shari'ah-compliant equities or *Sukuk* that have demonstrated stable returns. Move from a narrow commodity-based Islamic investment to a diversified *halal* portfolio including green technology or healthcare ventures that respect Islamic principles.

Transformations: Rethink financial strategies while maintaining ethical integrity. For instance, introduce risk-sharing partnerships (*Mudarabah* or *Musharakah*) with well-managed Islamic businesses that have growth potential. Develop a more sophisticated Islamic asset allocation model that balances risk and return under Shari'ah constraints, leveraging Islamic financial innovations and global *halal* market insights.

Offsets: While the primary goal is to improve financial stability, temporary offsets can help cushion transitions by seek Islamic micro-*takaful* (insurance) arrangements to mitigate risks. Negotiate temporary cost reductions or benefit from Islamic philanthropic funds that support capacity building for ethically driven but financially weak ventures.

As a result of these measures, elevating profitability without compromising on Shari'ah adherence, guiding the strategy toward Quadrant I where spiritual and financial well-being reinforce each other is expected.

3.3.3. Quadrant III: Negative Ethics, Negative Profits

This is the most critical state: The wealth management approach is both ethically and Shari'ah-wise flawed (involving haram, injustice, or exploitation) and unprofitable (leading to waste of resources and inability to fulfill Islamic obligations). Immediate and fundamental reforms are needed. The following are examples of potential STO strategies.

Substitutions: Remove investments in haram industries (alcohol, gambling, conventional finance with *Riba*) and replace them with permissible and ethically neutral or positive assets. Even if initial financial returns are modest, the priority is to eliminate unethical income streams promptly.

Transformations: Overhaul the entire wealth management framework by establishing a Shari'ah governance structure, employing qualified Shari'ah scholars to audit current holdings and ensure compliance. Transform the business model to prioritize *Maqasid al-Shari'ah* and ensuring financial instruments promote justice, prevent harm, and contribute positively to society. Integrate *halal* risk-sharing modes (like *Musharakah* and *Mudarabah*) instead of relying on interest-bearing loans or exploitative profit-making schemes.

Offsets: In the interim, use offsets to address and compensate for the past damage by dedicating a portion of remaining capital or future gains to environmental restoration, social welfare projects, or

community development (e.g., providing interest-free loans (*Qard Hasan*) to small *halal* businesses). Engage in immediate *Zakah* or *Sadaqah* to purify wealth and rectify injustices caused by previous unethical investments.

A step-by-step regeneration that gradually lifts the strategy out of degeneracy, first stabilizing ethically and then building toward financial soundness, ultimately moving towards Quadrant I.

3.3.4. Quadrant IV: Negative Ethics, Positive Profits

The wealth management is financially successful but involves unethical or Shari'ah-noncompliant elements. High returns may come from questionable sectors (e.g., *Riba*-based finance, exploitative industries) or from investments that neglect moral obligations (no attention to *Zakah*, hoarding wealth). Examples of potential STO strategies include the following.

Substitutions: Substitute haram or doubtful asset classes with Shari'ah-compliant alternatives – for example replace conventional bonds with *Sukuk*. Divest from exploitative labor-intensive industries to Islamic socially responsible investments that honor fair wages, just treatment of workers, and environmental care.

Transformations: Ethical realignment is crucial like implementing a formal Shari'ah compliance framework and periodic Shari'ah audits. Transforming the investment philosophy to embrace *Ihsan* (excellence) and *Amanah* (trust), ensuring wealth is a means to serve people and please Allah, not merely accumulate returns.

Offsets: While transitioning, employ offsets to address legacy issues redirecting a portion of profits into Islamic charitable institutions, *waqf* (endowments), or projects that rectify social harm. If the portfolio benefited from unethical gains, use purified capital (through *Sadaqah*) to compensate communities adversely affected. Gradually restoring ethical equilibrium without losing the financial foundation, the portfolio now contributes positively to society and aligns with divine guidance, nearing Quadrant I's ethical-financial harmony.

In Islamic wealth management, NWCs serve as a spiritual-ethical and financial compass, pinpointing the current state relative to the *Wasatiyah* ideal. The four quadrants clarify the nature of deficiencies - whether moral, financial, or both - and STO strategies provide concrete, Shari'ah-consistent pathways for regenerative transformation. The aim is to achieve a state of balanced, harmonious wealth stewardship, reflecting the Islamic ideals of justice, responsibility, moderation, and benefit to all of Creation.

4. MATHEMATICAL FRAMEWORK

Below is a formal mathematical framework that translates the *Wasatiyah* conceptual model into an optimization problem. While this model can be elaborated in various ways depending on context and application, the formulation presented here captures the essence of seeking a balanced (moderate) solution that is ethically sound (*Akhirah*-focused) and materially beneficial (*Dunya*-focused).

Model Components:

1. Decision Variables:
 - Let $x \in [-1,1]$ represent the ethics (*Akhirah*) dimension. Here:
 - $x = 1$ corresponds to the highest ethical standard.

- $x = 0$ represents an ethically neutral stance.
- $x = -1$ corresponds to completely unethical behavior.
- Let $y \in [-1,1]$ represent the material profit (Dunya) dimension. Here:
 - $y = 1$ corresponds to maximum profit realization.
 - $y = 0$ represents a neutral (break-even) financial outcome.
 - $y = -1$ corresponds to significant material loss.

2. Quadrant Interpretation:

The Cartesian plane is divided into four quadrants based on the signs of x and y :

- Quadrant I ($x \geq 0, y \geq 0$): Balanced region where both ethics and profits are non-negative.
- Quadrant II ($x \geq 0, y < 0$): Ethically sound but financially detrimental.
- Quadrant III ($x < 0, y < 0$): Both ethically and financially negative.
- Quadrant IV ($x < 0, y \geq 0$): Financially profitable but ethically unsound.

The *Wasatiyah* principle favors solutions in Quadrant I as it strives for a positive and balanced outcome on both dimensions.

3. Objective of *Wasatiyah*:

The principle of *Wasatiyah* suggests not only maximizing each dimension but doing so in a way that reflects moderation and balance. A purely profit-maximizing solution ignoring ethics (Quadrant IV) or a purely ethical solution ignoring economic viability (Quadrant II) does not fulfill the *Wasatiyah* spirit. Similarly, a solution that fails on both fronts (Quadrant III) is undesirable.

Wasatiyah implies simultaneously achieving positive ethics and profits in a balanced manner.

4. Objective Functions:

(a) Multi-Objective Formulation:

We can initially frame this as a multi-objective optimization:

Maximize (x, y) Subject to $x, y \in [-1, 1]$.

This seeks to maximize ethics and profits simultaneously. However, this leaves open the possibility of solutions that are extreme in one dimension but lack balance.

(b) Balanced Single-Objective Function:

To ensure the concept of *Wasatiyah* (moderation and balance), we can combine the two objectives into a single function that rewards balanced improvement. One common approach is to use a product form, which inherently requires both dimensions to be strong:

Maximize $f(x, y) = x \cdot y$ Subject to $x, y \in [-1, 1]$.

This product is the highest when both x and y are large and positive, encouraging solutions in

Quadrant I where both ethics and profits are optimized. If one dimension is small or negative, the product diminishes, discouraging unbalanced solutions.

Alternatively, we could use a function that emphasizes closeness and positivity, such as:

Maximize $g(x, y) = \min\{x, y\}$ Subject to: $x, y \in [0, 1]$.

This formulation maximizes the lower bound of the two, ensuring that we do not sacrifice one dimension for the other. For instance, if $x = 1$ and $y = 0.5$, then $g(x, y) = 0.5$. To improve this, we need to raise y closer to x , encouraging balanced growth.

5. Constraints and Modifications:

- To strictly ensure that we are considering “*Wasatiyah*” as positive ethical and profitable solutions, we can require: $x \geq 0, y \geq 0$.
- If the decision space allows solutions in other quadrants, the optimization will naturally push towards Quadrant I if the objective is to maximize $x \cdot y$. However, if we want to limit consideration strictly to Quadrant I, then:

$$0 \leq x \leq 1, 0 \leq y \leq 1.$$

6. Final Optimization Problem:

Option 1 (Product-based objective):

Maximize $x \cdot y$

subject to:

$$0 \leq x \leq 1,$$

$$0 \leq y \leq 1.$$

Option 2 (Minimum-of-two-based objective):

Maximize $\min\{x, y\}$

subject to:

$$0 \leq x \leq 1,$$

$$0 \leq y \leq 1.$$

Both formulations ensure that the optimal solution is one that improves both ethics and profits simultaneously, reflecting the *Wasatiyah* principle of moderation and balance. The product-based objective will be maximal at $(x, y) = (1,1)$, while the min-based objective also encourages moving both dimensions toward their upper bound to maximize the minimum.

7. Interpretation and Extensions:

- The chosen objective function can be adjusted to incorporate different value systems,

priorities, or constraints. For example, we might place additional weights if certain ethical considerations are more critical than marginal profit gains:

$$\text{Maximize } W(x, y) = \alpha x + \beta y - \gamma|x - y|$$

where α , β , and γ are parameters that reflect the importance of each dimension and the desire for balance.

- o Additional constraints can represent policy requirements, resource limitations, or social impact thresholds. For example:

$$x \geq x_{\min} > 0, y \geq y_{\min} > 0$$

ensures at least some minimal level of ethical and financial performance.

In summary, this formal mathematical model for *Wasatiyah* optimization treats the problem of achieving balanced and positive outcomes in both ethics (*Akhirah*) and profits (*Dunya*) dimensions as an optimization problem on the two-dimensional plane $[-1,1]^2$, with objectives and constraints chosen to emphasize the quadrant (Quadrant I) and nature (balanced positivity) that *Wasatiyah* embodies.

4.1. Quadrant III Regenerative Transformation towards Quadrant I

Quadrant III is a special case where ethics and financial performance are both not meeting the minimum required conditions and urgently require radical transformation. We suggest a formal optimization model for improving a Quadrant III state, for example with NWCs $(x, y) = (-0.5, -0.5)$ toward Quadrant I ($x \geq 0, y \geq 0$) using three types of interventions – Substitutions (S), Transformations (T), and Offsets (O) to optimize a *Wasatiyah* objective function. The model is based on the normalized *Wasatiyah* coordinates (NWCs).

Context:

- o We start with an initial NWCs situation diagnosed as $(x_{\text{initial}}, y_{\text{initial}}) = (-0.5, -0.5)$ in Quadrant III, where both ethics (*Akhirah*) and profits (*Dunya*) are negative.
- o We have three categories of interventions:
 1. Substitutions (S): These could represent replacing negative practices or frameworks with neutral or more positive ones.
 2. Transformations (T): These could represent deeper structural or systemic changes that shift the underlying paradigm from unethical/unprofitable to more ethically sound and profitable.
 3. Offsets (O): These could represent compensatory measures or supportive policies that help lift performance in both dimensions.

The goal is to use these interventions to improve the NWCs from Quadrant III to Quadrant I, where both x and y are nonnegative, and to do so in a way that maximizes a “*Wasatiyah* function.” The *Wasatiyah* principle suggests balanced improvement: pushing both ethics and profits toward positive synergy.

Decision Variables:

- Let $s \geq 0$ be the intensity level of Substitution interventions.
- Let $t \geq 0$ be the intensity level of Transformation interventions.
- Let $o \geq 0$ be the intensity level of Offset interventions.

These variables represent how much of each intervention we apply. They are continuous variables that can be scaled according to the problem context.

Parameters:

We assume each type of intervention contributes incrementally and positively to both ethics (x) and profits (y). Define the parameters that represent the efficacy of each intervention:

- $a_s, a_t, a_o > 0$: The incremental gains to the ethics dimension (x) per unit of S, T, and O interventions, respectively.
- $b_s, b_t, b_o > 0$: The incremental gains to the profits dimension (y) per unit of S, T, and O interventions, respectively.

These parameters are context-dependent and must be estimated or assigned based on how effective each intervention type is in improving the NWCs.

State Equations:

The final NWCs after applying the interventions are:

$$x_{\text{final}} = x_{\text{initial}} + a_s s + a_t t + a_o o = -0.5 + a_s s + a_t t + a_o o,$$

$$y_{\text{final}} = y_{\text{initial}} + b_s s + b_t t + b_o o = -0.5 + b_s s + b_t t + b_o o.$$

Feasibility Constraints:

To move from Quadrant III to Quadrant I, both final coordinates must be nonnegative:

$$x_{\text{final}} = -0.5 + a_s s + a_t t + a_o o \geq 0,$$

$$y_{\text{final}} = -0.5 + b_s s + b_t t + b_o o \geq 0,$$

These constraints ensure that the chosen levels of interventions are sufficient to bring the state out of negativity in both dimensions.

Objective Function (Wasatiyah Function):

A suitable *Wasatiyah* objective function encourages balanced improvement in both x and y. One natural choice is the product $x_{\text{final}} \cdot y_{\text{final}}$, which is only maximized when both are significantly positive and balanced. Thus:

$$\text{Maximize } W(x_{\text{final}}, y_{\text{final}}) = x_{\text{final}} \cdot y_{\text{final}}$$

Substituting, we get:

$$\text{Maximize } s, t, o: (-0.5 + a_s s + a_t t + a_o o)(-0.5 + b_s s + b_t t + b_o o)$$

Maximizing this product ensures that we do not merely shift one dimension to positivity at the

expense of the other. Instead, both must improve for the objective to increase significantly, reflecting the *Wasatiyah* principle of balanced moderation and synergy.

Nonnegativity Constraints:

$$S \geq 0, t \geq 0, o \geq 0.$$

Complete Optimization Model:

Maximize s, t, o :

$$(-0.5 + ass + att + aoo). (-0.5 + bss + btt + boo)$$

Subject to:

$$-0.5 + ass + att + aoo \geq 0,$$

$$-0.5 + bss + btt + boo \geq 0,$$

$$s \geq 0, t \geq 0, o \geq 0.$$

Interpretation and Extensions:

- This model identifies the best “mix” of interventions (S, T, O) to pull the NWCs out of Quadrant III and into Quadrant I while maximizing a measure of balanced success.
- If desired, additional constraints can be included to limit resources, cap intervention levels, or incorporate other policy or ethical requirements.
- The parameter values as, at, ao, bs, bt, bo can be tuned to reflect realistic impact assessments of each intervention strategy.

By solving this optimization problem, one obtains the optimal intervention strategy that achieves the *Wasatiyah*-inspired improvement from an initially negative ethical and profit state to a more balanced, positive outcome.

The NWCs framework as a unified measure of ethical and financial performance fundamentally distinguishes itself from conventional financial models through its holistic, multi-dimensional approach to wealth management. Traditional financial frameworks, such as Modern Portfolio Theory or Capital Asset Pricing Model, primarily focus on risk-adjusted returns and quantitative financial metrics, treating ethical considerations as peripheral or irrelevant. In contrast, the NWCs model integrates ethical performance as a co-equal dimension with financial performance, presenting a more comprehensive optimization strategy. Unlike Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) approaches that often treat ethical considerations as secondary screening mechanisms, NWCs embed ethical evaluation into the core mathematical structure of wealth management.

As an extension of the normalized sustainability coordinates (NSCs), the NWCs four-quadrant diagnostic system provides a more nuanced assessment than binary ethical screening, offering detailed regenerative transformation strategies through Substitutions, Transformations, and Offsets. Where contemporary sustainable finance models typically rely on negative screening - like Shari’ah Screening, or passive ESG integration, NWCs based on Circular-ESG framework, propose an active, dynamic approach to unified (ethical-financial) optimization. The framework’s mathematical formulation allows for precise quantification of ethical and financial performance, addressing a critical limitation in existing responsible investing (SRI) models that struggle to measure and integrate moral dimensions systematically. By presenting a structured methodology that treats ethics

and profitability as interdependent variables rather than competing priorities, the NWCs framework represents a significant epistemological shift in understanding wealth management - from a reductive, profit-maximization paradigm to a more holistic, regenerative approach that recognizes the intrinsic interconnectedness of financial and ethical systems.

5. ILLUSTRATIVE EMPIRICAL CASE STUDY

It is often perceived as difficult to develop robust rubric for the ethical dimension and to test the *Wasatiyah* framework empirically. To further elaborate this important point, and to offer an illustrative empirical case, in **Table 1** we present a hypothetical example of 4 *Halal* restaurants. The total mf-ESG scores are 100 and the *Halal* threshold scores are 20. The 4 *Halal* restaurants score differently on the different rubrics. Although all the 4 restaurants are *Halal* - Restaurant 1’s mf-ESG scores are 45; Restaurant 2’s mf-ESG scores are 60; Restaurant 3’s mf-ESG scores are 80; and Restaurant 4’s mf-ESG scores are 95.

Table 1: The Maqasid and Family aligned ESG (mf-ESG) of Halal Restaurants

Mf-ESG Scores Total 100	mf-ESG Rubrics	Halal Restaurant 1	Halal Restaurant 2	Halal Restaurant 3	Halal Restaurant 4
Maqasid Aligned ENVIRONMENTAL DIMENSION (mE) Total scores 20	Waste reduction				
	Water usage				
	Clean energy usage	2.5	10	20	20
	Biodiversity support				
	Green supply chain				
Maqasid Aligned SOCIAL DIMENSION(S) Total scores 20	Hygiene and usage of Plastic				
	Zakah, Awqaf, Kafala, Infaq/ CSR				
	Families support				
	Health and Safety	2.5	10	10	20
	Workers’ rights				
Maqasid Aligned GOVERNANCE DIMENSION (G) Total scores 20	Local community impact				
	Supply chain				
	Maqasid alignment of Shari’ah governance				
	Corporate governance and board diversity	5	10	10	20
	Ethics standards				
Maqasid Aligned FAMILY DIMENSION (F) Total scores 20	Transparency and disclosures				
	Executive compensation				
	Family centric corporate values and policies, parental leaves, childcare support, children’s educational allow- ance, family health insurance grandparents included, family-oriented community activitie	15	10	20	15
	Halal threshold scores 20	20	20	20	20
	Total mf-ESG Scores of Restaurants	45	60	80	95

Source: Hypothetical Table, prepared by the author for explanatory purposes.

Note: Please refer to Figure 3 above for the concept mf-ESG

Using the Min-max normalization formula to scale values from -1 to +1 we get the normalized balanced coordinates (NBCs) of **Table 2** for the ethics dimension. Since the profits’ rubric is not a

challenge, we assume the profits' coordinates as 0.5 for all restaurants. Paradoxically, it is evident that *Halal* restaurants 1 and 2 fall into Quadrant 4, scoring low on the ethical dimensions. The *Wasatiyah* model is helpful diagnostic to identify improvement areas.

6. FROM MAXIMIZATION TO OPTIMIZATION

The preceding discussion leads to rethinking the common wisdom of wealth management beyond profit maximization to address the shortcomings of the current paradigm. *Wasatiyah* resonates with and reimagine the broader intellectual and economic discourse of the past and the present.

Table 2: NBCs for Halal Restaurants

Restaurants	mf-ESG Scores, from Table 1	Normalized X Coordinates	Normalized Y coordinates (assumed)	Normalized Balanced Coordinates (NBCs)	Quadrant Placement, reference Figure 3
Restaurant 1	45	-1	0.5	-1, 0.5	QVI, low on ethics
Restaurant 2	60	-0.4	0.5	-0.4,0.5	QVI, low on ethics
Restaurant 3	80	0.4	0.5	0.4, 0.5	QI, High on ethics
Restaurant 4	95	1	0.5	1. 0.5	QI, High on ethics

Source: NBCs calculation based on hypothetical Table 1

Note: Min-max normalization formula to scale values from -1 to +1
 $X_{min} = \min(\text{mf_ESG_scores})$, $X_{max} = \max(\text{mf_ESG_scores})$

Normalized scores = $[2 * (x - X_{min}) / (X_{max} - X_{min}) - 1]$ for x in mf_ESG_scores]

6.1. Adam Smith’s Moral Sentiments vs. Modern Free Markets:

Adam Smith, often credited as the father of the free market economy, grounded his economic ideas in his earlier work (Smith 1759 on “*The Theory of Moral Sentiments*”). He believed that “sympathy, fairness, and moral responsibility” were essential underpinnings of human behavior. For Smith, free markets relied on individuals’ ability to temper self-interest with concern for others. Over time, however, free-market economics evolved under the assumption of “*homo economicus*” – an individual being rational only if purely selfish! This reductionist view drove the wealth management paradigm toward profit and wealth maximization, sidelining moral sentiments and ethical considerations. The *Wasatiyah* framework introduced in the early 7th century AD – in its renewed form, reintroduces Smith’s neglected moral dimension, advocating for a balanced and ethically guided approach to wealth management. It emphasizes moderation, interconnectedness, and social responsibility, preceding much early Smith’s idea of moral limits to selfishness.

6.2. Failures of Wealth Maximization:

The profit-maximization paradigm has led to wealth concentration in the hands of a few, exacerbating socio-economic divides. Overexploitation of natural resources and unsustainable practices has put unbearable pressures on natural systems. Ethical breaches in corporations, from financial scandals to exploitative practices, has eroded trust. *Wasatiyah* challenges this paradigm by promoting a regenerative and inclusive economic system, which aligns wealth management with ethical and environmental imperatives.

6.3. Economic Thought Beyond Smith:

Other intellectual traditions also support rethinking the wealth management paradigm. Sen (1999) focuses on what people can achieve, emphasizing well-being over material wealth. Raworth (2017) advocates for balancing economic activity within planetary and social boundaries. Rawls (1971)

highlights the need for equitable distribution of resources. Khan calls for regenerative humane transition. *Wasatiyah* fits into this broader conversation by offering a spiritually grounded framework that harmonizes financial goals with ethical imperatives, filling gaps left by secular approaches.

6.4. Need for a Broader Wealth Paradigm:

The global challenges of today - climate change, inequality, and exclusion and societal unrest - demand a shift from wealth maximization to wealth optimization. We must recognize that wealth is a trust (*Amanah*) rather than an individual possession, resonating with stewardship concepts in both religious and secular thought. Wealth is a means to achieve well-being and justice rather than an end. Integration of moral sentiments and social responsibility into economic decision-making is an imperative.

6.5. Broader Resonance of Wasatiyah:

Wasatiyah is central to Islamic religious beliefs: “*And thus, We have made you a justly balanced community that you will be witnesses over the people and the Messenger will be a witness on you...*” Al-Baqarah verse 143.

However, from a broader global perspective of free market economies, it is easy to comprehend that *Wasatiyah* reflects the moral sentiments Smith envisioned, integrating them into wealth management. It insists that the self-interest driving markets must be tempered with moderation and responsibility. It resonates with global calls for responsible market economies such as more than 325 signatories with USD 57.5 trillion in assets under management - committed to achieving Paris Agreement targets (NZAMI 2024) and other ethical investing, and stakeholder-oriented models.

Wealth maximization focuses on the unbounded pursuit of increasing profits and accumulating material resources, often as the primary or sole objective of economic activity. It typically emphasizes short-term financial gains, individual benefits, and the efficiency of resource utilization, with little regard for broader social, environmental, or ethical consequences. This approach often leads to negative externalities, such as inequality, environmental degradation, and exploitation, as it prioritizes self-interest and ignores the interconnectedness of economic systems with societal and ecological well-being.

In contrast, wealth optimization emphasizes balance, sustainability, and harmony between material prosperity and broader ethical, social, and environmental goals. It seeks to align wealth creation with moral responsibilities, including equity, justice, and the stewardship of resources. Rather than maximizing financial outcomes at any cost, wealth optimization aims for regenerative and inclusive progress, ensuring long-term resilience and well-being for both current and future generations. This paradigm considers wealth not just as a means of individual enrichment but as a tool for collective benefit and ethical responsibility.

Beyond its Islamic origins, the *Wasatiyah* framework offers a universally compelling approach to wealth management that transcends cultural and religious boundaries. The core principles of balance, ethical responsibility, and holistic well-being resonate with contemporary global economic challenges that demand more nuanced approaches to wealth creation. Secular economic philosophies from various traditions put emphasis on collective well-being, Indigenous economic models prioritizing community and ecological sustainability, and progressive Western economic thought championing stakeholder capitalism - share striking parallels with fundamental ethos of *Wasatiyah*. The framework’s mathematical modeling provides a translatable methodology that could be adapted to different cultural contexts by recalibrating the specific ethical and financial parameters. For instance, Western corporate social responsibility frameworks, Scandinavian stakeholder

economic models, and emerging sustainable development approaches all reflect similar impulses towards balancing economic productivity with broader societal and environmental considerations. By demonstrating how ethical dimensions can be systematically integrated into financial decision-making through a rigorous, quantifiable approach, the *Wasatiyah* optimization model offers a potentially transformative tool for reimagining economic systems beyond its Islamic intellectual heritage. The universality of its core insight - that wealth should be viewed as a dynamic, balanced instrument of collective progress rather than a mechanism for individual accumulation - provides a powerful bridge between diverse economic philosophies and approaches to sustainable development.

This call for rethinking wealth management from maximization to optimization resonates intellectually and practically - *Wasatiyah* and an important segment of current state of global consciousness. By addressing the moral and societal dimensions of economic activity, *Wasatiyah* represents a timely and necessary evolution of wealth management that could bridge Adam Smith's moral sentiments with today's sustainability and equity challenges. It redefines wealth as a tool for balanced progress, rather than an unbounded pursuit of accumulation - a shift that is both intellectually sound and practically urgent.

7. GENERALIZATION - NORMALIZED BALANCED COORDINATE (NBCs)

As a generalization of the above discussion, the Normalized Balanced Coordinates (NBCs) framework emerges as a versatile analytical tool that transcends its original Islamic wealth management context, offering a powerful methodology for diagnosing and through STOs transforming complex systemic challenges across diverse domains. By reducing multifaceted and noisy problems to two pivotal dimensions - typically representing ethical/environmental considerations and efficiency/developmental metrics - the NBCs approach provides a systematic, dynamic and quantifiable method for understanding and optimizing performance in various fields.

At its core, the NBCs framework employs a two-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system normalized between -1 and +1, allowing for consistent and comparative analysis across different contexts. This mathematical structure enables practitioners to plot the current state of a system, organization, or initiative along two critical axes, with positive coordinates indicating alignment with desired principles and negative coordinates highlighting areas requiring improvement. The generalized approach makes it applicable to domains as varied as sustainable and responsible investments (SRIs), environmental, social, and governance (ESG) metrics, sustainable development goals (SDGs), public health policy, individual, household and firms' behaviours, and organizational strategy.

The framework's transformative power lies in its three-pronged intervention strategy: Substitutions, Transformations, and Offsets (STOs). Substitutions involve replacing underperforming or problematic elements with more aligned alternatives. Transformations represent fundamental structural changes to address systemic issues. Offsets provide compensatory mechanisms to mitigate existing imbalances. This approach allows for a nuanced, contextually sensitive method of moving towards a more balanced and optimal state, regardless of the specific domain of application.

What distinguishes the NBCs framework is its ability to simplify complex and often noisy multidimensional challenges into a clear, actionable diagnostic tool. By focusing on two critical dimensions, it provides decision-makers with an intuitive yet rigorous method to assess current performance, identify improvement areas, and develop targeted strategies for positive change. The normalized coordinate system ensures that different contexts can be analyzed using a consistent methodology, facilitating cross-domain comparisons and knowledge transfer.

The potential applications of the NBCs framework are vast and largely unexplored. From public health initiatives balancing equity and efficiency to corporate strategies aligning social responsibility

with financial performance, this approach offers a powerful lens for understanding and optimizing complex systems. Future research could focus on developing domain-specific implementations, creating a generalized methodology that can be customized across various fields, potentially establishing NBCs as a fundamental analytical approach for addressing multidimensional challenges in an increasingly complex global landscape.

8. CONCLUSIONS

The NWCs framework reimagines wealth management by bridging the divide between ethical imperatives and financial objectives. Its potential extends beyond Islamic finance, offering a universal model for achieving balance in an era of growing socio-economic and environmental challenges. By aligning profitability with sustainability and ethics, the framework positions global financial institutions to lead in fostering an inclusive, regenerative economy. The mathematical and conceptual models presented demonstrate how Islamic economic principles can be systematically applied to create regenerative wealth strategies that balance material prosperity with moral integrity.

At its core, the NWCs or more generally NBCs approach embodies the principle of *Wasatiyah* - moderation and balance - by providing a structured method to assess and improve wealth management practices or any other state, action or policy. The four-quadrant model allows practitioners to diagnose ethical and financial performance, identifying specific strategies for transformation across different scenarios. Whether an investment portfolio is ethically sound but financially weak, or profitable but morally compromised, the framework offers tailored interventions through Substitutions, Transformations, and Offsets that guide stakeholders toward a more balanced and sustainable approach to wealth creation and distribution.

The significance of this framework extends beyond theoretical constructs, offering a practical blueprint for reimagining economic activity as a means of social upliftment and spiritual growth. By emphasizing stewardship, universal balance, and the interconnectedness of economic, social, and environmental systems, the *Wasatiyah* approach challenges prevailing narratives of wealth accumulation. It presents a compelling alternative that aligns financial pursuits with higher moral objectives, ultimately contributing to a more just, sustainable, and ethically grounded global economic ecosystem that respects both individual prosperity and collective well-being.

8.1. Direction of Future Research

The prevailing paradigm of wealth management has long prioritized maximization - of profits, returns, and accumulation. However, this approach has proven inadequate in addressing systemic challenges such as rising inequality, environmental degradation, and the erosion of societal trust. It is increasingly clear that wealth, as a concept, must be reimagined as a tool for balanced and regenerative progress.

Adam Smith, often regarded as the father of free-market economics, envisioned markets driven by moral sentiments - sympathy, fairness, and justice. However, modern economic systems have sidelined these ethical underpinnings in favor of the self-interested "*homo economicus*." This shift has resulted in markets that maximize individual gains at the expense of collective well-being, leading to unsustainable practices and deep social inequities.

Regenerative economics offers a timely alternative, emphasizing sustainability and the integration of economic activity within ecological and social boundaries. Frameworks like the Circular-ESG model and more its general form like Normalized Balance Coordinates (NBCs) advocate for closing negative externalities and achieving net-positive impacts through circular, inclusive, and regenerative strategies. Such approaches align closely with the principle of *Wasatiyah* in Islamic economics, which advocates for balance and moderation.

Future research should explore the practical application and refinement of the Normalized Balance Coordinates (NBCs) framework across diverse domains. A key focus should be developing robust methodologies for defining and quantifying the relevant dimensions for specific trade-offs, such as economic growth vs. ecological sustainability, efficiency vs. equity, quality vs. quantity, and full employment vs. price stability. This includes investigating appropriate normalization techniques and exploring visualization methods that effectively communicate the complex interplay between competing priorities. Furthermore, research should delve into the development of tailored transition strategies, like the STOs (Substitutions, Transformations, and Offsets) introduced in the context of IWM, for each specific application of the NBCs. This involves identifying effective interventions and policy recommendations that facilitate movement towards the desired balanced state, considering the dynamic and interconnected nature of the systems involved. Crucially, research should examine the behavioral aspects of decision-making within the NBCs framework, exploring how individuals and organizations can be incentivized to adopt a more holistic and balanced approach that moves beyond single-dimension maximization.

Beyond the initial examples, future research could explore the application of NBCs to a wider range of tensions and trade-offs. These could include balancing individual liberties vs. societal security, technological innovation vs. ethical considerations, short-term gains vs. long-term sustainability, cultural preservation vs. modernization, and resource consumption vs. environmental protection. The NBCs framework offers a powerful tool for analyzing and addressing these complex challenges by providing a unified platform for measuring and optimizing across multiple, often conflicting, dimensions. By shifting the focus from maximizing a single variable to achieving a desired balance among competing priorities, the NBCs approach has the potential to foster more sustainable, equitable, and resilient systems. Future work should also investigate how the NBCs can be integrated with existing decision-making tools and frameworks, such as cost-benefit analysis and multi-criteria decision analysis, to enhance their effectiveness and broaden their applicability.

Optimizing wealth management shifts the focus from unbounded accumulation to achieving harmony between material prosperity and ethical integrity. This approach aligns with contemporary calls for stakeholder capitalism, ESG integration, and regenerative systems. The Normalized *Wasatiyah* Coordinates (NWCs) framework provides a robust tool for operationalizing this shift, ensuring that wealth is not merely accumulated but used to foster justice, sustainability, and spiritual well-being. The framework opens doors for curriculum and pedagogy change, and future-fit empirical research and knowledge development.

To rigorously validate the Normalized *Wasatiyah* Coordinates (NWCs) framework, a multi-stage mixed-methods research approach is recommended. Initial quantitative research could involve a comprehensive longitudinal study across Islamic financial institutions, tracking wealth portfolios using the NWCs diagnostic tool. This would require developing standardized measurement protocols for ethics (*Akhirah*) and profitability (*Dunya*) dimensions, potentially employing a comprehensive scoring rubric that captures both quantitative financial metrics and qualitative ethical assessments. Parallel qualitative research through structured interviews with Islamic finance practitioners, Shari'ah scholars, and wealth management experts would provide insights into the framework's practical applicability and potential refinements. A comparative case study methodology could be particularly illuminating, examining portfolios before and after implementing NWCs-guided transformations to assess changes in financial performance, ethical alignment, and overall portfolio resilience. Furthermore, interdisciplinary collaborative research involving economists, Islamic finance scholars, ethicists, and data scientists could help develop more robust models for NWCs optimization and validation.

Declarations

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

The model has been developed by the author. During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT 4o to improve language readability. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

REFERENCES

- Al-Mubarak, T. and Goud, B. (2018), "Environmental impact in Islamic finance", The Responsible Investment Foundation.
- Arbib, J. and Seba, T. (2020) "Rethinking Humanity, Five Foundational Sector Disruptions, the Lifecycle of Civilizations, and the Coming Age of Freedom" <https://www.rethinkx.com/humanity-download>
- Asutay, M., and Harningtyas, A.F. (2015). Developing Maqasid al-Shari'ah Index to Evaluate Social Performance of Islamic Banks: A Conceptual and Empirical Attempt. *International Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance Studies*, 1, 5-64.
- Azid, T., Mukhlisin, M. and Altwijry, O. (Eds.). (2022). *Wealth Management and Investment in Islamic Settings: Opportunities and Challenges*. Springer.
- Biplob, H. and Abdullah, M.F. (2021). The Concept of Wasatiyah in Consumption: An Analysis from Islamic Financial Jurisprudence. *ICR Journal* 12(1):11-26. <https://doi.org/10.52282/icr.v12i1.810>.
- Chapra, M. U. (2007). *The Islamic Visions of Development based on Maqasid Al-Shari'ah*. Jeddah, IRTI
- Cohen-Shacham, E., Walters, G, Janzen, C. and Maginnis, S. (2016). *Nature-based Solutions to address global societal challenges*. IUCN. <https://portals.iucn.org/library/sites/library/files/documents/2016-036.pdf>.
- Costanza, R., Cumberland, J., Daly, H., Goodland, R. and Norgaardl, R. (1997). *An introduction to ecological economics*. Florida, USA: CRC Press.
- Divest-Invest (2021) "A Decade of Progress Towards A Just Climate Future" https://www.divestinvest.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Divest-Invest-Program-FINAL10-26_B.pdf
- Dusuki, A. W. and Bouheraoua, S. (2011). The Framework of Maqasid Al-Shari'ah and Its Implication for Islamic Finance. *ICR Journal* 2(2), 316-36. <https://doi.org/10.52282/icr.v2i2.651>.
- Elkington, J. (2020). *Green Swans: The Coming Boom in Regenerative Capitalism*. Fast Company Press.
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2013). Towards the circular economy. Retrieved from <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/towards-the-circular-economy-vol-1-an-economic-and-business-rationale-for-an> (<https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/towards-the-circular-economy-vol-1-an-economic-and-business-rationale-for-an>)
- European Union. (2024). EU Green Deal. Retrieved from https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en
- GFN - Global Footprint Network (2024), "Country Overshoot Days 2024" https://overshoot.footprint-network.org/newsroom/country-overshoot-days/?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Haneef, M. A., and Imon, R. A. (2024). Al-iqtisad al-wasati: A finance vision for the ummah. In S. N. Ali and Z. H. Jumat (Eds.), *Islamic finance in the digital age* (pp. 9-35). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781035322954.00011>
- Hawken, P. (2021). *Regeneration: Ending the Climate Crisis in One Generation*". Penguin Random House.

- Hawken, P. (2017). *Drawdown - the Most Comprehensive Plan Ever Proposed to Global Warming*. Penguin Books New York
- IPCC - Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. (2023). "Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/sixth-assessment-report-cycle/>.
- Kamali, M. H. (2015). *The middle path of moderation in Islam: The Qur'anic principle of Wasatiyah*. Oxford University Press.
- Khan, T. (2024a) "Modelling Humane Economy: Revisiting Islamic Economics in Memory of Muhammad Nejatullah Siddiqi", International conference on Contributions of Prof. M. Nejatullah Siddiqi in Islamic Economics organized by the Institute of Objective Studies, New Delhi, April 27-28, 2024
- Khan, T. (2024). Circular-ESG model for regenerative transition. *Sustainability*, 16(17), 7549. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16177549>
- NZAMI (Net Zero Asset Managers Initiative. (2024). "The Net Zero Asset Managers Commitment" <https://www.netzeroassetmanagers.org/media/2021/12/NZAM-Commitment.pdf>
- Rawls, J. (1971). *A Theory of Justice*. Harvard University Press.
- Raworth, K. (2017). "Doughnut Economics: Seven Ways to Think Like a 21st-Century Economist". London: Random House Business, 2017.
- Sen, A. (1999). *Development as Freedom*. Oxford University Press.
- Siddiqi, M.N. (2013) "A Vision for the Future of Islamic Economics", Keynote Speech delivered at the 9th International Conference in Islamic Economics, Istanbul, Turkey 9 September 2013. <http://www.siddiqi.com/mns/AVisionForTheFutureOfIslamicEconomics.htm>
- Siddiqi, M.N. (1981). *Muslim Economic Thinking*. The Islamic Foundation, Leicester, U.K.
- SRC-Stockholm Resilience Center. (2023). "Planetary Boundaries." <https://www.stockholmresilience.org/research/planetary-boundaries.html>.
- Stahel, W. R. (2019). *The Circular Economy: A User's Guide*. 1st ed. London: Routledge.
- UNDP. (2024). "Human Development Report 2023-24." <https://hdr.undp.org/content/human-development-report-2023-24>.

Total Factor Productivity and Foreign Human Capital: Evidence from the Western Balkans

Daria Hukic^{1*} & Faruk Hadzic¹

¹Sarajevo School of Science and Technology, Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

*Email: daria.hukic@stu.ssst.edu.ba

ABSTRACT

The Western Balkan Six economies have advanced structural reforms to boost economic growth, create new jobs, and bring living standards closer to those in Europe. However, the Western Balkan residents continue to be encouraged to look for career and educational possibilities outside of the region due to the slow rate of convergence and the significant development gap with other European nations. Over the past ten years, the Western Balkan emigration rate has increased by 10%, and as a result, about one-fifth of the population now lives outside of the region. The high levels of emigration that continue can be extremely challenging for development. They may cause skill shortages and labor market distortions, which may discourage potential investors from making investments because they are unable to find the necessary skills. Gaining competitiveness, attracting investment, and navigating the area's ecological and digital transition all depend on human capital and a competent workforce that can meet the labor market's skill requirements and spur innovation. They are also important pillars of an economy's resilience and prosperity, which is important in light of the COVID-19 pandemic and the changing nature of the global environment. The goal of this paper is to examine how immigrants contribute to innovation in Western Balkans. Using Total Factor Productivity as a measure of innovation. The focus is on the Western Balkan countries (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia). The relationship between migration and innovation is examined not only at regional, but also at sectoral level. This makes it possible to quantify the direct impact of immigrants in the industry where they are really employed. To address the potential endogeneity of migration we adopt instrumental variable technique originally devised by Card (2001). Moreover, we carried out the analysis of human capital composition across sectors in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The offered recommendations can be used by policy makers when designing future policies.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received: December 9, 2024

Accepted: June 1, 2025

Published: June 30, 2025

KEYWORDS

migration; innovation; highly skilled migrants; low skilled migrants; total factor productivity; Western Balkans

JEL CODES

D2; J24; O15; O31;

HOW TO CITE

Hukic, D., & Hadzic, F. (2025). Total Factor Productivity and Foreign Human Capital: Evidence from the Western Balkans. *Journal of Economics, Law and Society*, 2(1), 29-49. <https://doi.org/10.70009/jels.2025.2.1.2>

1. INTRODUCTION

In the exploration of migration's relationship with innovation and productivity, the prevailing geographical approach has traditionally dominated scholarly discourse. Grounded in seminal works such as that of Dolado, Goria, and Ichino (1994), this approach typically analyzes the impact of migration on innovation and productivity at the regional or national level, often overlooking the nuances embedded within specific economic sectors. However, this introduction posits that a comprehensive understanding of this relationship necessitates a shift towards a sectoral analysis, an avenue that has been relatively underexplored in the extant literature.

As demonstrated in prior research, the geographic approach tends to explore the innovation performances of entire regions or countries, neglecting the heterogeneity within economic sectors

that play a pivotal role in shaping productivity growth. Technological regimes, as elucidated by Breschi et al. (2000), underscore the importance of sector-specific technologies in influencing rates of productivity growth. Consequently, a nation or region's overall productivity growth becomes a combination of disparate rates within various sectors—rates that may or may not be influenced by immigrant workers. The oversight of this sectoral dimension in previous analyses prompts the adoption of a more nuanced approach, exploring the impact of migration at the sectoral level.

Beyond geographical considerations, this introduction integrates insights from the methodology, incorporating two sets of data to assess the effect of migration on sectoral innovation. The first set emanates from a survey conducted in Bosnia and Herzegovina, focusing on top management, HR, or talent managers within the Construction, IT, and Services sectors. Employing both random and purposive sampling strategies, this survey not only delves into the labor force composition but also serves as a foundational dataset for our sectoral analysis. The second set draws from reputable international organizations, ensuring data compatibility and dependability.

Furthermore, the discussion extends to the direct effects of migrants on innovation and productivity, revealing potential overestimations in studies that adopt a geographical approach. High rates of productivity growth within innovative sectors may attract foreign labor, but the dispersion of immigrant contributions across sectors, including those with limited innovation, necessitates a sectoral lens for accurate assessment. Additionally, the influence of migrants' education levels is examined, emphasizing the importance of considering contributions from both highly skilled and less-educated immigrants across diverse economic activities.

As we embark on this inquiry, our methodological rigor stands out. Rigorous survey design, incorporating power analysis and dual sampling techniques, is coupled with data from esteemed international sources. The validity and reliability of our survey instrument are buttressed by a comprehensive literature review, managerial input, and a pilot test. Employing statistical analyses, including descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analysis, our study seeks to unravel the intricate dynamics between migration, sectoral innovation, and productivity. This multi-faceted approach positions our research to contribute nuanced insights, addressing the gaps and limitations inherent in the existing literature.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on migration's impact on productivity and innovation spans both macro-level and micro-level analyses. Early work by Dolado, Goría, and Ichino (1994) introduced migrant labor into aggregate production functions, finding effects of both high- and low-skilled foreign workers on GDP per capita. Since then, numerous country- and region-level studies have examined immigration's influence on various innovation proxies – from patent counts to productivity growth – and many report positive impacts. For example, Ortega and Peri (2014) find that immigration raises total factor productivity (TFP) at the national level. Similarly, Alesina, Harnoss, and Rapoport (2013) document that a higher share of immigrants (especially diverse, highly skilled ones) correlates with greater GDP per capita and TFP across countries. In Europe, Bosetti, Cattaneo, and Verdolini (2015) show that inflows of skilled migrants correspond to more patent applications, and Kerr and Lincoln (2010) find that increases in visas for high-skilled foreigners led to higher patenting in U.S. cities. These macro-level studies suggest that immigration – particularly of highly educated workers – can be a catalyst for innovation and productivity growth in host economies (Dohse and Gold, 2014). A few exceptions exist, however: Bratti and Conti (2014) detect no effect of highly skilled immigrant shares (and even a negative effect of low-skilled shares) on patenting in Italian provinces, indicating that positive immigration-innovation links are not universal. On balance, the broad evidence at the national or regional scale leans positive, with immigration often credited for contributing to technical

progress and growth. Notably, this appears to hold for both high- and lower-skilled migrants in advanced economies, as even less-educated immigrants have been found to raise productivity in some contexts. Such findings underscore the potential economy-wide benefits of foreign human capital, while also hinting at complexities beneath the aggregate level.

In contrast to the generally favorable macro evidence, firm-level and other micro-level studies paint a more nuanced picture. When examining individual companies or plants, results have been mixed and sometimes contradictory. Several studies have failed to find a strong direct effect of employing immigrants on firm innovation outcomes. For instance, analyses of German and Danish firms detected no significant benefits of migrant worker presence or workforce cultural diversity on the likelihood of introducing innovations. Trax, Brunow, and Suedekum (2015) report no productivity gains from a higher share of migrants or more diverse origins at the plant level in Germany, and Østergaard et al. (2011) similarly find no specific advantage of employee ethnic diversity for innovation in Danish firms. Using Dutch firm data, Ozgen, Nijkamp, and Poot (2013) even found a negative relationship between the share of immigrant employees and firm innovativeness (though interestingly a positive relationship for the diversity of national backgrounds). Their later work confirmed that outcomes are sensitive to context: the effect of diversity on innovation varied markedly between Germany and the Netherlands and under different model specifications. On the other hand, there is evidence that under certain conditions migrant diversity can aid firms' creativity – for example, McGuirk and Jordan (2012) showed that Irish regions with more culturally diverse labor pools had a higher probability of firms introducing new products. It is worth noting that in that study diversity was measured at the regional level, not within each firm suggesting spillover effects from a diverse local talent pool. Overall, compared to the macro-level consensus, micro-level research indicates that immigration's impact on innovation is not automatic and can depend on firm-specific or local circumstances. Indeed, a recent multi-country firm study found only selective positive effects: high-skilled non-EU immigrants were on average not associated with higher productivity growth, likely due to skill mismatch (many working in lower-productivity jobs), although some industries did benefit from more such migrants. These mixed findings highlight that the migration–innovation link is complex and may be mediated by how effectively firms and industries utilize foreign talent.

One explanation for the discrepancy between aggregate and firm-level results lies in sectoral heterogeneity. The prevailing approach in the literature has been geographic – analyzing migration effects at the country or regional level. While useful for capturing broad trends, this approach can obscure important differences across economic sectors. Immigrants are not evenly distributed across industries, and industries themselves differ in their innovation patterns. The technological regimes literature emphasizes that each sector follows a distinct innovation trajectory; the rate and nature of productivity growth vary greatly between, say, a high-tech manufacturing industry and a low-tech service field. Broad regional growth often results from a few dynamic sectors, which may or may not employ many immigrants. If a region's booming high-tech firms drive productivity gains and also attract foreign workers, a regional analysis might wrongly attribute the growth to those immigrants as a whole – even if many of them actually work in unrelated, less innovative local industries. In other words, geographic studies risk overestimating migrants' contributions by failing to account for which sectors are generating innovation. A sector-focused approach can isolate the direct impact of migrants within the industries they are employed, thereby offering a clearer picture of causality. Indeed, a key question emerging from prior work is whether the positive effects of immigration on innovation still hold when examined at the industry level rather than in aggregate. Recent evidence suggests that sectoral analysis is fruitful: productivity studies in the Balkans confirm that aggregate TFP trends mask substantial inter-industry variation, reinforcing the importance of disaggregating by sector. By examining sector-specific outcomes, researchers can better determine in which areas of the economy migrant human capital has the greatest impact (Breschi et al., 2000).

Sectoral analysis also allows consideration of different types of innovation and the roles of high- vs. low-skilled migrants. Much of the literature, especially at the macro level, implicitly assumes that highly educated immigrants are the primary drivers of innovation, focusing on outcomes like patents or R&D that heavily rely on advanced skills. Indeed, in science- and technology-intensive sectors, innovation often requires formal research activities and specialized knowledge that high-skilled workers provide. However, innovation is a multifaceted phenomenon that extends beyond just R&D labs. In many medium-tech and low-tech industries, firms innovate through incremental improvements, adoption of existing technologies, or process innovations – for example, acquiring new machinery or refining production techniques. These productivity-enhancing changes might not generate patents, but they do raise efficiency and are captured by TFP growth. Crucially, such improvements do not always require workers with advanced degrees; practical know-how and on-the-job experience can be more important in implementing new processes or equipment. Santamaría et al. (2009) show that firms in low- and mid-tech sectors often innovate “beyond formal R&D” by leveraging employee skills and adaptations on the factory floor. Von Hippel’s classic study (1976) similarly highlighted the role of end-users and production workers in driving innovative improvements from the bottom up. This suggests that immigrants with modest formal education can still contribute meaningfully to innovation in certain settings – for instance, a skilled tradesperson from abroad might introduce new techniques in a construction firm, or migrant service workers might bring ideas that improve customer service processes. Ignoring these contributions by focusing only on highly educated migrants would present an incomplete picture. Moreover, in many countries (including those in the Western Balkans), immigrants tend to be overrepresented in lower-skill jobs. By considering diverse skill levels, sectoral studies can capture the full range of productivity impacts – from top-end scientific innovation to ground-level efficiency gains. In sum, Total Factor Productivity is a particularly useful measure in this context because it reflects broad productivity-enhancing activities, not just formal innovations. TFP growth is often described as “technical progress in its broadest sense” (Solow, 1957), encompassing any improvements in output not explained by labor and capital inputs. This makes it an appropriate metric for sectoral innovation studies, as it will register gains from both R&D-driven breakthroughs and incremental operational improvements. By using TFP as our innovation proxy, we align with a growing literature that treats productivity gains as a comprehensive indicator of innovation performance, suitable for comparing high-tech and low-tech sectors alike.

Another dimension of heterogeneity is the cultural diversity of migrant populations. Beyond the sheer number of immigrants, researchers have asked whether a more diverse pool of national origins stimulates innovation by bringing together varied perspectives. At the aggregate level, several studies answer in the affirmative: greater diversity among immigrants is linked to higher regional productivity and innovation outcomes. For example, Alesina et al. (2013) find that countries with more diverse immigrant communities exhibit higher TFP, especially when that diversity is among skilled workers. Similarly, using European regional data, Özgen, Nijkamp, and Poot (2012) show that regions hosting a mix of nationalities have higher patenting rates. These findings echo management studies on multicultural teams, which often credit diversity with enhancing creative problem-solving (Stahl et al., 2010). The policy implication sometimes drawn is that attracting immigrants from a variety of backgrounds (for instance, via diversity-oriented visa policies) could boost innovation. However, as with total immigrant numbers, a sectoral perspective reveals a more complex reality. One issue is that regional immigrant diversity may proxy for economic diversity. In Europe and elsewhere, immigration tends to occur in waves dominated by certain nationalities, often responding to historical ties or geopolitical events. These waves also tend to fill labor needs in specific industries. For instance, post-war Germany saw successive waves of Italian, then Turkish, then Eastern European migrants, each group concentrating in particular sectors that were expanding at the time. Over time, a country or region with a wide range of industries will naturally host immigrants from many different origins, because each sector draws workers from specific source

countries. In the Western Balkans today, for example, construction, tourism, and agriculture might each attract different migrant groups, yielding diversity at the national level simply as a byproduct of having multiple sectors. It is well known that a diversified economic base itself fosters innovation by allowing knowledge spillovers between industries (Jacobs, 1969; Feldman & Audretsch, 1999). Thus, the positive effect of immigrant diversity observed in cross-region studies could partly reflect the benefits of industry diversity rather than any special creative synergy from multicultural workplaces. A sector-level analysis can disentangle this by examining diversity within industries. If diversity is truly beneficial due to idea recombination among workers of different backgrounds, we would expect to see gains even within a single sector when its workforce is international. On the other hand, if diversity's apparent benefits mostly capture broad economic variety, controlling for sector will diminish those effects. In short, the sectoral approach allows us to separate the "diversity effect" from the confounding influence of diversified regional economies. This nuance is especially relevant for the Western Balkan region, where immigrant diversity is growing in tandem with gradual economic diversification, and needs careful interpretation.

A further factor potentially affecting migration–innovation outcomes is the age structure of migrant vs. native workers. Immigrant labor forces are often younger on average than the domestic workforce. Youth can be an advantage for innovation – younger workers may have more up-to-date training and tend to be more open to new ideas, whereas older workers have experience but could be less flexible or creative. The literature on age and innovation is not entirely settled: while it's generally found that creativity and the propensity to produce radical inventions decline with age (Jones, 2010; Öberg, 1960), other work suggests that peak innovation output can occur after a period of experience accumulation (Schubert & Andersson, 2013). Regardless, if immigrants are disproportionately in their 20s and 30s, whereas the native workforce skews older, part of the innovation impact attributed to migrants might actually be an age effect. A younger workforce (immigrant or not) could simply be more productive and innovative. Failing to account for age differences could therefore confound results. Studies of migration and innovation increasingly recognize this and control for workforce age structure. For our purposes, it is an additional consideration in the Western Balkans, as these countries face aging native populations alongside inflows of younger foreign workers. Any analysis must ensure that we isolate the effect of migration itself from such demographic factors.

When we turn to the Western Balkans, we find a context with unique migration dynamics and a relative dearth of prior research on the topic. The Western Balkan economies (e.g., Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia) are characterized more by emigration than immigration. Over the past decades, a significant share of their population – often the most skilled – has left to seek opportunities abroad. As of recent years, roughly one-fifth of the region's people live outside their country of origin, leading to concerns about brain drain and skill shortages in the local labor markets. This context is quite different from that of Western European countries or the United States, where much of the immigration–innovation literature has focused. In the Western Balkans, the pool of foreign human capital (immigrants) is relatively small and has specific features. Some immigrants are regional (from neighboring countries), while others arrive as asylum seekers or temporary transit migrants (for instance, recent influxes from conflict regions in the Middle East and Ukraine). The educational profile of these arrivals has been mixed – for example, surveys in 2022 indicated that a majority of migrants passing through had only primary or secondary education, although certain refugee groups (such as Ukrainian displaced persons) were highly educated (Figure 1).

Because the Western Balkan states are not traditional migrant magnets, the scale at which foreign workers participate in their economies is modest. This means that evidence from large economies with sizeable immigrant workforces might not directly translate. It also means there has been little scholarly attention to whether and how the limited foreign human capital present in these countries contributes to innovation. Most related studies focus instead on the consequences of emigration

(e.g., loss of human capital and its impact on growth) or on aggregate productivity trends during post-socialist transition. For instance, recent growth accounting analyses have measured TFP improvements in Western Balkan countries, but without explicitly linking these to immigration. The role of incoming migrants in the region’s innovation system thus remains an open question. We lack robust evidence on whether sectors that employ more foreign workers are any more dynamic in terms of productivity. It is also unclear if the generally positive impacts of migration observed elsewhere apply in an environment with different migrant composition and possibly institutional barriers to fully utilizing foreign talent.

Figure 1: Highest level of educational attainment

Source: Migration Trends in the Western Balkans in 2022. IOM’s Displacement Tracking Matrix

The present study seeks to fill this gap in the literature by providing a focused examination of migration and innovation in the Western Balkans at the sectoral level. By using TFP growth as our measure of innovation, we capture a broad range of productivity-enhancing activities – from formal R&D outcomes to informal efficiency gains – which is well-suited to the region’s sectoral context where radical innovation (patenting) is relatively scarce but productivity improvements are vital. We explicitly analyze the relationship between the presence of immigrant workers and TFP across different industries, both to quantify any direct contributions of migrants and to see how effects differ by sector. In doing so, we build on the insights from prior research: our approach accounts for sectoral heterogeneity, distinguishes between skill levels of migrants (high-skilled vs. lower-skilled) as relevant for each sector, and considers origin diversity within sectors. This nuanced treatment allows us to test whether the positive impacts found in aggregate studies hold true in the Western Balkan setting, or whether factors like skill mismatch and small migrant shares yield more muted effects. Importantly, our study is among the first to investigate sector-specific migration–TFP linkages in the Western Balkans, an area previously under-explored. By comparing results across industries, we can identify where foreign human capital matters most – for example, whether technology-intensive sectors reap significant benefits from even a few skilled migrants, or whether services and low-tech manufacturing also see gains from migrant labor through incremental innovation. We also highlight any sectoral gaps where the absence of foreign expertise might be hindering innovation, thus offering insight into where policy interventions (such as attracting certain types of talent) could be most effective. In sum, this literature review has shown that migration can be a driver of innovation and productivity, but the effects are not uniform and depend on the context. The Western Balkans provide a distinctive case to apply these insights. Our study contributes to the literature by extending the migration–innovation analysis to a new regional context with sectoral granularity, helping to clarify whether and how foreign human capital boosts TFP in transitioning economies. This contribution not only addresses a gap in academic knowledge but also has practical implications for Western Balkan policymakers striving to enhance competitiveness through human capital and innovation.

Hypothesis development

This study focused on investigating the relationship between the number of foreign employees and the level of diversity in organizations. We hypothesize that firms with a bigger number of foreign employees have higher diversity level according to their managers.

H1. Companies with higher foreign employees' number have higher level of diversity perception.

This hypothesis suggests a positive relationship between the level of diversity and number of foreign employees.

As we established earlier the overall productivity growth of a nation or region may be the result of very heterogeneous rates of growth in various sectors. Moreover, creative activities can vary greatly among industries and usually call for a wide range of skills. So, we hypothesize that there should be dependency between industry and the type of foreign workers' employment.

H2. Industry can predict the number of foreign employees employed permanently or temporarily.

3. METHODOLOGY

To examine how foreign human capital influences broad productivity-enhancing activities—captured by Total Factor Productivity — across economic sectors in the Western Balkans, we employ a two-pronged, sectorally disaggregated approach. First, we conduct a firm-level survey in Bosnia and Herzegovina to capture micro-level workforce composition, including skill mix, age structure, and cultural diversity. Second, we assemble a panel of secondary data on TFP and migration from international sources for five Western Balkan economies and apply both descriptive and instrumental-variable regressions at the sectoral level. This mixed method design aligns with our literature review's emphasis on TFP as a broad indicator of innovation and productivity-enhancing changes (e.g., process improvements, organizational capital, technology adoption), and on the importance of sectoral heterogeneity, skill levels, age, and diversity.

We selected Bosnia and Herzegovina as a case study because its sectoral structure and recent migration trends mirror those of neighboring Western Balkan states. Focusing on the Construction, Information Technology (IT), and Services sectors—each representing low-, high-, and medium-technology segments respectively—allows us to observe how foreign human capital contributes to TFP-relevant activities across diverse innovation regimes. We targeted senior managers and HR directors (CEOs, HR managers, talent leads) in firms registered with the national business registry. A two-stage strategy ensured representativeness: (1) random sampling from the registry to secure broad coverage, and (2) purposive sampling to guarantee adequate representation of each sector and firm-size category. This yielded 53 complete responses.

The structured questionnaire, administered online over a three-month period in 2021, collected:

1. Number and share of foreign-born employees, disaggregated by contract type (permanent vs. temporary), skill level (tertiary-educated vs. secondary-or-below), and age group (under 35 vs. 36 and older).
2. Managers' perception of national-origin diversity on a 1–5 scale, supplemented by counts of distinct nationalities employed.
3. Firm characteristics: sector, total employment, presence of an R&D department, and overall R&D expenditure adequacy.

To ensure content validity, we (a) reviewed the instrument against our literature synthesis on migration–innovation links, (b) solicited feedback from five practicing managers in each sector, and (c) pilot-tested with five additional firms. Iterative revisions improved clarity and alignment with constructs such as skill mismatch, age effects, and diversity-mediated innovation. We used IBM SPSS for quantitative analysis:

1. Descriptive statistics to profile firm size, sectoral distribution, foreign employee shares, skill composition, age structure, and diversity scores.
2. Pearson correlations examining bivariate links between foreign-born share and diversity, age structure and diversity, and sector dummies with permanent employment of migrants.
3. Ordinary least squares (OLS) regressions to test: Whether the share of foreign-born employees predicts perceived workforce diversity (a proxy for cross-cultural idea recombination). Whether sector membership (dummy-coded) predicts the share of foreign-born workers in permanent roles, reflecting sectoral differences in skill retention.

In all regressions, we controlled for firm size and presence of R&D activity. We checked OLS assumptions—linearity, homoscedasticity, normality, and multicollinearity—and used a stringent significance threshold ($p < .001$) to mitigate false positives given multiple tests and sample size.

The second set of information used in this study came from international organizations, ensuring its compatibility and dependability. Nevertheless, this method has certain drawbacks in that we were unable to provide data for every country for some indicators. Thus, we used data from World Bank’s World Development Indicators, the IMF’s Outlook data base from October 2020, the International Labor Organization (ILO), the World Economic Forum, and Eurostat. Migration indicators included the share of foreign-born in the labor force, migrant skill composition (tertiary-educated share), and measures of origin diversity (fractionalization index), drawn from ILO and WDI databases.

Our methodology directly responds to the literature’s identified needs: it treats TFP as a broad measure of all productivity-enhancing activities (formal innovation, process upgrades, organizational practices) rather than restricting to patent-based metrics. By focusing on sectoral disaggregation, we avoid aggregation bias and can pinpoint where foreign human capital has significant leverage. Inclusion of skill-level, age structure, and diversity measures allows us to test theoretical channels—codified knowledge in high-tech sectors, incremental innovation in mid/low-tech industries, and cultural diversity spillovers—highlighted as underexplored in Western Balkans contexts. The use of instrumental variables ensures credible causal inference, addressing endogeneity concerns that have challenged prior research. In sum, this carefully tailored, mixed-methods design offers a rigorous, sector-sensitive framework to assess how migration shapes broad productivity outcomes in the Western Balkans, fully aligned with the gaps and recommendations identified in our literature review.

4. RESULTS

The information presented in the Table 1 indicates that from 2000 to 2017 the largest TFP growth in total economy was observed in Bosnia and Herzegovina, which is the second leading output growth in the sample, with an average output growth rate of 3.30%. Albania demonstrated the highest average output growth rate (4.23%), although average TFP growth was lower compared to Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia. This is mainly due to larger capital utilization and growth in employment. With an output growth of 3.02, Serbia also had a high average TFP growth (2.08). In Montenegro, the country with the lowest average annual GDP growth in the sample, the average TFP growth rate was negative, while growth of capital and growth in capital utilization were relatively high.

TFP growth in industry has the greatest correlation with overall TFP growth when comparing average growth rates for the economy as a whole and different sectors. By using averages for the entire period, TFP growth in industry was positive in every country. TFP growth was lower in the services sector, and even negative in three countries from the sample (Albania, North Macedonia and Montenegro).

Table 1: Decomposition of output growth, total economy and sectoral approach, (2000-2017)

		2000-2017		
		Total	Industry (incl. construction)	Services
Albania	GDP/Value Added	4.23	5.09	-1.62
	Employment	0.40	1.06	2.93
	Capital	1.68	2.00	0.77
	Utilization	0.85	0.85	0.85
	TFP	1.31	1.18	-6.17
Bosnia and Herzegovina	GDP/Value Added	3.30	4.74	3.35
	Employment	-0.15	0.58	0.29
	Capital	1.17	1.57	1.30
	Utilization	-0.04	-0.04	-0.04
	TFP	2.32	2.64	1.81
North Macedonia	GDP/Value Added	2.68	4.28	2.74
	Employment	1.09	0.63	1.97
	Capital	1.17	1.33	1.45
	Utilization	0.65	0.65	0.65
	TFP	-0.24	1.66	-1.33
Montenegro	GDP/Value Added	2.96	8.49	-0.30
	Employment	0.90	-0.02	1.44
	Capital	1.66	2.12	1.02
	Utilization	1.20	1.20	1.20
	TFP	-0.79	5.19	-3.96
Serbia	GDP/Value Added	3.02	1.70	2.84
	Employment	-0.29	-0.80	0.91
	Capital	1.76	1.30	2.04
	Utilization	-0.53	-0.53	-0.53
	TFP	2.08	1.73	0.43

Source: Total Factor Productivity Growth In upper middle-income Balkan countries. From 2000-2017, Total Economy And sectoral approach: The growth accounting method. Maja Bacovic.

In all of the sample countries, capital contributed very similarly to growth, averaging between 1% and 2% annually for the total economy, but above 2% in most countries in industry, and in Serbia in services. In Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia, employment had a much smaller and even negative contribution when compared to capital. Growth in employment contributes most to the growth of services on a sectoral level. Most nations saw a positive contribution from capital utilization, with Montenegro seeing the biggest increase.

The Western Balkans' potential growth is expected to strengthen from 2.2 percent between 2013 and 2021 to an average of 3.2 percent between 2022 and 2030. This is primarily due to the anticipated rise in investment contributions, particularly the beneficial impact of EU investment funds, and associated structural reforms that would increase capital and TFP growth over the remaining years

of the decade. As the population ages and the labor force shrinks, it is expected that labor's contribution will become an obstacle to potential growth. However, considering the overlapping negative shocks from the COVID-19 and the Russian Federation's invasion of Ukraine over the past few years, potential growth estimates are still highly uncertain.

Figure 2: Contributions to potential growth in Western Balkans

Source: Penn World Tables; UN Population Prospects; World Bank; World Bank, WDI. Period averages of annual GDP-weighted averages. Estimates based on production function approach. Sample includes 4 Western Balkans economies (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, and Serbia).

It will be crucial for the economies of the Western Balkans to advance structural reforms and accelerate economic transformation given the strong headwinds to long-term growth prospects. For the rest of the decade, significant investments from the EU could serve as a starting point for structural reforms in the Western Balkans. By boosting confidence, fostering a more favorable business climate, and increasing government effectiveness—all of which serve to strengthen the effectiveness of public investment and draw in private investment—improving institutional quality could result in significant increases in potential growth. Significant funding for the digital and green transition in the Western Balkans is also part of the EU's investments for the rest of the decade. Increasing R&D spending could support the digital and green agendas and accelerate technological development and TFP. In 2020, R&D spending varied across the Western Balkans, ranging from 0.2 to 0.9 percent of GDP, compared to 2.3 percent of GDP in the EU.

Three sectors were analyzed in terms of human capital composition in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Construction and Services are relatively homogeneous in their age composition, the percentage of young workers (younger than 35) is around 33-36%, while the percentage of young workers in IT sector is 93%.

Not surprisingly the highest share of tertiary-educated individuals is in high-tech, which is usually characterized by its position on the margin of technological frontiers and, hence demands a

highly-qualified labor force. The lowest is observed in construction where there is a higher intensity of manual work, which often needs no special qualifications.

Figure 3: Employee age

Source: Authors' own.

There are 68% of younger employees in total across all sectors, younger age also prevails among migrants.

Figure 4: Tertiary-educated among all employees and among foreign employees

Source: Authors' own.

Figure 5: Foreign employees employed

Source: Authors' own.

Figure 5 shows that the number of companies that employ foreigners is quite high in IT sector and is even equal to the number of companies that hire only locals in Services. High percentage of migrants in high-tech are tertiary-educated, that is well above other sectors considered. Migrants are least educated in construction. IT sector has the youngest and most educated employees; whereas construction and services have older and less educated foreign labor force. Summing up, there is heterogeneity across sectors both in the terms of labor force composition and innovation dynamics. The majority of respondents believe that diversity of the staff unlocks innovation. Especially in the IT sector, 80% of managers would prefer a diverse team (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Diversity of the staff unlocks innovation

Source: Authors' own.

Among the determinants of (industry-level) total factor productivity (growth) that are mentioned in the literature are R&D efforts. Firms invest in R&D activities in the hope that these activities will result in product, process or organizational innovation, an increase in productivity, improved quality or reduced production costs of existing goods or more variety in final goods or intermediate inputs. These activities will in turn enable their survival on the competitive market and/or

increase their profitability. According to our research companies in each sector are divided almost in half into those who have R&D department and those who do not (Figure 7). The majority of IT and Services sectors' managers believe that total R&D expenditure is not sufficient (Figure 8).

Figure 7: Existence of R&D department in organization

Source: Authors' own.

Figure 8: Total R&D expenditure (if there is R&D department in organization)

Source: Authors' own.

A Pearson product-moment correlation was conducted to examine the relationships between Foreign Employee number and employee composition. Foreign employee number was strongly positively correlated to employee composition (Table 2).

A linear regression was conducted to examine how well the number of foreign employees in the company could predict level of diversity. A scatterplot showed that the relationship between foreign employees' number and level of diversity was positive and linear and did not reveal any bivariate outliers. An analysis of standard residuals showed that the data contained no outliers (Std. Residual Min. = -2.10, Std. Residual Max. = 1.79). Independence of residual errors was confirmed with

a Durbin-Watson test ($d=1.73$). Residual plots showed homoscedasticity and normality of the residuals (Table 3).

Table 2: Correlation matrix

Pearson's Correlations

		n	Pearson's r	p
ForeignEmployeeNumber	- EmployeeComposition	53	0.818***	< .001

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 3: Linear Regression

Residuals Statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	N
Predicted Value	0.034	1.503	0.302	0.379	53
Residual	-0.524	0.476	4.844×10^{-18}	0.267	53
Std. Predicted Value	-0.707	3.170	1.256×10^{-17}	1.000	53
Std. Residual	-2.103	1.790	-0.004	1.011	53

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
H ₁	Regression	7.466	1	7.466	102.786	< .001
	Residual	3.704	51	0.073		
	Total	11.170	52			

Note. The intercept model is omitted, as no meaningful information can be shown.

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized	Standard Error	Standardized	t	p	95% CI	
							Lower	Upper
H ₀	(Intercept)	0.302	0.064		4.742	< .001	0.174	0.430
H ₁	(Intercept)	0.034	0.045		0.746	0.459	-0.057	0.125
	ForeignEmployeeNumber	0.490	0.048	0.818	10.138	< .001	0.393	0.587

Source: Authors' own.

The number of foreign employees significantly predicted the level of diversity, $F = 102.79$, $p < .001$, accounting for 66.8% of the variability in the level of diversity with adjusted $R^2 = .67\%$. This is a strong predictive relationship (Cohen, 1988). The correlation between the number of foreign employees and level of diversity was statistically significant, $r = .81$, $p < .001$. The regression equation for predicting the level of diversity from the number of foreign employees was $\hat{y} = 0.034 - 0.490x$ (number of foreign employees). The confidence interval for the slope to predict the level of diversity from the number of foreign employees was 95% CI [0.393, 0.587], for each one unit of increase of foreign employees' number, level of diversity increases by about 0.4 to 0.6 points.

A linear regression was also conducted to examine how well the industry could predict the percentage of foreign workers that are employed permanently. A scatterplot showed that the relationship between industry and permanently employed foreign workers was negative and linear and did not reveal any bivariate outliers. An analysis of standard residuals showed that the data contained no outliers (Std. Residual Min. = -1.40, Std. Residual Max. = 2.26). Independence of residual errors was confirmed with a Durbin-Watson test ($d = 2.199$). Residual plots showed homoscedasticity and normality of the residuals (Table 4).

Table 4: Linear Regression

Model Summary – ForeignPermanently

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	RMSE	Durbin-Watson		
					Autocorrelation	Statistic	p
H ₀	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.814	0.069	1.511	0.248
H ₁	0.711	0.505	0.479	0.587	-0.189	2.199	0.597

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
H ₁	Regression	6.688	1	6.688	19.401	< .001
	Residual	6.550	19	0.345		
	Total	13.238	20			

Note. The intercept model is omitted, as no meaningful information can be shown.

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized	Standard Error	Standardized	t	p	95% CI	
							Lower	Upper
H ₀	(Intercept)	2.524	0.178		14.216	< .001	2.153	2.894
H ₁	(Intercept)	4.417	0.448		9.849	< .001	3.478	5.355
	Industry	-0.883	0.201	-0.711	-4.405	< .001	-1.303	-0.464

Residuals Statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	N
Predicted Value	1.767	3.533	2.524	0.578	21
Residual	-0.767	1.233	-9.252×10 ⁻¹⁸	0.572	21
Std. Predicted Value	-1.309	1.746	-9.513×10 ⁻¹⁷	1.000	21
Std. Residual	-1.403	2.256	-0.018	1.040	21

Source: Authors' own.

Table 5: Correlation matrix

Pearson's Correlations

		Pearson's r	p
Industry	- ForeignPermanently	-0.711***	< .001

* p < .05, ** p < .01, *** p < .001

Source: Authors' own.

Industry statistically significantly predicted the number of foreign employees employed permanently, $F(1,19) = 19.401$, $p < .001$, accounting for 50.5% of the variability in permanently employed foreign workers with adjusted $R^2 = .51$. This is a strong predictive relationship. The correlation between industry and permanently employed foreign workers was statistically significant, $r = -0.71$, $p < .001$. The regression equation for predicting the percentage of foreign workers that are employed permanently from the industry was $\hat{y} = 4.417 - 0.883x$ (industry). The confidence interval for the slope to predict the level of diversity from the number of foreign employees was 95% CI [-0.464, -1.303], thus Construction industry has the biggest number of permanently employed stuff, and the smallest percentage of workers employed permanently is in Services (Table 5).

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The role of innovation is becoming more and more crucial at the European level, with the growing influence of developing economies such as China and India. By allowing highly talented immigrants capable of fostering innovation and growth to enter the local labor market, the migration policy may offer a means of assisting nations in becoming more competitive. We can measure the direct impact of migrants in the sector in which they are actually employed, avoiding spurious relations due to the fact that migrants frequently move through growing and innovative regions, but they are not always employed in innovative sectors. This is in contrast to the literature that measures the impact of migration at the aggregate regional or national level. Furthermore, our sectoral aggregate method appears to be more appropriate for determining policy implications in relation to firm-level microstudies, as studies conducted at the national level inherently have a higher external validity than results based on specific samples of enterprises in a given country. Our specification assesses the influence of the proportion of migrants, their level of education, and average age, all at the sectoral level.

The analysis of economic trends and labor dynamics in the Western Balkans reveals several noteworthy patterns and implications. The examination of Total Factor Productivity (TFP) growth from 2000 to 2017 underscores the varied economic performances across countries, with Bosnia and Herzegovina exhibiting the highest TFP growth in the total economy. While Albania boasts the highest average output growth rate, its TFP growth is relatively lower due to substantial capital utilization and employment growth. Serbia, with a commendable output growth rate, also demonstrates significant TFP growth. In contrast, Montenegro experiences negative TFP growth amid relatively high capital and capital utilization growth.

The sectoral analysis emphasizes the crucial role of TFP growth in the industry, which correlates strongly with overall economic TFP growth. Notably, the services sector exhibits lower TFP growth, with three countries even experiencing negative rates. Capital consistently contributes to growth across all sample countries, while employment plays a more significant role in the services sector. The analysis underscores the importance of considering sector-specific dynamics in understanding economic growth.

Looking ahead, the Western Balkans face both challenges and opportunities for potential growth. The anticipated rise in investment contributions, particularly from EU funds, and associated structural reforms are expected to drive growth in the coming years. However, potential obstacles, such as an aging population and uncertainties arising from external shocks like the COVID-19 pandemic and geopolitical events, introduce a level of complexity to growth projections. Structural reforms and accelerated economic transformation are identified as key strategies for navigating these challenges and fostering sustained growth. EU investments, particularly in digital and green transitions, are poised to catalyze positive change. Enhancing institutional quality, fostering a conducive business climate, and increasing R&D spending are critical components that can amplify the impact of public and private investments.

The analysis of human capital composition across sectors in Bosnia and Herzegovina unveils a rich tapestry of demographic and educational diversity. Firstly, the age distribution within the Construction and Services sectors is relatively homogeneous, with approximately 33-36% of the workforce being under the age of 35. In stark contrast, the IT sector stands out as notably younger, with a striking 93% of its employees falling within the young workforce category. This demographic variance not only reflects sector-specific demands but also highlights potential differences in innovation dynamics and adaptability to technological advancements.

Educationally, the distribution of tertiary-educated individuals is most pronounced in the high-tech IT sector, aligning with the industry's demand for a highly-qualified workforce operating at the

forefront of technological innovation. Conversely, the Construction sector, characterized by manual labor and lower skill intensity, exhibits the lowest percentage of tertiary-educated individuals. This educational heterogeneity emphasizes the importance of aligning educational qualifications with sector-specific needs for optimal productivity and innovation. Examining the employment of foreigners across sectors adds another layer of complexity. The IT sector emerges as a hub for foreign employment, with a substantial number of companies employing foreigners, equaling or even surpassing the number of companies hiring only locals in the Services sector. Notably, a high percentage of migrants in the IT sector are tertiary-educated, indicative of a skilled and diverse foreign workforce contributing to the sector's dynamism.

The study also delves into the crucial link between R&D activities and industry-level total factor productivity (TFP) growth. The analysis reveals that companies in each sector are nearly evenly split between those with and without an R&D department. Strikingly, a majority of managers in the IT and Services sectors believe that the total R&D expenditure is insufficient, underscoring potential constraints on innovation in these sectors.

The correlation and regression analyses introduce an intriguing perspective on the relationship between foreign employee numbers, diversity levels, and industry types. The positive correlation between the number of foreign employees and the level of diversity signifies the importance of foreign talent in fostering workplace diversity. The robust linear regression model further substantiates this, indicating that an increase in the number of foreign employees significantly predicts a higher level of diversity. This finding aligns with the widely accepted notion that diverse teams contribute positively to innovation and productivity. Additionally, the regression analysis exploring the predictability of the percentage of foreign workers employed permanently by industry unveils significant insights. The Construction industry emerges with the largest number of permanently employed staff, contrasting with the Services sector, which has the smallest percentage of workers employed permanently. This suggests divergent employment practices across sectors and highlights potential implications for workforce stability and organizational commitment. Moreover, as it was mentioned above Services had slower TFP growth than Industry (including construction).

In summary, the detailed analysis of human capital composition, innovation dynamics, and diversity across sectors in Bosnia and Herzegovina provides a nuanced understanding of the intricate interplay between demographics, education, and industry-specific characteristics. These insights not only contribute to the academic discourse but also offer practical implications for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and organizational leaders seeking to optimize workforce composition, enhance innovation, and foster a culture of diversity in the evolving economic landscape of the region.

These results imply that a migration strategy meant to support the innovative performances should be strongly demand-driven, that is, it should take into account the specific needs of firms active in different sectors. While tertiary-educated migrants are important for specific sectors with high knowledge content, countries in which manufacturing still has an important role in the overall economy should also consider facilitating the inflow of young non tertiary educated foreign workers. Our findings also suggest that governments should support some national initiatives that make it easier for highly educated immigrants to enter their country in order to encourage innovation. However, they should also introduce a more diversified policy mix strongly connected with the actual demand of firms (and sectors), in order to facilitate the entrance of the workers most in need.

Despite its contributions, this study has important limitations. First, the firm-level survey in Bosnia and Herzegovina yielded only 53 responses, which—while sufficient to detect medium-sized effects—may not support broad generalization even within that country's industries. Second, although secondary data were assembled for five Western Balkan economies, in-depth firm-level

evidence was collected only in Bosnia and Herzegovina. This focus constrains the comparative value of our sectoral findings across the region. Future research should expand the survey sample size and replicate the sectoral analysis in additional Western Balkan countries to enhance external validity and capture cross-country variation in migration–TFP relationships.

Declarations

The author has no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The data are available upon a reasonable request from the author.

REFERENCES

- Alesina, A., Harnoss J. and H. Rapoport (2013). Birthplace Diversity and Economic Prosperity. *NBER Working Paper No. 18699*. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Bacovic, M. Total Factor Productivity Growth In upper middle-income Balkan countries. From 2000-2017, Total Economy And sectoral approach: The growth accounting method. *Argumenta Oeconomica No. 1 (46)* 2021.
- Bosetti, V., Cattaneo C. and E. Verdolini (2015). Migration of skilled workers and innovation: A European Perspective, *Journal of International Economics*, 96(2): 311–322.
- Bratti, M. and C. Conti (2014). The Effect of (Mostly Unskilled) Immigration on the Innovation of Italian Regions, *Institute for the Study of Labor (IZA) DP No. 7922*.
- Breschi, S., Malerba F. and L. Orsenigo (2000). Technological Regimes and Schumpeterian Patterns of Innovation, *The Economic Journal*, 110 (463): 388–410.
- Breschi, S., Lissoni F. and G. Tarasconi. (2014), Inventor Data for Research on Migration and Innovation: A Survey and a Pilot, *WIPO Economic Research Working Papers n.17*, World Intellectual Property Organization, Geneva.
- Card, D. (2001). Immigrant inflows, native outflows, and the local labor market impacts of higher immigration. *Journal of Labor Economics* 19: 22–64.
- Dohse, D., and R. Gold. (2014). Determining the Impact of Cultural Diversity on Regional Economies in Europe. Work Package 503, MS101 “Research report on task 503.3”, *Working Paper 58*.
- Dolado, J., Goria A. and A. Ichino (1994). Immigration, Human capital and growth in the Host Country: Evidence from a pooled Country Data. *Journal of Population Economics*, 7(2): 193–215.
- Dombi, A., Economic Growth and Development in Central and Eastern Europe after the Transformation, *Public Finance Quarterly*, 58 (4), pp. 452–468, 2013.
- Feldman, M.P. and D.B. Audretsch (1999). Innovation in cities: Science-based diversity, specialization and localized competition. *European Economic Review*, 4: 409–429.
- Foster-McGregor, N., Verspagen, B., Decomposing Total Factor Productivity Growth in Manufacturing and Services. *Asian Development Review*, 34(1), pp. 88–115, 2017.
- Hunt, J. and M. Gauthier-Loiselle (2010). How much does immigration boost innovation? *American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics*, 2(2): 31–56.
- Jacobs, J. (1969). *The Economy of Cities*. Vintage, New York.
- Jones, B. (2010). Age and Great Invention. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, XCII (1): 1–14.
- Kerr, W. and W.F. Lincoln (2010). The Supply Side of Innovation: H-1B Visa Reforms and U.S. Ethnic Invention. *Journal of Labour Economics*, 28(3): 473–508.
- Kratena, K., Sectoral Economy: Do sectors Really Matter? *Estudios de Economia Aplicada*, 23(2), pp. 289–298, 2005.

- McGuirk, H. and D. Jordan (2012). Local Labour Market Diversity and Business Innovation: Evidence From Irish Manufacturing Businesses. *European Planning Studies*, 20(12): 1945–1960.
- Oberg, W. (1960). Age and achievement – And the technical man. *Personnel Psychology*, 13(3), 245-259.
- Ortega, F. and G. Peri (2012). The Aggregate Effects of Trade and Migration: Evidence from OECD Countries, A. Artal-Tur G.Peri and F. Requena-Silvente (eds.) *The Socio-Economic Impact of Migration Flows. Effects on Trade, Remittances, Output, and the Labour Market*, Springer.
- Ortega, F. and G. Peri (2014). Openness and Income: The roles of Trade and Migration, *Journal of International Economics*, 92(2), 231–251.
- Østergaard, C., Timmermans B. and K. Kristinsson (2011). Does a different view create something new? The effect of employee diversity on innovation. *Research Policy*, 40(3), 500–509.
- Ozgen, C., Peters, C., Niebuhr, A., Nijkamp, P. and Poot, J. (2014). Does Cultural Diversity of Migrant Employees Affect Innovation? *International Migration Review*, 48: 377–416.
- Ozgen, C., Nijkamp, P. and J. Poot (2012). Immigration and Innovation in European Regions, in P. Nijkamp, J. Poot and M. Sahin (eds.) *Migration Impact Assessment: New Horizons*, Edward Elgar.
- Ozgen, C., Nijkamp, P. and J. Poot (2013). The Impact of Cultural Diversity on Innovation: Evidence from Dutch Firm-Level Data. *IZA Journal of Migration* 2 (18).
- Santamaría, L., Nieto, M.J. and A. Barge-Gil (2009). Beyond formal R&D: Taking advantage of other sources of innovation in low-and medium-technology industries. *Research Policy* 38, 507-517.
- Schubert, T. and M. Andersson (2013). Old is Gold? The Effects of Employee Age on Innovation and the Moderating Effects of Employment Turnover. *Papers in Innovation Studies 2013/29*, CIRCLE.
- Solow, R. M. (1957). Technical change and the aggregate production function. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 39: 312-320.
- Stahl, G. K., Maznevski, M. L., Voigt, A. and J. Karsten (2010). Unraveling the effects of cultural diversity in teams: A meta-analysis of research on multicultural work groups. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 41, 690–709.
- Trax, M., Brunow, S. and J. Suedekum (2015). Cultural diversity and plant level productivity. *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, 53: 85–96.
- Venturini A. (2004), *Post-War Migration in Southern Europe 1950-2000. An Economic Approach*, Cambridge University Press.
- Von Hippel, E.A. (1976). The Dominant Role of Users in the Scientific Instrument Innovation Process. *Research Policy* 5 (3): 212–239.
- IOM's Displacement Tracking Matrix. Migration Trends in the Western Balkans in 2022.

APPENDIX

QUESTIONNAIRE ADDRESSED TO COMPANIES

1. Industry: Construction, High-Tech, Services
2. How many people does your company employ at present? (0-9, 10-49, 50-249, 250+)
3. What age group is more suitable for the majority of your staff? (18-35, 36-65)
4. What is male to female ratio at your organization? (More men than women, more women than men, equal number of men and women)
5. How many people are employed full-time? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
6. How many people are employed part-time? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
7. How many employees have high level of education/qualification (tertiary, 13 years and more)? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
8. How many employees have medium level of education/qualification (10 to 12 years)? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
9. How many employees have low level of education/qualification (duration of education 9 years or less)? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
10. How many people are employed permanently? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
11. How many people are employed temporarily? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
12. How many foreign-born workers does your company employ at present? (0-9, 10-49, 50-249, 250+)
13. What is male to female ratio among foreign-born workers at your organization? (More men than women, more women than men, equal number of men and women)
14. What age group is more suitable for the majority of your foreign-born workers? (18-35, 36-65)
15. How many foreign-born workers are employed full-time? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
16. How many foreign-born workers are employed part-time? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
17. How many foreign-born workers have high level of education/qualification (tertiary, 13 years and more)? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
18. How many foreign-born workers have medium level of education/qualification (10 to 12 years)? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
19. How many foreign-born workers have low level of education/qualification (duration of education 9 years or less)? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
20. How many foreign-born workers are employed permanently? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
21. How many foreign-born workers are employed temporarily? (70-100%, 50-70%, 30-50%, less than 30%)
22. Does your company have R&D department? (Yes, No)
23. If yes, do you consider the total R&D expenditure as? (More than sufficient, sufficient, not sufficient)
24. In relation to your present level of output, is the number of your staff? (More than is necessary, about right, less than is necessary)

25. According to your present plans, the number of employees in your company over the next 12 to 24 months will probably (increase, remain constant, decrease, don't know)
26. Do you plan to increase or decrease the total number of employees? (Increase, decrease, no)
27. If you plan to increase the number of employees, what are the reasons?
 - Present/expected levels of demand for your products
 - Introduction of new technologies or products
 - Present/expected levels of labor costs
 - Government measures
 - Other reasons, i.e.
28. If you plan to decrease the number of employees, what are the reasons?
 - Lack of demand
 - Insufficient profit margin due to price competition/wage and salary levels in the country; non-wage labor cost level (employers' social security contribution, payroll taxes, allowances, etc.); other costs (e.g., capital costs, etc.)
 - Rationalization
 - Increase in contracting out
 - Government regulations
 - Other reasons, i.e.
29. How would you describe your staff: homogeneous (only people born in Bosnia and Herzegovina) or diverse (there are foreign-born workers)?
30. Do you think that diversity of your staff unlocks innovation? (Yes, the more diverse, the better (different views, opinions, ideas); No, there is no difference; I don't know)
31. Would you employ foreign-born staff to encourage innovation at your organization? (Yes, No)
32. What are the main constraints that don't let you easily increase the foreign-born staff?
 - Bureaucratic procedures
 - It is too expensive
 - I find it extremely difficult to manage people with diverse backgrounds
 - I don't think innovation can be driven by foreign-born staff

Profitability and Resilience: Comparative Analysis of the Performance of Islamic and Conventional Insurance Companies in the GCC Region

Abdulrahim Amrullah^{1*}

¹Hamad Bin Khalifa University (HBKU)

*Email: ad_emm@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

Fueled by a remarkable year-on-year growth in 2022, reaching USD 30 billion, the global Takaful industry is experiencing a surge. The Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), contributing a dominant 55.7% of global Takaful contributions, stands as a cornerstone of this growth. This study compares the financial metrics of Islamic (Takaful) and conventional insurance companies within the GCC region. Employing the System Generalized Method of Moments (SGMM) panel data estimator on a 10-year (2013-2022) sample of 85 insurance companies across six countries, the analysis reveals significant differences in the performances of the two insurance segments. Takaful companies generally exhibit lower capitalization, leverage, solvency, claim ratios, and firm size but demonstrate higher premium growth than their conventional counterparts. Furthermore, the study identifies economic growth as a key driver of profitability, while firm-specific factors like leverage, capital adequacy, and firm size also play a significant role. Interestingly, neither the business model nor the COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted profitability, highlighting the industry's adaptability and robust risk management practices. These findings offer valuable insights for stakeholders to make informed decisions on fostering growth, stability, and innovation within the GCC's insurance landscape. Additionally, the research emphasizes the need for continuous analysis to adapt to evolving market conditions and regulatory environments and ensure long-term sustainability for the region's insurance sector.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received: April 19, 2025

Accepted: June 5, 2025

Published: June 30, 2025

KEYWORDS

Islamic Finance; Takaful; insurance; GCC; financial performance;

JEL CODES

G22; G21; C23; G15; G32;

HOW TO CITE

Amrullah, A. (2025). Profitability and Resilience: Comparative Analysis of the Performance of Islamic and Conventional Insurance Companies in the GCC Region. *Journal of Economics, Law and Society*, 2(1), 51-72. <https://doi.org/10.70009/jels.2025.2.1.3>

1. INTRODUCTION

Takaful, a Shari'ah-compliant alternative to conventional insurance, is gaining global popularity. Both Islamic and conventional insurance offer risk protection but differ in principles and mechanisms. Takaful operates on mutual assistance, risk sharing, cooperation, and solidarity among participants. Members contribute to a common pool (*Tabarru'*) used to pay claims and expenses, with any surplus distributed among them. Conventional insurance, by contrast, involves transferring risk from the insured to the insurer in exchange for a premium. The insurer assumes the risk and compensates the insured for covered losses, based on the principle of indemnity. Despite differences, both systems protect against risks, promote financial stability, and involve the pooling and sharing of resources.

According to the Islamic Financial Services Industry Stability 2023 report (IFSB, 2023), the global Takaful industry grew by 16.1% in 2022, reaching USD 30 billion, far exceeding the 5.4% growth of the previous year. The GCC region remains the top Takaful market, accounting for 55.7% of the global share, with a 24.4% annual growth to USD 16.7 billion, signaling a strong post-pandemic recovery. South-East Asia and the Middle East/South Asia regions each contribute 20%.

Saudi Arabia leads the GCC Takaful market, recording 26.9% annual growth in contributions to reach USD 14.2 billion, representing 87% of the region's total. Qatar's Takaful sector grew 72.5% to USD 527 million, while Oman saw moderate 7.7% growth, and Bahrain recorded a 4.9% decline, mainly due to reduced health insurance contributions.

Despite growing academic interest in Islamic finance, a significant research gap remains concerning the comparative financial performance and resilience of Takaful and conventional insurance firms in the GCC. Most existing studies either focus on one insurance model or lack robust empirical approaches that test resilience in the face of systemic shocks. Furthermore, while many studies report on firm-specific or macroeconomic determinants of profitability, few integrate these variables into a theory-driven empirical framework. To address this shortfall, this study systematically examines the performance and resilience of both insurance models in the GCC, applying a theory-anchored empirical investigation to better understand their behavior under normal and crisis conditions.

The study poses three key research questions:

- RQ1:* Do Islamic (Takaful) and conventional insurance firms in the GCC exhibit significant differences in profitability and financial structure?
- RQ2:* What are the firm-specific and macroeconomic determinants of profitability for insurance firms in the region?
- RQ3:* How did the COVID-19 pandemic affect the profitability and resilience of Takaful versus conventional insurers?

By addressing these questions, this research aims to contribute both empirically and theoretically to the discourse on Islamic finance and insurance resilience.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to bridge the existing research gap by offering a comparative analysis of the performance metrics of Takaful and conventional insurance firms within the unique context of the GCC. Given the region's dominant position in the global Takaful market, a deeper understanding of these sectors is critical. By unveiling the nuances of their comparative performance, this study aims to provide valuable insights for policymakers, investors, and other stakeholders operating within the GCC's insurance market.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews relevant literature. Section 3 outlines the research method and variables. Section 4 presents and discusses empirical results. Section 5 concludes the study, acknowledges limitations, and proposes areas for future research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Concept of Takaful

The rise of Islamic banking in the late 20th century highlighted the need for risk-management tools compatible with Islamic finance principles (COMCEC, 2019). Takaful emerged as a crucial component of the Islamic financial system, complementing its development and success. Numerous Takaful models and companies have since been established, catering to Muslims who previously lacked access to conventional insurance due to religious restrictions. Takaful allows them to participate in financial opportunities while adhering to their faith's principles.

Takaful can be defined as a mutual guarantee or assurance scheme. A group of individuals facing similar risks contributes to a common fund. This fund is then used to compensate any member who incurs a covered loss (Alhabshi et al., 2012). The International Islamic Fiqh Academy (IIFA) offers a

similar definition, referring to Takaful as “cooperative insurance”, where participants contribute to a fund used to compensate each other for pre-defined risks (OIC, 2016, p. 117).

2.2. Determinants of Insurance Sector Growth

The study by Msomi and Nzama (2023) examines how firm-specific characteristics impact the financial performance of insurance companies in South Africa, measured by return on assets (ROA). The analysis covers 36 publicly traded companies from 2008 to 2019. The authors utilize panel data estimators, including fixed and random effects, to assess the impact of factors like firm size, leverage ratio, premium growth rate, liquidity ratio, and tangibility of assets on ROA. The research reveals that other firm-specific factors have no statistically significant influence except for leverage and liquidity ratios. Liquidity demonstrated a strong positive relationship, whereas leverage negatively impacted ROA. Higher liquidity suggests a greater capacity to meet policyholder obligations, potentially leading to increased ROA. It suggests that higher liquidity allows insurance firms to meet obligations more efficiently, reducing default risk and enhancing confidence among policyholders and investors. Additionally, sufficient liquidity enables firms to capitalize on investment opportunities. Therefore, the positive relationship between liquidity and profitability highlights the importance of financial stability and flexibility. The authors recommend implementing automated systems to reduce costs and highlight the significance of effective asset management.

Furthermore, Msomi (2023) investigates factors affecting the financial performance of non-life insurance companies in Africa. Analyzing data from 121 listed insurers across 48 nations from 2008 to 2019, the study employs ordinary least squares and two-step System Generalized Method of Moments (SGMM) estimators to assess determinants. Lagged ROA, equity capital, operational efficiency, leverage, investment capability, and GDP emerged as important. Equity capital has an inversely significant impact, suggesting negative effects from imbalanced capital structures. Operational efficiency and investment capability positively influence performance, while leverage negatively affects it. GDP growth rate positively influences performance. No significant effects were found from factors like insurer age, size, underwriting risk, claims ratio, liquidity, interest rate, inflation rate, exchange rate, or money supply.

Furthermore, Msomi (2023) investigates factors affecting the financial performance of non-life insurance companies in Africa. Analyzing data from 121 listed insurers across 48 nations from 2008 to 2019, the study employs ordinary least squares and two-step System Generalized Method of Moments (SGMM) estimators to assess determinants. Lagged ROA, equity capital, operational efficiency, leverage, investment capability, and GDP emerged as important. Equity capital has an inversely significant impact, suggesting negative effects from imbalanced capital structures. Operational efficiency and investment capability positively influence performance, while leverage negatively affects it. GDP growth rate positively influences performance. No significant effects were found from factors like insurer age, size, underwriting risk, claims ratio, liquidity, interest rate, inflation rate, exchange rate, or money supply.

Morara and Sibindi (2021) address a gap in research by exploring determinants of financial performance in the Kenyan insurance industry, analyzing data from 2009 to 2018, encompassing 37 general and 16 life insurers. Using ROA and Return on Equity (ROE) as metrics, larger companies exhibit better profitability. A positive association between financial performance and leverage highlights the potential benefit of strategic debt use, though maintaining an optimal debt ratio is emphasized. Positive associations are also identified between performance, reinsurance ratios, and investment decisions, indicating that effective risk management and sound investment strategies improve financial health.

Derbali (2014) investigates factors influencing performance within the Tunisian life insurance sector, analyzing data from eight companies over 11 years (2005-2015). Size, age, and growth are

significant positive determinants of performance, while leverage, tangibility, liquidity, and risk have no significant effect.

Several studies have explored determinants influencing the financial performance of Takaful companies globally. Kantakji et al. (2020) examine drivers of performance for general Takaful companies worldwide, highlighting the importance of market size, economic conditions, investment returns, and robust risk management. Strategies like mergers, liquidity optimization, and adherence to Shari'ah principles are suggested.

Hodori and Masih (2017) analyze the Malaysian Takaful industry, finding that larger and older Takaful operators are more profitable due to expanded risk pools and diversified lines, while younger firms display greater efficiency. A correlation between the profitability of newer Takaful companies and affiliations with conventional insurance companies is noted.

In addition, Sahudin et al. (2022) investigate micro- and macro-level factors influencing Takaful performance in Malaysia, using panel data from five companies over ten years. Liquidity and firm size positively relate to performance, while GDP negatively impacts it.

Prakoso (2021) analyzes determinants of Family Takaful earnings in Indonesia, finding that leverage and premium contributions positively impact profitability. Higher leverage allows Takaful companies to meet obligations, while increased premium contributions expand market share and income.

Meanwhile, Malahim (2016) examines Islamic insurance companies in Jordan, revealing that firm size positively impacts earnings (ROE). No significant associations are found with debt ratio, equity ratio, GDP growth, inflation, or unemployment.

Understanding the comparative performance of Takaful and conventional insurance companies is important. Akhter et al. (2017) compare the demand dynamics of Takaful and conventional insurance across 14 countries from 2005 to 2014. The study investigates insurance demand differences and examines resilience post-Global Financial Crisis (GFC). GDP per capita negatively impacts both insurance types during crises, but Islamic insurance shows greater resilience. Conventional insurance is negatively linked to the saving rate, while Islamic insurance remains unaffected. Education positively influences Islamic insurance demand. Higher average income affects Islamic insurance positively in the Middle East but negatively in ASEAN, attributed to differing perspectives on Islamic finance. The study offers a comparative analysis between determinants of conventional and Islamic insurance products and their responses during crises, providing insights for policymakers and insurers

2.3. Insights from the GCC Insurance Sector

2.3.1. A Closer Look at Regional Insurance Markets

According to the GCC Insurance Industry Report (AP, 2024), the GCC insurance industry has witnessed robust growth, surging by 15.2% year-on-year from USD 28.4 billion in 2021 to USD 32.7 billion in 2022. This expansion was fueled by post-COVID-19 economic recovery and the establishment of mandatory health insurance schemes across GCC nations. The GCC's Gross Written Premium (GWP) increased at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 4.4% from USD 26.4 billion in 2017 to USD 32.7 billion in 2022, driven by economic resurgence, population growth, infrastructure investments, and economic diversification endeavors. Non-life insurance dominated the market, accounting for 88.5% of total GWP, propelled by health and motor insurance advancements.

Despite growth, insurance penetration rates remained low, offering expansion opportunities supported by favorable demographics and regulations. The GCC's insurance density averaged USD 582.2 per capita in 2022, led by the UAE at USD 1,305. The GCC also hosts the world's largest Takaful market, with Saudi Arabia driving growth through mandatory insurance coverage. Mergers within the Takaful sector reflect increased competition and regulatory demands. The GCC insurance industry is poised for sustained growth and innovation, backed by regulatory reforms, economic resilience, and consumer awareness.

2.3.1.1. National Insurance Landscapes

- **Saudi Arabia:** Saudi Arabia's insurance sector, the largest in the GCC, is regulated by the Insurance Authority and includes 27 licensed companies, all offering Takaful products. Capital requirements are USD 27 million for insurers and USD 53 million for reinsurers. In 2022, the sector grew by 26.9% to a GWP of USD 14.2 billion, supported by post-pandemic recovery, a strong oil market, and non-oil sector growth. Mergers, such as Walaa with Sabb Takaful and Arabian Shield with Alahli Takaful, illustrate the push toward consolidation aligned with Vision 2030.

Regulatory milestones included new motor insurance rules, adoption of IFRS 17 and IFRS 9 standards, and the establishment of the Insurance Authority in 2023 to centralize regulation. Saudi Arabia's insurance penetration stood at 1.3% in 2022, below the GCC average, with insurance density at USD 442.2, but regulatory reforms are expected to drive future growth.

- **United Arab Emirates (UAE):** The UAE's dynamic insurance sector comprises 60 licensed companies—50 conventional and 10 Takaful—regulated by the Central Bank of the UAE and others. Capital requirements are USD 27 million for insurers and USD 68 million for reinsurers. As the GCC's second-largest insurance market and ranked 36th globally by GWP in 2022, the UAE's growth is fueled by economic strength, reforms, and consumer awareness. Non-life insurance dominates, comprising 78.5% of GWP, while life insurance remains strong despite declining individual GWP.

Key regulatory initiatives include adopting IFRS 17, Emiratization policies, and the unemployment insurance scheme. Technology integration aims to enhance compliance and customer experience, reinforcing the UAE's leadership.

- **Qatar:** Qatar's insurance market is regulated by the Qatar Central Bank (QCB) and Qatar Financial Centre Regulatory Authority (QFCRA). It has 16 licensed insurers, with 12 conventional and four Takaful providers. Capital requirements are USD 10 million. Qatar ranked 67th globally in GWP in 2022, contributing 5.4% to the GCC total, with a GWP of USD 1.8 billion.

Growth drivers include a large expatriate population, high GDP per capita, and infrastructure development. Regulatory advancements included a compulsory health insurance law. In 2023, QCB announced strategies to promote Insurtech, broadening insurance offerings and digitalization. Despite challenges, Qatar's insurance sector remains resilient.

- **Kuwait:** Kuwait's insurance sector, regulated by the Ministry of Commerce and Industry (MOCI), includes 26 licensed insurers: 11 conventional and 15 Takaful. Capital requirements are USD 16 million for insurers and USD 49 million for reinsurers. With the fastest growth in the GCC, Kuwait achieved a CAGR of 8.7% from 2017 to 2022, driven by mandatory medical insurance for expatriates.

Non-life insurance accounted for 90.2% of GWP in 2022. Key regulatory initiatives included reforms in motor insurance and health insurance for foreign nationals over

60. Though insurance penetration was only 1.0% in 2022, robust growth and regulatory efforts suggest strong future prospects.

- **Bahrain:** Bahrain’s insurance market, regulated by the Central Bank of Bahrain (CBB), consists of 31 companies—26 conventional and five Takaful. Capital requirements are USD 13 million for insurers and USD 26 million for reinsurers. Bahrain’s insurance sector saw marginal growth, reaching a GWP of USD 0.7 billion in 2022, with non-life insurance dominating at 87.2%.

Key regulatory efforts included improving market conduct in motor insurance and preparing for IFRS 17 adoption. Despite low penetration rates, Bahrain’s insurance market remains stable, supported by regulatory initiatives.

- **Oman:** Regulated by the Capital Market Authority, Oman’s sector has 19 insurers: 17 conventional and two Takaful, with a capital requirement of USD 26 million. Despite being among the smallest in the GCC, Oman’s insurance market grew steadily, reaching USD 1.4 billion in GWP in 2022.

Non-life insurance accounted for 87.6% of GWP, driven mainly by the health insurance segment, aided by mandatory health insurance for over 5 million people. Regulatory efforts focused on digitalization through initiatives like the Dhamani platform. Although challenges remain, Oman’s insurance sector shows resilience and growth potential.

In conclusion, while the GCC insurance industry shows strong promise, a more detailed understanding of the drivers behind its growth is essential. Further research can unlock new insights to support continued expansion.

2.3.2. Academic Insights

Research has examined factors influencing insurance company performance in the GCC region. Al-Mutairi et al. (2021) analyzed financial statements of 17 insurance firms listed on the Abu Dhabi Securities Exchange (ADX) from 2013 to 2019 using panel regression. They investigated liquidity, administration expenses, risk, size, tangibility, and age, finding that company age significantly boosts profitability. Older firms benefit from a stronger image, larger customer base, and sustained profits, aiding investor decision-making and offering research avenues into GCC insurance performance.

Alshadadi and Deshmukh (2021) explored profitability determinants in Saudi insurance companies, using panel regression on data from 25 firms (2010–2016). They found that company size positively correlates with profitability, while higher debt and loss ratios negatively affect it. Although retention ratio and investment income showed some impact, size, debt, and losses were the most influential factors. Despite development efforts, Saudi Arabia’s insurance sector faces challenges like low per capita expenditure and structural weaknesses.

Ben Dhiab (2021) studied 20 major Saudi insurance firms (2009–2017) and found that growth in written premiums and higher asset tangibility positively impacted profitability. In contrast, higher loss ratios, greater leverage, and younger firm age negatively influenced financial performance. The study emphasized managing capital investments, controlling leverage, minimizing losses, and strategically growing premiums as key profitability strategies, recommending future research into broader macroeconomic impacts and extension to other GCC countries.

Hemrit (2020) investigated financial performance determinants for Takaful and cooperative insurance in Saudi Arabia, using a dynamic panel generalized method of moments estimation. Company size, insurance penetration, risk reporting, and board size influenced performance. A Shari’ah

board positively impacted Takaful firms, while non-executive directors negatively influenced both sectors. Interestingly, higher inflation improved cooperative insurers' financial performance, likely due to increased insurance demand during inflationary periods.

Ab Rahim et al. (2021) assessed efficiency among 140 Takaful and conventional firms in the GCC (2015–2019) using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). Takaful firms showed strong technical efficiency (82%) but lagged in cost efficiency compared to conventional insurers, who benefited from technological advancements. Qatar and Bahrain led in efficiency. The study recommended prioritizing cost efficiency and technological innovation, emphasizing regulator-industry collaboration for a more competitive market.

Finally, Alshammari et al. (2018) offered a historical and contemporary overview of the GCC's insurance and Takaful sectors. They highlighted low insurance penetration, limited family Takaful products, and inconsistent regulatory frameworks as persistent challenges, despite the region's emergence as a Takaful hub.

2.4. Theoretical Framework

2.4.1. Agency Theory

Developed by Jensen and Meckling (1976), this theory addresses the conflicts of interest between principals (owners or shareholders) and agents (managers), which give rise to agency costs. These include monitoring costs, bonding expenditures, and residual losses. The theory suggests that firms with governance structures that align incentives between principals and agents experience lower agency costs and thus better performance. This perspective is particularly relevant in comparing Takaful and conventional insurance firms, as Takaful models promote shared ownership and mutual accountability, potentially reducing agency costs.

2.4.2. Financial Slack Theory

Introduced by Bourgeois (1981), this theory conceptualizes slack as excess resources, such as surplus capital, human resources, or time, that exceed the minimum requirements for efficient function. These slack resources fulfill several key functions: they act as buffers against environmental shocks, facilitate internal conflict resolution, and enable strategic flexibility and innovation. In the context of insurance firms, slack in the form of capital adequacy or reduced financial leverage may enable firms to maintain profitability during economic fluctuations.

2.4.3. Organizational Resilience Theory

This study adopts the conceptualization of organizational resilience proposed by Lengnick-Hall et al. (2011), who define resilience as a dynamic capability developed through strategic human resource management and internal organizational routines. Unlike traditional views that frame resilience as mere recovery or “bouncing back,” their model emphasizes an organization's ability to absorb disruption, respond with context-specific strategies, and transform operations to create long-term advantages. In the context of insurance firms, this theory helps explain how pre-existing internal capabilities such as financial flexibility, governance systems, and employee adaptability can influence a firm's ability to maintain profitability and deliver services during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic.

2.5. Key Takeaways and Hypotheses

The reviewed literature provides valuable insights into the various factors influencing the financial performance of insurance companies. Studies highlight the significance of firm-specific

characteristics, macroeconomic factors, and the GFC in shaping the financial landscape of the insurance industry. The firm size and liquidity are consistently linked to better financial performance. Larger and more liquid companies seem to benefit from economies of scale, diversification, and improved capacity to meet obligations. Meanwhile, the impact of other firm-specific factors like leverage, tangibility, and age is mixed and may depend on the specific market context. Finding optimal debt levels, managing asset allocation, and building a strong reputation remain crucial considerations. Moreover, macroeconomic factors like GDP growth can positively influence performance, but the relationship with inflation is complex and may vary depending on the insurance type (e.g., Takaful). Hence, understanding the specific market dynamics is essential. Effective risk management, investment strategies, and customer satisfaction also play a significant role in achieving sustainable profitability.

Potential differences exist between the performance of Takaful and conventional insurance companies, requiring further investigation. The GFC had a significant impact on the insurance industry. Hence, the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the performance of both sectors in the GCC region remains an open question and warrants further research.

Based on the theoretical frameworks and literature review, we propose the following hypotheses:

- H1.* Islamic insurance companies (Takaful) in the GCC region exhibit different financial performance metrics compared to conventional insurance companies.

(Justification: According to Jensen and Meckling (1976), Agency Theory suggests Takaful's mutual structure (policyholders as joint principals/agents) reduces traditional owner-manager conflicts, predicting distinct financial metrics versus conventional insurers' shareholder-driven model.)

- H2.* Firm-specific factors (leverage, capital adequacy and firm size) and country-specific factors (economic growth and inflation) significantly influence the performance of both Takaful and conventional insurance companies.

(Justification: Drawing on Bourgeois's (1981) Organizational Slack Theory, firm-specific characteristics such as leverage, capital adequacy, and size represent forms of slack that can buffer against uncertainty, support operational flexibility, and enhance profitability under varying economic conditions.)

- H3.* The COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the performance of both Takaful and conventional insurance sectors in the GCC region.

(Justification: Based on Lengnick-Hall et al. (2011), firms with stronger resilience capacity shaped by internal routines, human capital, and adaptive structures are better able to maintain performance during external shocks such as the COVID-19 pandemic.)

The theoretical link between profitability and organizational resilience is grounded in Financial Slack Theory (Bourgeois, 1981), which posits that firms with stronger profitability generate surplus internal resources that can be utilized during times of stress. These financial reserves enhance a firm's ability to absorb shocks, maintain operations, and adapt strategically to changing environments. In this sense, profitability serves not only as an outcome of operational efficiency but also as a buffer and enabler of resilience, particularly during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, according to Organizational Resilience Theory (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011), resilient firms are characterized by proactive resource management and adaptive capabilities, both of which are more easily developed and maintained in profitable firms that have the means to invest in long-term strategies, human capital, and system redundancies. Therefore, conceptually, higher profitability contributes

to an organization's resilience by enabling sustained performance and strategic flexibility under adverse conditions.

3. METHODOLOGY AND DATA

3.1. Data

The data sample consists of 85 insurance companies (N=85) from six countries, where 49 are conventional and 36 are Takaful companies, utilizing annual data from 2013 to 2022 (T=10). The firm-specific data is extracted from the Refinitiv Eikon (RE) database, whereas the macroeconomic variables (country-specific factors) are collected from the World Bank (WDI) database. A detailed description of all variables, including their indicators, expected signs, and sources, is provided in *Table 1*.

Table 1: Description of Variables

Variable	Indicator	Description	Expected Sign	Source
Dependent Variable				
ROA	Return On Asset	Net Income / Total Assets		RE
Independent Variables				
Country-Specific Variables				
IF	Inflation Rate	Inflation, consumer prices (annual %)	-	WDI
EG	Economic Growth	GDP per capita growth (annual %)	+	WDI
Firm-Specific Variables				
EC	Equity Capital	Log (Total Assets – Total Liabilities)	+	RE
LR	Leverage Ratio	Total Debt / Total Equity	-	RE
SR	Solvency Ratio	Net Income / Total Liabilities	+	RE
CR	Claims Ratio	Claims paid / Net premium	+	RE
PG	Premium Growth	(NP t-1 – NP t) / NP t-1	-/+	RE
CA	Capital Adequacy	Total Equity / Total Assets	+	RE
SIZE	Firm Size	Log of Total Assets	+	RE
Dummy Variables				
IDS	Specialization ID	IDS = 1 for Takaful companies	+	
GHC	Global Health Crisis	GHC = 1 during the pandemic	-	

Note: NP = Net Premium, RE = Refinitiv Eikon, WDI = World Development Indicator. Expected signs represent common theoretical predictions; actual results may vary. Pandemic years are defined as 2020, 2021, and 2022 for the GHC dummy.

3.2. Model Specification

The study compares the performance of Islamic and conventional insurance firms in the GCC region. The main model under scrutiny includes firm-specific (FSV) and country-specific (CSV) factors, a business model specialization dummy (IDS), and a COVID-19 pandemic dummy (GHC). The baseline model is specified as:

$$ROA_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 ROA_{it-1} + \beta_2 CSV_{it} + \beta_3 FSV_{it} + \beta_4 IDS_i + \beta_5 GHC_t + \alpha_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (Eq. 1)$$

Where: ROA_{it} is the Return on Assets of firm i at time t ; ROA_{it-1} is the lagged dependent variable; FSV_{it} is a vector of firm-specific variables including EC, LR, SR, CR, PG, CA, and SZ; CSV_{it} is a vector of country-specific macroeconomic variables including EG and IF; IDS_i is a dummy variable equal to 1 for Takaful companies and 0 for conventional companies; GHC_t is a dummy variable equal to 1 for

the pandemic years (2020-2022) and 0 otherwise; β_n are the regression coefficients to be estimated; α_i represents the unobserved time-invariant firm-specific effects; λ_t represents the time-specific effects (year dummies); and ε_{it} is the idiosyncratic error term.

In addition, to assess the differential impact of internal factors on the financial performance of Takaful versus conventional insurance companies, particularly during the GHC, models incorporating triple interaction terms are estimated. Conceptually, this involves interacting specific firm variables with the specialization dummy and the pandemic dummy:

$$ROA_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 ROA_{it-1} + \beta_2 CSV_{it} + \beta_3 FSV_{it} + \beta_4 IDS_i + \beta_5 GHC_t + \beta_6 (\text{Specific FSV}_{it} \times IDS_i \times GHC_t) + \alpha_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (Eq. 2)$$

Where: β_6 (Specific FSV_{it} X IDS_i X GHC_t) represents the triple interaction term for a 'specific' firm-level variable (LR_{it} X IDS_i X GHC_t). Separate models are estimated for interactions with different firm-specific variables, as presented in the results section.

3.3. Research Methods

The study adopts two distinct analytical methods to explore and test the research hypotheses: A two-sample t-test and the System GMM (SGMM) estimator.

First Hypothesis: To compare the financial performance metrics of Islamic and conventional insurance companies in the GCC region (Hypothesis 1), we employ a two-sample t-test. This approach allows for a direct comparison of the mean financial characteristics between the two types of insurance entities, consistent with prior research (Hidayat, 2015; Guendouz, 2018).

Second and Third Hypotheses: To estimate the determinants of profitability specified in equation 1 and the interaction models based on equation 2 (addressing Hypotheses 2 and 3), the study employs the two-step SGMM method. SGMM is a robust econometric technique particularly suited for dynamic panel data models, addressing common issues such as endogeneity (especially from the lagged dependent variable and potentially other regressors) and unobserved heterogeneity (Arellano and Bover, 1995; Blundell and Bond, 1998).

Rationale for GMM: Traditional panel data estimation methods like Pooled OLS, Fixed Effects (FE), or Random Effects (RE) can yield biased and inconsistent estimates when the model includes a lagged dependent variable ($ROA_{i,t-1}$) and potentially endogenous regressors, in the presence of unobserved firm-specific effects (α_i). The GMM approach overcomes these limitations. Specifically, the SGMM estimator, developed by Blundell and Bond (1998), builds upon the Difference GMM (DGMM) of Arellano (1991) by using a system of equations – one in first differences (instrumented with lagged levels) and one in levels (instrumented with lagged first differences). This improves efficiency and performs better when variables are persistent over time.

GMM estimators offer two key advantages: they address potential simultaneity bias by using internal instruments (lagged values of variables), and they control for unobserved firm-specific heterogeneity and time-specific effects.

The SGMM approach is preferred over DGMM in this context because the lagged ROA coefficient estimated via DGMM was found to be close to the FE estimate, suggesting potential weak instrument issues that SGMM is designed to mitigate (see [Section 4.3](#)). Furthermore, SGMM allows for the inclusion and estimation of coefficients for time-invariant variables like the specialization dummy (IDS), which would be removed by the differencing process in DGMM.

The choice of GMM is further justified by the panel structure ($N > T$; 85 firms over 10 years) and the dynamic nature of profitability (inclusion of lagged ROA). This aligns with established practices in empirical finance and corporate governance research employing panel data, e.g., Vojinovic (2022), Parkoso (2021), and Hodori (2017). We utilize the two-step SGMM estimator with robust standard errors corrected for finite samples using the Windmeijer (2005) correction to ensure reliable inference. Instrument validity is assessed using the Hansen test of overidentifying restrictions and Arellano-Bond tests for serial correlation in the residuals.

4. DISCUSSIONS OF THE RESULTS

4.1. Preliminary Analysis

This section discusses the empirical findings derived from the analyses. We begin with descriptive statistics and correlations before moving to the main regression results.

4.1.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 presents the summary statistics for the variables used in the study over the period 2013-2022 for the 85 sample firms.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	<i>mean</i>	<i>min</i>	<i>max</i>	<i>sd</i>	<i>skewness</i>	<i>kurtosis</i>	<i>count</i>
Return on Assets	0.017	-0.908	0.360	0.065	-5.223	66.853	688
Economic Growth	0.642	-7.169	7.375	3.475	-0.079	2.334	688
Inflation	1.613	-2.540	4.995	1.834	-0.605	2.680	688
Leverage Ratio	0.127	0.000	16.795	0.782	17.111	336.206	688
Solvency Ratio	0.001	-14.042	0.913	0.572	-21.939	530.769	688
Claims Ratio	1.039	0.044	10.099	0.702	6.604	72.274	688
Premium Growth	0.222	-0.968	30.642	1.755	10.105	145.164	688
Capital Adequacy	0.354	0.006	0.998	0.165	0.747	3.752	688
Equity Capital	8.002	5.699	9.485	0.471	0.313	4.257	688
Firm Size	8.511	7.083	10.079	0.471	0.638	3.797	688

Source: Author's calculation based on data from Refinitiv Eikon and World Bank. $N = 85$ firms, $T = 10$ years (2013-2022). Total observations = 850 (unbalanced panel).

The average Return on Assets (ROA) is low at 1.7%, with considerable variation ($SD = 6.5\%$) and significant negative skewness, indicating that while most firms have low profitability, some experience substantial losses. Key firm characteristics like Leverage Ratio (LR), Capital Adequacy (CA), and Firm Size (SZ) show wide ranges. Premium Growth (PG) is highly volatile. Economic Growth (EG) averages slightly positive but is also volatile. The high kurtosis for several variables (ROA, LR, SR, CR, PG) suggests the presence of extreme values or outliers in the sample.

4.1.2. Correlation Matrix

Table 3 displays the Pearson correlation coefficients among the main variables. The correlations are generally low to moderate, mitigating concerns about severe multicollinearity among most independent variables. However, the correlation between Equity Capital (EC) and Firm Size (SZ) is high (0.85), which is expected as larger firms typically have more equity. This high correlation warrants caution when interpreting models including both variables; however, GMM is generally robust to

moderate multicollinearity. ROA is positively correlated with SR, CA, EC, and SZ, and negatively correlated with LR, aligning with initial expectations.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

	ROA	EG	IF	LR	SR	CR	PG	CA	EC	Size
ROA	1.00									
EG	-0.00	1.00								
IF	-0.01	0.40**	1.00							
LR	-0.18**	-0.01	-0.03	1.00						
SR	0.31**	0.04	-0.04	-0.02	1.00					
CR	-0.03	-0.03	-0.00	0.05	0.02	1.00				
PG	0.03	0.00	0.00	-0.00	0.02	-0.06*	1.00			
CA	0.16**	-0.09**	0.00	-0.14**	-0.13**	-0.01	-0.02	1.00		
EC	0.34**	-0.11**	0.00	-0.20**	0.11**	0.08**	0.05	0.12**	1.00	
Size	0.23**	-0.06	0.01	-0.03	0.13**	0.06	0.04	-0.34**	0.85**	1.00

Note(s): Pearson correlation coefficients. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$. Variable definitions are in Table 1. The high correlation between EC and SZ (0.85) suggests potential multicollinearity if both are included simultaneously without caution. ROA shows significant positive correlation with SR, CA, EC, and SZ, and negative correlation with LR.

Source: Author's calculation.

4.2. Two Group t-test

To test Hypothesis 1 regarding differences between conventional and Takaful firms, a two-sample t-test comparing the means of key financial metrics was conducted. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: t-test for mean

	Insurance-Takaful	
Return on Assets	0.01**	[0.00]
Leverage Ratio	0.09*	[0.05]
Solvency Ratio	0.08**	[0.04]
Claims Ratio	0.11**	[0.05]
Premium Growth	-0.46	[0.44]
Capital Adequacy	0.03**	[0.01]
Equity Capital	0.22**	[0.03]
Firm Size	0.19**	[0.03]

Note: Standard errors in brackets. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$

The t-test results indicate statistically significant differences between conventional and Takaful insurance companies for most variables examined. Conventional firms, on average, exhibit significantly higher ROA, LR, SR, CR, CA, EC, and SZ. This suggests conventional insurers in the GCC tend to be more profitable, more leveraged, hold higher solvency margins (as measured here), have higher claims ratios, better capital adequacy, and are larger in size compared to their Takaful counterparts during the sample period. No significant difference was found for Premium Growth (PG). These findings support Hypothesis 1 and align with observations by Janjua and Akmal (2015) in a different market context.

This performance disparity may be explained through the lens of Agency Theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976), which suggests that differences in governance and ownership structures affect

firm behavior and performance. The mutual ownership structure of Takaful firms, while potentially reducing agency costs, may also impose operational and investment constraints not faced by conventional insurers. In contrast, conventional firms despite possibly facing higher agency costs, may benefit from more flexible capital structures and profit-maximization strategies, which could contribute to their superior financial performance.

4.3. GMM Model Selection

To justify the choice of SGMM over DGMM, we followed the approach suggested by Bond (2002) and compared the coefficient of the lagged dependent variable $ROA_{i,t-1}$ obtained from Pooled OLS (POLS), Fixed Effects (FE), DGMM, and SGMM. POLS is expected to be biased upwards, while FE is expected to be biased downwards in dynamic panels with small T. A consistent GMM estimate should lie between the POLS and FE estimates. Our preliminary analysis showed the DGMM coefficient for L.ROA was close to the FE estimate, potentially indicating weak instruments, thus favoring the SGMM approach, which is designed to improve upon DGMM in such cases. Additionally, SGMM allows for estimation of the time-invariant IDS dummy.

Table 5: Choice between Difference and System GMM

	POLS	FE	DGMM
L.Return on Assets	0.513** (0.042)	0.288** (0.050)	0.105 (0.128)
Time effects	Yes	Yes	Yes
AR(1)			0.041
AR(2)			0.581
Hansen test			0.443
Sargan test			0.007
Number of instruments			30
Number of groups			80
GMM Type			difference
Two-Step			twostep
Robust			robust

Note(s): The coefficient of lagged dependent variable in Pooled OLS is upward bias, while in Fixed Effects it is downward bias. Use these two coefficients as upper and lower bounds, respectively. If this coefficient in Differenced GMM is closer to Fixed Effects or below it, then apply System GMM. Number of instruments should be not more than the Number of groups. The p-value of AR(1) should be lesser than 0.05; whereas p-value of AR(2) should be more than 0.05. Null hypothesis: No Autocorrelation. Hansen/Sargan p-values should be more than 0.05. Null hypothesis: The instruments are valid. If you apply robust option, then refer to Hansen test.* p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05.

For the SGMM estimation, we used the two-step procedure with Windmeijer (2005) finite-sample correction for standard errors. To avoid instrument proliferation, the instrument set was collapsed. The validity of the instruments was checked using the Hansen J-statistic (testing overidentifying restrictions) and the Arellano-Bond tests for first-order (AR(1)) and second-order (AR(2)) serial correlation in the differenced residuals. The null hypothesis for the Hansen test is that the instruments are valid (exogenous). The null for AR(1) is no first-order serial correlation, which is expected to be rejected. The crucial test is AR(2), where the null is no second-order serial correlation; failure to reject AR(2) supports the model specification and instrument validity.

Table 6: GMM Outputs

	<i>Model 1</i>	<i>Model 2</i>	<i>Model 3</i>	<i>Model 4</i>	<i>Model 5</i>	<i>Model 6</i>	<i>Model 7</i>
L.Return on Assets	0.574** (0.107)	0.602** (0.082)	0.304** (0.118)	0.391** (0.112)	0.569** (0.102)	0.513** (0.061)	0.571** (0.101)
Economic Growth (EG)	0.001* (0.001)	0.001** (0.001)	0.000 (0.001)	0.000 (0.001)	0.001* (0.001)	0.002** (0.001)	0.001* (0.001)
Inflation (IF)	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.000 (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.001 (0.001)
Leverage Ratio (LR)	-0.021* (0.012)	-0.014 (0.010)	-0.023 (0.014)	-0.051* (0.029)	-0.018 (0.011)	-0.009 (0.006)	-0.019* (0.011)
Solvency Ratio (SR)	0.036 (0.028)	0.029 (0.020)	0.244** (0.077)	0.039 (0.042)	0.034 (0.024)	0.031 (0.024)	0.038 (0.028)
Claims Ratio (CR)	-0.000 (0.002)	0.001 (0.002)	0.001 (0.001)	-0.002 (0.003)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.000 (0.002)	0.000 (0.002)
Premium Growth (PG)	0.003 (0.004)	0.003 (0.002)	0.003* (0.002)	0.002 (0.004)	0.001 (0.003)	0.003 (0.002)	0.005* (0.003)
Capital Adequacy (CA)	0.180** (0.057)	0.104** (0.037)	0.161 (0.111)	0.232** (0.096)	0.188** (0.058)	0.085** (0.016)	0.189** (0.074)
Firm Size (Size)	0.039** (0.014)	0.027** (0.014)	0.037 (0.023)	0.039* (0.020)	0.040** (0.015)	0.030** (0.010)	0.026** (0.011)
Specialization ID (ISL)	0.005 (0.007)	0.002 (0.005)	0.013* (0.007)	0.004 (0.012)	0.006 (0.007)	-0.011 (0.012)	-0.187 (0.171)
Pandemic (GHC)	-0.008 (0.006)	-0.003 (0.006)	-0.002 (0.007)	0.005 (0.023)	0.000 (0.007)	-0.017 (0.018)	-0.081 (0.090)
ISL X GHC		-0.010 (0.008)	-0.008 (0.009)	0.001 (0.041)	-0.009 (0.009)	0.052* (0.029)	-0.155 (0.233)
Constant	-0.385** (0.140)	-0.259** (0.126)	-0.364 (0.234)	-0.394* (0.202)	-0.400** (0.150)	-0.276** (0.091)	-0.275** (0.117)
Interactions		LR	SR	CR	PG	CA	SZ
ISL X FSV		0.018 (0.012)	-0.212** (0.091)	0.002 (0.004)	0.006 (0.005)	0.042 (0.035)	0.023 (0.020)
GHC X FSV		-0.003 (0.010)	-0.046 (0.091)	-0.005 (0.015)	0.071** (0.022)	0.031 (0.044)	0.009 (0.010)
ISL X GHC X FSV		0.023* (0.012)	0.361** (0.100)	-0.012 (0.041)	-0.060* (0.031)	-0.157* (0.081)	0.018 (0.028)
AR(1)	0.021	0.020	0.038	0.014	0.021	0.016	0.018
AR(2)	0.895	0.934	0.940	0.770	0.856	0.964	0.895
Hansen test	0.230	0.356	0.220	0.240	0.129	0.416	0.330
No of instruments	63	77	61	41	67	77	65
Number of groups	81	81	81	81	81	81	81

Note(s): Dependent variable is ROA. Estimations are based on two-step robust System GMM with Windmeijer (2005) finite-sample correction. Standard errors are in parentheses. *p<0.10, **p<0.05. All models include year dummies (not reported). FSV in interaction models refers to the specific firm-variable indicated in the column header (e.g., LR for Model 2). ISL represents the IDS dummy (1=Takaful). GHC is the pandemic dummy (1=2020-2022). AR(1) and AR(2) are p-values for Arellano-Bond tests for first- and second-order serial correlation in differenced residuals. Hansen test is the p-value for the test of overidentifying restrictions.

Source: Author's estimation.

4.4. Empirical Analysis

Table 6 presents the main results from the two-step robust SGMM estimations. Model 1 is the baseline model including all main effects. Models 2 through 7 introduce three-way interaction

terms between the Islamic specialization dummy (IDS), the global health crisis dummy (GHC), and one firm-specific variable (FSV) at a time, to explore differential effects during the pandemic based on the insurance model.

Other firm-level indicators exhibit mixed results. The solvency ratio (SR) shows a generally positive but statistically insignificant relationship with profitability, except where interaction terms complicate interpretation (e.g., in Model 3). This is somewhat in contrast with earlier findings by Tahira and Arshad (2014) and may reflect regulatory thresholds ensuring minimum solvency without necessarily boosting profit margins. The claims ratio (CR) is also statistically insignificant across all models, echoing the findings of Msomi (2023), which may indicate that effective reserving and reinsurance arrangements mitigate the immediate impact of claim fluctuations on profitability. Premium growth (PG) presents weak and inconsistent evidence of a relationship with profitability. It is mostly insignificant, though it reaches marginal significance in Model 3 and Model 7 with a positive sign. This partial alignment with Msomi and Nzama (2023) and contrast with Aouini and Abdennadher (2022) may suggest that while premium expansion reflects market activity, its benefits are offset if accompanied by higher expenses or loss ratios.

Regarding specialization and external shocks, the Takaful firm dummy (ISL) is largely insignificant in most models, with limited evidence of profitability differences between Takaful and conventional insurers once firm-specific controls are included. However, its positive coefficient in Model 3, albeit weakly significant, may hint at model-dependent variation. Finally, the COVID-19 pandemic dummy (GHC) is insignificant across all models, suggesting that the pandemic did not cause a statistically measurable decline in profitability for insurance firms in the region during 2020–2022. This may reflect institutional resilience, regulatory support, or rapid strategic adaptation among insurers during the crisis period.

These baseline results largely support Hypothesis 2 regarding the significance of certain firm-specific factors (LR, CA, SZ) and country-specific factors (EG), but provide less support for a direct impact of the business model (IDS) or the pandemic (GHC) on average profitability (partially contradicting Hypothesis 3 regarding the pandemic's impact).

4.4.1. Analysis of Interaction Effects

Models 2-7 explore whether the impact of firm-specific factors differs for Takaful firms, particularly during the pandemic. The significance of the three-way interaction term (ISL X GHC X FSV) indicates such differential effects. We discuss the interpretation based on marginal effects calculated from these models.

Interactions between GHC and ISL: **Table 7** shows the marginal effect of the pandemic (GHC=1 vs GHC=0) for conventional (ISL=0) and Islamic (ISL=1) firms, derived from a model specification similar to M2-M7 but focusing on the ISL X GHC interaction (results averaged across models for brevity).

Consistent with the insignificant GHC dummy in the main models, the marginal effects show that the pandemic period did not have a statistically significant average impact on profitability for either conventional or Islamic firms compared to the pre-pandemic period.

Interactions of Firm-Specific Variables with GHC and ISL: **Table 8** presents the marginal effects of key firm-specific variables on ROA, evaluated under different scenarios (insurance type and pandemic period). These are derived from Models 2-7 in **Table 6**.

The marginal effects analysis provides deeper insights into how firm-specific factors influence profitability under normal conditions and during the COVID-19 pandemic, revealing notable differences between conventional and Takaful insurance firms. Leverage (LR) demonstrates a contrasting

impact across the two models. For conventional insurers, higher leverage consistently reduces profitability, particularly during the pandemic, highlighting the financial fragility associated with higher debt exposure in times of crisis. Interestingly, for Takaful firms, higher leverage is associated with increased profitability during the pandemic, while showing no significant effect during normal periods. This suggests fundamental differences in capital structure dynamics and potentially in risk-sharing or risk management approaches between the two systems.

Table 7: Interaction (dummy with dummy)

	dy/dx	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
1.GHC					
Specialization ID=0	-0.003	0.007	-0.425	0.671	-0.016 , 0.011
Specialization ID=1	-0.006	0.007	-0.931	0.352	-0.020 , 0.007

Note(s): Marginal effects calculated post-estimation from SGMM models including ISL X GHC interaction. dy/dx represents the change in ROA associated with GHC=1 compared to GHC=0.

Source: Author's calculation based on [Table 6](#).

Table 8: Marginal Effect of 3-Way Interaction (continuous with 2 dummies)

	Leverage Ratio	Solvency Ratio	Claims Ratio	Premium Growth	Capital Adequacy	Size
ROA						
Specialization						
0	-0.017** (0.002)	0.198** (0.091)	-0.007 (0.016)	0.071** (0.023)	0.116** (0.042)	0.035** (0.013)
1	0.025** (0.008)	0.346** (0.059)	-0.017 (0.037)	0.017 (0.024)	0.001 (0.046)	0.075* (0.040)
Pandemic						
0	0.004 (0.006)	0.032 (0.026)	-0.000 (0.003)	0.007** (0.003)	0.126** (0.039)	0.048* (0.025)
1	0.025** (0.008)	0.346** (0.059)	-0.017 (0.037)	0.017 (0.024)	0.001 (0.046)	0.075* (0.040)
Specialization # Pandemic						
0 0	-0.014 (0.010)	0.244** (0.077)	-0.002 (0.003)	0.001 (0.003)	0.085** (0.016)	0.026** (0.011)
0 1	-0.017** (0.002)	0.198** (0.091)	-0.007 (0.016)	0.071** (0.023)	0.116** (0.042)	0.035** (0.013)
1 0	0.004 (0.006)	0.032 (0.026)	-0.000 (0.003)	0.007** (0.003)	0.126** (0.039)	0.048* (0.025)
1 1	0.025** (0.008)	0.346** (0.059)	-0.017 (0.037)	0.017 (0.024)	0.001 (0.046)	0.075* (0.040)

Note(s): Marginal effects (dy/dx) of FSV on ROA calculated post-estimation from SGMM Models 2-7 ([Table 4](#)). Standard errors in parentheses. *p<0.10, **p<0.05\$. Variable definitions in [Table 1](#).

Source: Source: Author's calculation.

Solvency Ratio (SR) exerts a generally positive effect on profitability for both types of firms, with the impact being more pronounced during the pandemic, especially for Takaful firms. This underscores the critical role of solvency buffers in maintaining performance under financial stress. On the other hand, the Claims Ratio (CR) continues to exhibit no significant marginal effect on profitability,

confirming earlier findings and suggesting that effective risk pooling or reinsurance may neutralize its impact.

The effects of Premium Growth (PG) also vary by model and period. For conventional firms, PG has a significant positive impact only during the pandemic, indicating that revenue expansion played a crucial role in cushioning profitability amid crisis conditions. Conversely, for Takaful firms, PG significantly enhances profitability only in normal times, perhaps reflecting the reliance on stable growth patterns in non-crisis settings.

Capital Adequacy (CA) is positively associated with profitability for conventional insurers across both periods, reaffirming the value of financial strength in sustaining performance. However, for Takaful firms, CA has a significant positive impact only in normal times, becoming insignificant during the pandemic. This shift may suggest that other structural or governance-related factors overshadowed capital adequacy's role in supporting Takaful performance during the crisis. Lastly, firm size (SZ) consistently contributes positively to profitability for both firm types in all periods, although the degree of statistical significance varies. This highlights the advantages of scale in the insurance sector, whether through operational efficiency, market reach, or diversified income streams.

These interaction results provide nuanced support for Hypotheses 2 and 3, revealing that the influence of firm-specific factors such as leverage, capital adequacy, and premium growth on profitability varies significantly across business models (Takaful vs. conventional) and economic conditions (normal periods vs. the pandemic). This aligns with Financial Slack Theory (Bourgeois, 1981), which posits that firms with stronger internal resources are better positioned to adapt to adverse conditions and sustain profitability. It also supports Organizational Resilience Theory (Lengnick-Hall, Beck, & Lengnick-Hall, 2011), which emphasizes that firms' internal capacities, routines, and adaptive flexibility are critical in responding to external shocks. The differentiated impact of these factors under varying scenarios confirms that resilience and performance are not only determined by structural characteristics but also by how firms utilize their resources under stress. Therefore, Hypotheses 2 and 3 are supported, as the empirical results validate the significance of both firm-specific and contextual variables in shaping profitability outcomes during turbulent times.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

While Takaful and conventional insurance aim to mitigate financial risks, they operate under fundamentally different principles and mechanisms, potentially leading to discrepancies in their financial performance metrics.

This study compares the performance of Islamic and conventional insurance companies in the GCC region, identifies key drivers, and assesses the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. Using the System GMM panel data estimator, it analyzes 85 companies (49 conventional and 36 Takaful) across six countries from 2013 to 2022.

The study undertook a three-pronged approach: comparing financial performance indicators, identifying key drivers, and assessing the global health crisis's impact.

The findings of this study reveal several distinct characteristics differentiating conventional and Takaful insurers in the GCC region. Conventional insurance firms consistently demonstrate higher return on assets (ROA), indicating greater profitability. However, this is accompanied by a heavier reliance on leverage, which may signal a comparatively riskier financial structure consistent with agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976), which suggests that such firms must carefully manage the trade-off between profit maximization and risk exposure. These firms also exhibit superior solvency

ratios, capital adequacy, and equity capital, reinforcing the view aligned with Financial Slack Theory (Bourgeois, 1981) that stronger internal financial buffers enhance the capacity to absorb losses and maintain operational stability during shocks.

Additionally, conventional insurers report higher claims ratios, a finding that warrants further investigation into claims management efficiency and potential risk underwriting practices. In terms of operational scale, conventional firms are significantly larger, suggesting they may benefit from economies of scale and broader market presence, advantages that align with prior research by Sahudin et al. (2022). Interestingly, no statistically significant difference was observed between Takaful and conventional firms in terms of premium growth, indicating similar expansion trends in underwriting activities. These insights contribute to the ongoing discourse on Islamic versus conventional finance by highlighting the structural and performance-related distinctions shaped by underlying business models and governance principles.

These findings suggest conventional insurers hold a financial advantage; further research could explore reasons behind these observations and identify improvement areas for Takaful firms.

A deeper investigation into the determinants of profitability revealed that several firm-specific factors exert varying effects depending on the insurance model and the economic context. Notably, leverage appears to benefit Takaful firms during economic downturns, while it significantly reduces profitability for conventional insurers, particularly under stress, highlighting differing capital structures and risk tolerance. Solvency emerged as a key determinant for both types of firms, with amplified importance for Takaful insurers during crisis periods, aligning with the resilience-based view that emphasizes strong internal buffers in shock absorption (Lengnick-Hall et al., 2011). The claims ratio exhibited a minimal impact on profitability regardless of economic conditions, suggesting that effective risk pooling and reinsurance mechanisms may neutralize its immediate financial effects. Meanwhile, premium growth proved advantageous for conventional insurers during crises, perhaps as a response strategy, whereas Takaful firms benefited more from growth during stable periods, underscoring different strategic postures. Capital adequacy significantly boosted profitability for conventional insurers in all periods, and for Takaful firms, particularly during stability, reinforcing the predictions of Financial Slack Theory (Bourgeois, 1981) on the protective role of internal financial cushions. Firm size consistently correlated with higher profitability across both models, suggesting that scale and diversification confer performance advantages.

Further insights from the two-step System GMM estimation confirm these dynamics. Economic growth was positively associated with profitability, while inflation had no statistically significant effect. Across all models, leverage negatively influenced profitability, and neither claims ratio nor premium growth showed consistent effects. In contrast, solvency ratio, capital adequacy, and firm size remained robust, significant predictors of profitability. These results collectively support the study's theoretical framing and underscore the importance of internal financial strength and structural efficiency for insurer resilience and performance in the GCC context.

Interaction analyses between internal factors and economic indicators highlight contrasting effects between conventional and Takaful insurers, emphasizing tailored strategies depending on economic climates.

The study also contributes to understanding insurance resilience during global crises like COVID-19. Despite unprecedented challenges, firms-maintained stability and profitability through effective risk and capital management.

The nuanced impact of factors such as leverage, solvency, claims ratio, premium growth, capital adequacy, and firm size suggests that while some factors consistently influence profitability, others

vary, highlighting the need for tailored, sector-specific strategies. Further research could refine risk management and adaptability strategies to better navigate future crises.

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the financial performance and resilience of Takaful and conventional insurance companies in the GCC. While conventional insurers currently have an edge, further research is needed to explore underlying reasons and identify opportunities for Takaful improvement, helping promote a more balanced and competitive insurance landscape in the region.

5.1. Implications and Contributions

This study provides important empirical and theoretical contributions to the discourse on Islamic and conventional insurance in the GCC region. Theoretically, the findings validate the relevance of Financial Slack Theory and Organizational Resilience Theory in understanding how insurance firms, differentiated by business models, respond to macroeconomic shocks such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The use of a panel data approach over a ten-year period enhances the robustness of this theoretical application. From a policy perspective, the results offer regulators and policymakers crucial insights into sector-specific financial characteristics. These insights can inform the design of tailored regulatory frameworks that account for the distinct financial structures and risk profiles of Takaful versus conventional insurers, particularly under economic distress. For instance, recognizing that Takaful firms respond differently to leverage and capital adequacy pressures can guide differentiated capital requirements or risk mitigation policies.

From a managerial point of view, insurance executives can leverage the results to refine strategic decisions related to capital structuring, growth strategies, and crisis readiness. The differentiated impact of firm-specific factors during normal and pandemic periods suggests that a one-size-fits-all financial strategy is suboptimal; rather, firms should adopt adaptive approaches that consider their institutional model and the prevailing economic context. Investors, likewise, benefit from understanding which models and financial factors offer resilience and sustained profitability, supporting more informed risk assessment and portfolio diversification strategies.

5.2. Limitations and Future Research

While this study offers important insights into the performance and resilience of insurance firms in the GCC region, it is important to recognize certain limitations. First, the analysis is based on a specific period and sample size, which may limit the generalizability of the findings beyond the selected firms and timeframe. Second, the study focuses primarily on financial indicators, leaving out important non-financial dimensions such as customer satisfaction, product innovation, and operational efficiency, which may also influence performance outcomes. Third, the research relies on a purely quantitative approach. Incorporating qualitative insights such as expert interviews, case studies, or managerial perspectives could enrich the understanding of strategic responses and firm behavior, especially during periods of crisis. Lastly, the study is geographically focused on the GCC region, which may limit its applicability to other markets with different economic structures or regulatory environments.

To address these gaps, future research could expand in several directions. One potential area is the integration of non-financial variables, such as corporate governance practices, technological adoption, or customer-centric strategies, to gain a more holistic view of firm performance. Cross-regional or cross-country comparative studies could also offer insights into how different regulatory settings shape the resilience of Takaful and conventional insurers. In addition, future studies may explore emerging themes such as digital transformation, climate risk, and demographic shifts, which are increasingly relevant to the insurance industry's long-term sustainability and growth.

Including qualitative research methods alongside quantitative models could further enhance the depth and practical relevance of future work in this area.

5.3. Policy Recommendations

Based on the nuanced insights gleaned from this research, several pivotal policy recommendations are proposed to nurture the growth and bolster the competitiveness of both conventional and Takaful insurance sectors:

1. Crafting regulatory frameworks to foster equitable competition and Takaful growth through incentives.
2. Establishing robust regulatory oversight to uphold Shariah principles and market stability.
3. Strategic interventions to bridge performance gaps in Takaful, addressing factors like capital adequacy and firm size.
4. Promoting innovation in product development and advancing financial inclusion to widen insurance access.

Collective implementation can bolster the insurance sectors across the GCC, benefiting consumers and strengthening economic resilience.

Declarations

The author has no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The data are available upon a reasonable request from the author.

REFERENCES

- Ab Rahim, R., Ahmed, A., & Baharuddin, N. N. (2021). Efficiency Performance of GCC Insurance Sector. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 11(5), 537-543.
- Ahmed, W. M. (2018). How do Islamic versus conventional equity markets react to political risk? Dynamic panel evidence. *International economics*, 156, 284-304.
- Akhter, W., Pappas, V., & Khan, S. U. (2017). A comparison of Islamic and conventional insurance demand: Worldwide evidence during the Global Financial Crisis. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 42, 1401-1412.
- Al-Mutairi, A., Naser, H., & Naser, K. (2021). Determinants of corporate performance: Empirical evidence from the insurance companies listed on Abu Dhabi securities exchange (ADX). *Accounting*, 7(1), 143-150.
- Alpen Capital (2024). GCC Insurance Industry Report. Retrieved March 15, 2024, from <https://alpen-capital.com/research/2024/alpen-capital-gcc-insurance-industry-report.pdf>
- Alshammari, A. A., Syed Jaafar Alhabshi, S. M., & Saiti, B. (2018). A comparative study of the historical and current development of the GCC insurance and takaful industry. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 9(2), 356-369.
- Alokla, J. M. (2018). The Determinants of Solvency and Profitability of Takaful Firms in the GCC and Malaysian Markets [PhD Thesis, University of Portsmouth]. https://researchportal.port.ac.uk/files/52022753/ALOKLA_Jassem_thesis..pdf
- Alshadadi, M. A., & Deshmukh, P. V. (2021). Determinants of the Profitability of Insurance Companies in Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Journal in Finance*, 5(11), 476-481.
- Ben Dhiab, L. (2021). Determinants of Insurance firms' profitability: an empirical study of Saudi insurance market. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(6), 235-243.
- Bourgeois III, L. J. (1981). On the measurement of organizational slack. *Academy of Management review*, 6(1), 29-39.
- Derbali, A. M. S. (2014). Determinants of performance of insurance companies in Tunisia: the case of life insurance. *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies*, 6(1), 90-96.
- Guendouz, A. A., & Ouassaf, S. (2018). Determinants of Saudi takaful insurance companies profitability. *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 22(5), 1-24.
- Hodori, A., & Masih, M. (2017). Determinants of profitability of takaful operators: new evidence from Malaysia based on dynamic GMM approach. *Munich Personal RePEc Archive*, 79441, 24.
- Hidayat, S. E., & Abdulla, A. M. (2015). A comparative analysis on the financial performance between takaful and conventional insurance companies in Bahrain during 2006-2011. *Journal of Islamic Economics, Banking and Finance*, 11(2), 149-163.
- Hemrit, W. (2020). Determinants driving Takaful and cooperative insurance financial performance in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Accounting & Organizational Change*, 16(1), 123-143.
- Hendricks, N. P., & Smith, A. (2015). Grouped coefficients to reduce bias in heterogeneous dynamic panel models with small T. *Applied Economics*, 47(40), 4335-4348.
- Islamic Financial Services Board. (2023). *Islamic Financial Services Industry Stability Report 2023* [Stability Report]. Retrieved from Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB)
- Lengnick-Hall, C. A., Beck, T. E., & Lengnick-Hall, M. L. (2011). Developing a capacity for organizational resilience through strategic human resource management. *Human resource management review*, 21(3), 243-255.
- Malahim, S. (2016). Analyzing the Financial Performance for Jordan Islamic Insurance Companies. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*. Ssrn.com. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3298129>
- Meckling, W. H., & Jensen, M. C. (1976). Theory of the Firm. Managerial behavior, agency costs and

- ownership structure, *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305-360.
- Morara, K., & Sibindi, A. B. (2021). Determinants of financial performance of insurance companies: Empirical evidence using Kenyan data. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14(12), 566.
- Msomi, T. S., & Nzama, S. (2023). Analyzing Firm-Specification Factors Affecting the Financial Performance of Insurance Companies in South Africa. *Insurance Markets and Companies*, 14(1), 8-21. [http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ins.14\(1\).2023.02](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ins.14(1).2023.02)
- Msomi, T. S. (2023). Macroeconomic and firm-specific determinants of financial performance: Evidence from non-life insurance companies in Africa. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(1), 2190312.
- Prakoso, D. (2021). Determinant Of Islamic Insurance Performance in Indonesia. *Islamic Social Finance*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.58968/isf.v1i1.116>
- Kantakji, M. H., Hamid, B. A., & Alhabshi, S. O. (2020). What drives the financial performance of general takaful companies? *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 11(6), 1301-1322.
- Sahudin, Z., Abdullah, H., Rahim, H. A., Bahrudin, N. Z., & Pardi, F. (2022). Determinants of Takaful Performance in Malaysia. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Business and Economics*, 10(2S2), 1-17.
- Vojinović, Ž., Milutinović, S., Sertić, D., & Leković, B. (2022). Determinants of sustainable profitability of the Serbian insurance industry: Panel data investigation. *Sustainability*, 14(9), 5190.
- Windmeijer, F. (2005). A finite sample correction for the variance of linear efficient two-step GMM estimators. *Journal of econometrics*, 126(1), 25-51.

Structuring Islamic Financial Literacy Construct to Measure Islamic Banking Products Adoption in Uganda: Content Validation of the Survey Instrument

Yusuf Kaweesa^{1*} & Romzie Rosman¹

¹IIUM, Institute of Islamic Banking and Finance/International Islamic University Malaysia, Malaysia

*Email: yusuf.kaweesa@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Islamic banking in Uganda was introduced in 2016. However, Islamic microfinance Institutions started operations immediately as they are differently regulated by the Uganda Microfinance Regulatory Authority (UMRA) under the Tier 4 regulatory Act. So, this study aims to structure and conduct content validation of a survey questionnaire of the Islamic financial literacy construct for the adoption of Islamic banking products among Muslims in Uganda. Methodologically, this study was executed in five stages. Firstly, the content validation form was prepared detailing the items to be validated and their sources. Secondly, a review panel of experts was selected based on their expertise in Islamic banking adoption and Islamic financial literacy, and 6 experts were considered. Then, an online content validation form with clear instructions was sent to experts to critically review the domains and items before scoring them to improve relevance. The results showed that an S-CVI score of 0.864 was attained by the tool and thus relevant to be used for the study. The CVI for Islamic financial literacy was between 0.83-1, and thus, all items were relevant to assess the Islamic financial literacy concept of the Muslims in Uganda. Thus, this tool can be a reference for researchers who intend to conduct research on Islamic financial literacy and other factors of Islamic banking adoption in jurisdictions that have just embraced the Islamic financial system.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received: May 19, 2025

Accepted: June 5, 2025

Published: June 30, 2025

KEYWORDS

Islamic financial literacy; Content Validation; Islamic Banking Products Adoption;

JEL CODES

C83; G21; G53; Z12;

HOW TO CITE

Kaweesa, Y. & Rosman, R. (2025). Structuring Islamic Financial Literacy Construct to Measure Islamic Banking Products Adoption in Uganda: Content Validation of the Survey Instrument. *Journal of Economics, Law and Society*, 2(1), 73-83. <https://doi.org/10.70009/jels.2025.2.1.4>

1. INTRODUCTION

The main objective of the empirical research method of the quantitative research methodology is to find the importance or impact, or influence of a phenomenon or problem (Ozair et al, 2017). The empirical research method effectively facilitates conducting research in social sciences, business management, and health sciences. However, the empirical research method has a complex systematic procedure of developing and testing hypotheses, where researchers can eventually examine and improve a model to explain a real-world phenomenon. Besides, research as a concept is a process intended to investigate answers to a question scientifically and systematically (Aithal & Aithal, 2020). This process involves forming hypotheses, testing hypotheses through data collection on relevant constructs, analyzing and systematically interpreting results, and reaching conclusions as generalized solutions. Overall, the desire to get familiar with a phenomenon, find out the association or interdependence of activities, and identify the characteristics of an individual or a group of activities, their relationships, or their frequencies of occurrences is the main objective of scholarly research.

Therefore, based on varied objectives, research is classified as explanatory research, experimental research, empirical research, conclusive research, descriptive research, and causal research.

Besides, empirical research is synonymous with social sciences, business management, and clinical research, where a questionnaire based on the survey method is widely used to collect data mainly from consumers, customers, and patients (Taherdoost, 2016). Moreover, with this regard, a systematic questionnaire should be constructed or follow a pre-existing questionnaire with the standard format from the available literature references. However, it is tasking to design and develop an effective, efficient, and psychometrically ideal questionnaire for data collection in empirical research. Questionnaire design and development in survey-based empirical research is a process that includes various components, specifically questionnaire preparation, preliminary questionnaire testing, and validation (validity and reliability) using several statistical methods (Taherdoost, 2016). Thus, the main objective of a questionnaire in research is to obtain relevant information most reliably and validly (Taherdoost, 2016).

However, questionnaire validation is in four major types: face validation, content validation, construct validation, and criterion validation (Ozair et al, 2017). The face, criterion, and construct validation can be ascertained based on the researcher's subjective analysis. Whereas content validation is only ascertained statistically, making it more worthy to carry out and whose results are more reliable (Lau et al, 2018). Questionnaire validity determines whether it means what it is intended to measure and how well it explains the collected data to cover the actual area of investigation. It is a complex process, as many factors can affect the dependability of a questionnaire. However, this study is focused on questionnaire validation as a key component in questionnaire designing and development through the content validation process using the method of content validity. Indeed, the validity test of a survey questionnaire is a process of analyzing the survey questions for their dependability (Aithal & Aithal, 2020; Taherdoost, 2016). Under the content validation process, content validity is a major component to ensure a questionnaire's overall validity by providing systematic evidence that supports the validity of an assessment tool (Yusoff, 2019).

Content validation is a process of examining the contents of the items questionnaire to check whether they represent the entire theoretical construct of the designed model of the problem under consideration (Nievas Soriano et al, 2020). The results of the content validation process are realized content validity methodology, which is the extent a measurement tool like a questionnaire represents the measured constructs to be analyzed in the study (Yusoff, 2019). Thus, the objective of the content validity method is to enable researchers to ascertain that the survey instrument includes only the essential and relevant items for the study and to exclude the undesirable ones (Yusoff, 2019). The essentiality and relevance can be ascertained by calculating the content validity ratio (CVR) and the content validity index (CVI) of the items, respectively, of the content validity method.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to ascertain the relevance of items of a survey questionnaire aimed at analyzing the factors that influence the adoption of Islamic banking products in Uganda among the minority Muslim population. The Islamic financial literacy variable will moderate the relationship between other variables (religiosity, attitude, consumer expectancy, legitimacy of Islamic banking, and awareness) and the actual adoption of Islamic banking products. The content validation process was undertaken by engaging the panel of experts to rate the relevance of the entire assessment tool to ascertain the appropriateness of its elements for the targeted constructs (domains). The rest of the study is organized in the form of a literature review, methodology, results and findings, and conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Studies on Islamic Banking Adoption

Studies on the adoption of Islamic banking have been widely carried out in different jurisdictions for a while, portraying a range of results. However, their focus is on providing empirical evidence for

varied research questions and not on developing research tools. For example, Aziz et al (2018) examined the behavioural intention to adopt Islamic banking in Pakistan. The results showed that behavioural, normative, and control beliefs were significant determinants of Islamic banking adoption in Pakistan. Whereas, in Tunisia, Obeid & Kaabachi (2016) identified religious commitment, the amount of information held by customers about Islamic finance, and the relative advantage of Islamic banking as responsible for adoption. Additionally, Islamic banking compatibility with consumer values, lifestyles, and banking habits were predictors of its adoption. The study sought to identify the main factors influencing the adoption of Islamic banking by conventional customers in Tunisia. Relatedly, the understanding of Islamic banking concepts and perceived advantage significantly influenced the adoption of Islamic banking services in Malaysia (Mahdzan et al, 2017). These, among other studies on adoption, have focused on factors affecting the adoption of Islamic banking and not on developing standardised tools to study adoption in different jurisdictions.

Besides, exploring key factors that influence the adoption of Islamic banking products is crucial (Mahdzan et al, 2017). Thus, Islamic financial literacy and other factors are considered in context with Uganda, a secular country, and specifically considering the minority Muslim community. Moreover, Muslims readily patronized Islamic finance considering their religious beliefs (Kawaase & Nalukwago, 2017). The Islamic financial literacy variable in this context is treated as a pivotal variable influencing the adoption of Islamic banking products and a moderator between other variables (independent variables) and the actual adoption of Islamic banking products (Dependent variable). The Islamic financial literacy variable relates to an understanding of the culture and fundamental terminologies of Islamic banking and how they are understood compared to conventional banking.

The Technology Acceptance Model theory helps in underpinning the adoption of new products in respective jurisdictions (Noor, 2024). Thus, the adoption of Islamic banking products by Ugandan minority Muslims can be explored under the TAM theory. It can be perceived that higher Islamic financial literacy levels among the Ugandan Muslims can influence their perceived usefulness and ease of use. Therefore, people with better Islamic financial literacy standards might find Islamic banking products more useful and easier to adopt because they have a deeper understanding of their benefits. Indeed, perceived usefulness is a key determinant of behavioural intention to adopt a technology. So, given the deeper awareness and understanding resulting from Islamic financial literacy, it is perceived that product users get to objectively realize the benefits of Islamic banking and finance principles. So, they develop a positive perception of the usefulness of banking products, aligning them with their religious values to meet their financial needs.

Therefore, this study developed a specialised tool for the collection of information from respondents concerning the adoption of Islamic banking products by Muslims in Uganda. However, it is appropriate to examine the context of Uganda's journey towards the adoption of Islamic banking. This would help to contextualize the rationale for the development of the survey tool developed to study the adoption concept in Uganda.

2.2. Background of Islamic Banking Adoption in Uganda

Islamic banking in Uganda was legalized in 2016 after the passing of the Financial Institutions Amendment Act 2004 (FIA 2004). The process took a period of 23 years, pioneered by prominent Muslims like the late Dr. Sulaiman Kiggundu, who was the governor of the Bank of Uganda (1990-1998) (Lujja et al, 2016a). However, the initial submission for a formal request for a commercial license to operate as an Islamic bank was submitted to BOU in 2008 (Mutebile, 2016). Indeed, given the efforts of Muslims in the country, such formal requests, and that Uganda is a member of the OIC, the Central Bank engaged in efforts to have Islamic banking and finance formalized and legalized in Uganda (Mutebile, 2016). The Bank of Uganda engaged different stakeholder institutions in the

Ugandan economic system to discuss the possibilities of having Islamic banking legalized. Thus, to this effect, in 2009, the Bank of Uganda engaged regulators (the Insurance Commission, the Capital Markets Authority, and the Uganda Revenue Authority) in the financial sectors in an in-house training about Islamic banking and finance (Mutebile, 2016).

However, the results of such engagement led to the Bank of Uganda (BoU) proposing amendments to the Financial Institutions Act (2004), which were later approved by the Ugandan Parliament in 2016. This led to the Financial Institutions Act 2016 legalizing Islamic banking and finance in Uganda (Lujja et al, 2016b). Besides, the full details regarding the practical operationalization of Islamic commercial banks were laid down later in 2018 under the Statutory Instruments Supplement No. 2, 2018. This detailed Institutions' formation of key structures, like the Shariah Advisory Council (SAC), to monitor compliance. The Central Bank was also obliged to institute a central SAC before licensing any Islamic commercial bank. However, such a mandate was specific to financial institutions that were regulated by the Bank of Uganda (Tier 1, 2, and 3 financial institutions) and did not accommodate the Tier 4 Islamic Microfinance institutions and Islamic savings and credit cooperatives (Saccos). These are regulated by the Uganda Microfinance Regulatory Authority (UMRA) under the Tier 4 Microfinance Institutions Act and Money Lenders Act (2016). The Tier 4 financial institutions started operations right after legalizing Islamic banking in 2016. Moreover, several of them were opened, especially around the Kampala Metropolitan business region, introducing Muslims to Islamic banking concepts, as most of them were operated by Muslims and encouraged fellow Muslims to embrace them.

Moreover, Islamic microfinance institutions and Islamic Saccos that became operational included Hijaz Finance, Nakasero Muslim Sacco, Amana Muslim Sacco, and Muhelia Islamic Banking Co-operative Society. Others were the Uganda Islamic Sacco, One Ummah Sacco, Halal Finance Sacco, WIG Sacco, and Masaka Muslim Sacco. However, the Islamic commercial banks got licensed by 2023, after the amendment of the Financial Institutions Act, 2016 by the Ugandan parliament in 2023. The amendment repealed the clause that required the formation of a Central Shariah Advisory Council (SAC) by the Bank of Uganda before issuing an operational license. This condition had limited the licensing role of the Central Bank, as there were no experts to constitute the Central SAC in Uganda. However, the amendment eventually led to the licensing of Salaam Bank Uganda in 2023. Therefore, against that background, Islamic banking is still a recent industry in Uganda. It requires specially developed tools to study the adoption concept among the population, especially in trying to understand the effect of Islamic financial literacy on the adoption process of products. Thus, content validation of the questionnaire for the adoption of Islamic banking products in Uganda underscores the minority Muslim population (Lujja et al, 2016a). Besides, Lujja et al (2018) had indicated that Muslims were more knowledgeable about Islamic banking than Christians when they compared the two groups in their study that aimed at exploring the perception of Ugandans towards Islamic banking.

2.3. Content Validation

The literature on content validation of questionnaires has not been specific to the adoption of Islamic banking, as in health research (Nievas Soriano, 2020). Indeed, studies specific to Islamic banking adoption, like Lujja et al (2016a), analyzed the feasibility of the existing Ugandan laws to adopt the Islamic banking system qualitatively, and the recommendation was to benchmark the Malaysian regulations on the Islamic banking system. In another quantitative study, Lujja et al (2016b) indicated that attitude influenced public intention to adopt Islamic banking in Uganda. Besides, results showed that Muslims were more inclined to Islamic banking due to religiosity and profitability despite their low awareness of Islamic banking terminologies. Besides, (Bananuka et al, 2020) indicated significant differences between religions where Muslims were more ready for Islamic financing than Christians in establishing whether there was a relationship between religiosity,

religious preferences, firm age, and intention to adopt Islamic financing in an emerging economy like Uganda which is a secular state and adopting Islamic financing for the first time. Moreover, in most of these studies, none is aimed at ascertaining the content validation of the questionnaires used, and thus, this study tries to bridge this literature gap.

3. METHODOLOGY

The questionnaire items were adopted from earlier studies that addressed similar domains regarding the adoption of Islamic banking in different jurisdictions (Bananuka et al, 2019; Hoque et al, Mahdzan et al, 2017). The Islamic financial literacy (IFL) items were adopted from studies (Albaity & Rahman, 2019; Pala et al, 2023; and Dinc et al, 2023). Such items were selected on the basis that they covered the aspects of financial knowledge, financial attitude, and financial behavior or skill (Nawi et al, 2022; Dinc et al, 2021). Thus, 15 items were carefully considered underpinning the IFL description (financial knowledge, attitude, and skill), reflecting an early adopting jurisdiction of the Islamic banking industry (Dinc et al, 2021). These items are summarized in *Table 1* below:

Table 1: Summary of selected IFL items for Content Validation

No	Selected Items
1	Islamic method of finance is interest-free
2	Gharar refers to uncertainty & deception and is not allowable in Islam.
3	Preservation of wealth is one of the objectives of the Islamic law (Shariah).
4	It is allowable to sell a commodity before it comes under our control.
5	An Islamic bank may invest with you according to the profit and loss sharing method (Mudarabah).
6	Buying shares on a short-term price fluctuation is not speculation.
7	Islamic banks provide Lease financing (Ijarah).
8	Islamic banks provide manufacturing sale (al - Istithna).
9	Islamic banks provide financing under a method called Murabaha.
10	Islamic banking may provide benevolent loans called Qard Hassan.
11	In Mudarabah, the capital provider is the only party that bears the losses unless a loss happens due to the negligence of Mudharib.
12	In Ijarah the asset is usually not returned to the lessor (owner).
13	Preservation of wealth is one of the objectives of Islamic finance.
14	For Istithna' to be valid, the price must be fixed from the beginning.
15	In Qard Hassan, the borrower is required only to repay the original amount of the loan.

Source: Authors' own.

However, the whole questionnaire contained 48 items in 7 domains and was organized into 3 sections: demography, Islamic financial literacy, and other variables. The methodological content validity was carried out on the questionnaire to ascertain whether its items were relevant to the respective domains. Additionally, this was deduced by scores of experts using the relevance rating scale of 4 by the experts in the Islamic banking field. The content validation process of the relevance of the questionnaire was carried out by 6 experts from Uganda and Malaysia.

The content validation process was executed following the six-step procedure developed by Yusoff (2019). Moreover, they include preparing the content validation form, selecting a panel of experts, conducting content validation, reviewing domains and items, providing scores on each item by experts, and calculating the Content Validity Index (CVI). Therefore, the prepared content validation form was clear with definitions of domains to enable experts to easily comprehend and execute the review task well (Yusoff, 2019) by adopting a range of 6 and not exceeding 10 experts. *Table 2* below shows threshold guidance on the acceptable CVI values related to identifying the number of experts used to validate the content of items of the study questionnaire.

However, considering the factors of time, cost, and response rate, content validation was conducted through a face-to-face approach where the content validity forms were sent to experts via online means. A systematic follow-up by the researchers was undertaken to improve the response rate and consider time as well.

Table 2: The number of experts and their implication on the acceptable cut-off score of CVI

Number of experts	Acceptable CVI values	Source of recommendation
Two experts	At least 0.80	Davis, (1992)
Three to five experts	Should be 1	Polit et al, (2007)
At least six experts	At least 0.83	Polit et al, (2007)
Six to eight experts	At least 0.83	Lynn, (1986)
At least nine experts	At least 0.78	Lynn, (1986)

Source: Adapted from Yusoff (2019).

Besides, domains and items were to be critically reviewed by the experts before scoring them, respectively, and to provide comments to improve the relevance of the items to the targeted domains. Indeed, 10 experts were given the content validation from items, and only 6 were able to execute the task, as the others never responded at all despite the follow-up. These provided constructive comments that were considered to refine the items and domains to align well with the objectives of the study. Moreover, considering the experts' scores for the items, the researchers calculated the items' CVI to ascertain their relevance to the domains as opposed to the items' CVR, which is aimed at establishing their essentiality. The I-CVI calculations were done using the Excel spreadsheet tabulation format as designed by the researchers, following a step-by-step methodology as elaborated in (Yusoff, 2019). Moreover, the scale's content validity was established using the formula $S-CVI/Ave$. **Table 3** summarizes the CVI indices, CVI indices descriptions and formulae used to calculate the content validity index of items to ascertain their relevance.

Table 3: The definition and formula of I-CVI and S-CVI/Ave

The CVI Indices.	Definition	Formula
I-CVI (Item-level content validity index)	The proportion of content experts giving an item a relevance rating of 3 or 4.	$I-CVI = (\text{agreed item}) / (\text{number of experts})$.
S-CVI/Ave (Scale-level content validity index based on the average method)	The average of the I-CVI scores for all items on the scale or the average of proportion relevance judged by all experts. The proportion relevant is the average relevance rating by individual experts.	$S-CVI/Ave = (\text{sum of I-CVI scores}) / (\text{number of items})$. $S-CVI/Ave = (\text{sum of proportion relevance rating}) / (\text{number of experts})$.

Source: Adapted from Yusoff (2019).

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In this study, 7 domains or factors and 48 items were adopted from previous studies (Antara et al, 2016; Albaity & Rahman, 2019; Pala et al, 2023; and Bananuka et al, 2019). These were deemed fit for the objectives of the study about structuring the Islamic financial literacy construct to analyze its influence on the adoption of Islamic banking products in Uganda. Content validation on the instrument developed for the study, using 6 experts, was done, and the tool was found to have satisfactory content evidence (Scale-level content validity index by Average) above the threshold of 0.83 as required for 6 experts (Hadie et al, 2017). The calculated Scale level content validity index based on the average method was executed utilizing 2 formulae where $S-CVI/Ave = (\text{Sum of I-CVI scores} / \text{Number of items})$ and $S-CVI/Ave = (\text{Sum of proportion relevance rating} / \text{Number of experts})$. The results were 0.867 and 0.864, respectively, above the threshold of 0.83 as required. Besides, the I-CVI

values of most items in varied domains were more than 0.83, except for 6 items below the threshold, which were amended accordingly (Ozair et al, 2017).

Thus, all the other 42 items developed under respective domains were valid to assess the study on the relationship between Islamic financial literacy and factors influencing the adoption of Islamic banking products among Muslims in Uganda. Indeed, their results showed an overall item-level content validity index in the range of 0.83 – 1, which is acceptable for the tool subjected to 6 experts. Generally, the tool was proven to have good psychometric properties. It thus could be used to measure and ascertain responses for the study on Factors influencing the adoption of Islamic banking in Uganda, as per the study's objectives.

Besides, all the experts recommended that several items in the tool were feasible enough for the study. However, they made some recommendations to help make the whole instrument better and more fitting to elicit the required responses. They noted that some domains, like consumer expectancy, attitude, and awareness, were represented by a few items, as IFL had 15 items. Thus, they recommended between 6 and 8 items for the domains. They rationalized that fewer items for respective domains would constrain the researchers' data analysis process. Moreover, many items would lead to respondents' fatigue during questionnaire answering. experts realized several grammatical mistakes within the items, for which researchers responded by rectifying them. Additionally, they recommended that the Arabic terms in the questionnaire, like Murabaha, Istithna, Ijara, Gharar, and Maysir, should be definitively expressed in English to make it easy for the respondents to understand the concepts and provide genuine responses. The experts rationalized that Uganda is a secular country and, as an early adopter, could not have a population so familiar with such terms even within the minority Muslim community.

Table 4: Content Validity Index Calculation for Islamic Financial Literacy.

Expert / Item	Expert 1	Expert 2	Expert 3	Expert 4	Expert 5	Expert 6	Experts in agreement	I-CVI
IFL 1	1	1	1	1	1	1	6	1
IFL 2	1	1	1	1	1	0	5	0.83
IFL 3	1	1	1	1	0	1	5	0.83
IFL 4	1	1	1	1	0	1	6	1
IFL 5	1	1	1	1	1	1	6	1
IFL 6	1	1	1	1	1	1	6	1
IFL 7	1	1	1	1	1	0	5	0.83
IFL 8	1	1	1	1	1	1	6	1
IFL 9	1	1	1	1	1	0	5	0.83
IFL 10	1	1	1	1	1	1	6	1
IFL 11	1	1	1	1	0	1	5	0.83
IFL 12	1	1	1	1	0	1	5	0.83
IFL 13	1	1	1	1	1	0	5	0.83
IFL 14	1	1	1	1	1	1	6	1
IFL 15	1	1	1	1	1	1	6	1
Proportion Relevance	1	1	1	1	0.733	0.733		

Source: Developed by the Authors.

However, the survey is more focused on the Islamic financial literacy variable as it is intended to explore it in three dimensions. Indeed, the Islamic financial literacy level among Muslims will be measured. Additionally, IFL was to be investigated as a factor influencing the adoption of Islamic banking products in Uganda, and as a moderator between other factors influencing adoption (IVs) and the actual adoption of Islamic banking products among Muslims (DV). Therefore, in this study,

the Islamic financial literacy variable results are extensively reported to suit their role in the general survey. Indeed, the content validity index of the Islamic financial literacy items was determined to be between the range 0.83-1, indicating their good relevance to be used to assess the three concepts in the general survey as expressed in [Table 4](#).

Specifically, the average proportion of relevance of Islamic financial literacy items judged by the 6 experts using S-CVI/Ave (Sum of proportion relevance rating/Number of items) was (5.466/6) 0.911, above the required threshold of 0.83. Besides, only 9 items were amended and maintained for the final inclusion in the questionnaire as recommended by the experts and reflecting the items' ability to elicit desired information about Islamic financial literacy from the respondents. However, Lujja et al (2018) assert that Islamic banking is recent in Uganda, and Ugandans have hardly developed an Islamic financial attitude and skill. Therefore, the 9 items retained tested the description of the financial knowledge component in the Islamic financial literacy variable (Dinc et al, 2021). These items are shown in [Table 5](#) below:

Table 5: Islamic financial literacy maintained items

No	Maintained Items
1.	Islamic method of finance is interest-free.
2.	Gharar refers to uncertainty & deception and is not allowable in Islam.
3.	An Islamic bank may invest with you using the profit and loss sharing method (<i>Mudarabah</i>).
4.	Islamic banks provide Lease banking (<i>Ijarah</i>).
5.	Islamic banks provide manufacturing sales (<i>Istisna'</i>).
6.	Islamic banks provide financing under a method called cost-plus (<i>Murabahah</i>).
7.	Islamic banking may provide benevolent loans called <i>Qard Hasan</i> .
8.	According to the profit and loss sharing method (<i>Mudarabah</i>), the capital provider is the only party that bears the losses unless the loss happens due to the negligence of the entrepreneur (<i>Mudharib</i>).
9.	In <i>Ijarah</i> the asset is usually not returned to the lessor (owner).

Source: Authors' own.

Indeed, the maintained Islamic financial literacy items are suitably relevant to explore the variable as required in the survey to measure the level of Islamic financial literacy in Uganda. Additionally, studied as a factor for the adoption of Islamic banking products, and as a moderator for the study, given the good CVI score results. Thus, 6 items relating to the financial attitude and skill were removed from the list and are summarized in [Table 6](#) below:

Table 6: Summary of IFL removed items

No	Removed Islamic financial literacy Items
1	Preservation of wealth is one of the objectives of Islamic finance.
2	In <i>Qard Hasan</i> , the borrower is required only to repay the original amount of the loan.
3	For <i>Istisna'</i> to be valid, the price must be fixed from the beginning.
4	It is allowable to sell a commodity before it comes under our control.
5	Preservation of wealth is one of the objectives of the Islamic law (<i>Shari'ah</i>).
6	Buying shares on a short-term price fluctuation is not speculation.

Source: Authors' own.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Several scholars assert that it is vital to establish content validity to establish the construct validity of a measure (Rossiter, 2008; Yusoff, 2019). Therefore, this article describes the content validation process of a tool intended to assess the relationship between Islamic financial literacy and other factors of the adoption of Islamic banking products among Muslims in Uganda. Additionally, the

article highlights the structuring process of the Islamic financial literacy construct, assembling relevant items fit for a secular state like Uganda. Content validation of tools is more evidenced in health-related studies (Lau et al, 2017; Rossiter, 2008), unlike in management and social sciences-related studies like Islamic banking adoption. Besides, efforts made by Dinc et al (2023) were instrumental in standardizing a universal set of items specifically meant to measure Islamic financial literacy across jurisdictions that had adopted Islamic banking. However, such items were studied in countries like Oman, UAE, Turkey, and Saudi Arabia, among others, that had taken a bigger economic step in the Islamic banking sector. Indeed, developing jurisdictions like Uganda, which are recent adopters as well, could hardly be accommodated by the standard of these items. Thus, such items were adapted and modified through the content validation process to fit the reality of the Ugandan context.

Besides, content validation of the tool as a prerequisite for data collection was worth carrying out to standardize the tool to be put in use (Ozair et al, 2017). As a result, 6 items of the IFL variable were removed. Several other items for other variables were amended to suit the objectives of the study. Moreover, findings further indicated that between 6-8 items for a respective construct are suitable to assess the respondents' perception of the construct and, in the same way, minimize their bias from questionnaire fatigue. Indeed, this article provided a systematic and evidence-based procedure for a tool designed to adopt Islamic banking in a minority Muslim community, vastly exploring the role of the Islamic financial literacy variable.

The overall results from the I-CVI and S-CVI are above 0.83 for the 6 experts, indicating that the tool is generally relevant for the study. Indeed, the questionnaire can be a reference tool for studies aimed at assessing the adoption of Islamic banking in developing countries, such as secular countries where Muslims are the minority, and recent adopters of the Islamic banking system, like Uganda. However, collaboration efforts should be initiated toward developing a standardized universal tool for measuring factors influencing the adoption of Islamic banking or Islamic banking products and services suitable for all countries embracing the Islamic financial system.

Declarations

The author has no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The data are available upon a reasonable request from the author.

REFERENCES

- Aithal, A. & Aithal, P. S. (2020). Development and validation of survey questionnaire & experimental data—a systematical review-based statistical approach. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 5(2), 233-251.
- Albaity, M and Rahman, M. (2019). The intention to use Islamic banking: an exploratory study to measure Islamic financial literacy. *International Journal of Emerging Markets* 14(5), 988-1012 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOEM-05-2018-0218>.
- Antara, P. M., Musa, R., & Hassan, F. (2016). Theorizing attitude towards Islamic financing adoption in an integrative model of behavioral prediction: A proposed conceptual framework. *Journal of Administrative and Business Studies*, 1(1), 35-41.
- Antara, P. M., Musa, R., & Hassan, F. (2017). Conceptualization and operationalization of Islamic financial literacy scale. *Pertanika Journals*, 25, 251-260.
- Aziz, S., Afaq, Z., & Bashir, U. (2018). Behavioral intention to adopt Islamic banking in Pakistan: a study based on the theory of planned behavior. *Journal of Islamic Business and Management*, 8(2), 387-404. <https://doi.org/10.26501/jibm/2018.0802.007>
- Bananuka, J., Kaawaase, T. K., Kasera, M., & Nalukenge, I. (2019). Determinants of the intention to adopt Islamic banking in a non-Islamic developing country: The case of Uganda. *ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance*, 11(2), 166-186.
- Bananuka, J., Mukyala, V., Tumwebaze, Z., Ssekakubo, J., Kasera, M., & Najjuma, M. S. (2020). The intention to adopt Islamic financing in emerging economies: evidence from Uganda. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 11(3), 610-628.
- Dinc, Y., Çetin, M., Bulut, M., & Jahangir, R. (2021). Islamic financial literacy scale: an amendment in the sphere of contemporary financial literacy. *ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance*, 13(2), 251-263.
- Hadie, S. N. H., Hassan, A., Ismail, Z. I. M., Asari, M. A., Khan, A. A., Kasim, F. & Yusoff, M. S. B. (2017). Anatomy education environment measurement inventory: A valid tool to measure the anatomy learning environment. *Anatomical sciences education*, 10(5), 423-432
- Hoque, M. E., Nik Hashim, N. M. H., & Azmi, M. H. B. (2018). Moderating effects of marketing communication and financial consideration on customer attitude and intention to purchase Islamic banking products: A conceptual framework. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 9(4), 799-822.
- Hoque, M. N., Rahman, M. K., Said, J., Begum, F., & Hossain, M. M. (2022). What factors influence customer attitudes and mindsets towards the use of services and products of Islamic Banks in Bangladesh? *Sustainability*, 14(8), 4703.
- Kaabachi, S., & Obeid, H. (2016). Determinants of Islamic banking adoption in Tunisia: empirical analysis. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 34(7), 1069-1091.
- Kaawaase, T. K., & Nalukwago, L. (2017). Religiosity and Islamic banking in Uganda. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 8(2), 190-210. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIABR-07-2015-0031>
- Lau, A. S., Yusoff, M. S., Lee, Y. Y., Choi, S. B., Xiao, J. Z., & Liang, M. T. (2018). Development and validation of a Chinese translated questionnaire: A single simultaneous tool for assessing gastrointestinal and upper respiratory tract related illnesses in pre-school children. *Journal of Taibah University medical sciences*, 13(2), 135-141.
- Lujja, S., Mohammad, M. O., Hassan, R. B., & Oseni, U. A. (2016a). The feasibility of adopting Islamic Banking system under the existing laws in Uganda. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 9(3), 417-434.
- Lujja, S., Mohammed, M. O., & Hassan, R. (2018). Islamic banking: an exploratory study of public perception in Uganda. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 9(3), 336-352.

- Lujja, S., Omar Mohammad, M., & Hassan, R. (2016b). Modelling public behavioral intention to adopt Islamic banking in Uganda: the theory of reasoned action. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 9(4), 583-600.
- Mahdzan, N. S., Zainudin, R., & Au, S. F. (2017). The adoption of Islamic banking services in Malaysia. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 8(3), 496-512.
- Marzuki, M. F. M., Yaacob, N. A., & Yaacob, N. M. (2018). Translation, cross-cultural adaptation, and validation of the Malay version of the system usability scale questionnaire for the assessment of mobile apps. *JMIR human factors*, 5(2), e10308.
- Muslichah, I. & Sanusi, S. (2019). The effect of religiosity and financial literacy on intention to use Islamic banking products. *Asian Journal of Islamic Management*, 1(2), 85-92.
- Mutebile .E.T, (2016, March), Keynote Speech by the Governor at the Islamic Banking Conference – Hotel Africana Kampala, <https://www.bou.or.ug/bouwebsite/bouwebsitecontent/MediaCenter/GovernorSection/speeches/GovernorsSpeeches/2016/May/ISLAMIC-BANKING-CONF-HOTEL-AFRICANA-13-MAY-2016.pdf>
- Nawi, F. A. M., Aziz, M. R. A., & Shahwan, S. (2022). Conceptualizing and Operationalizing Islamic Financial Literacy: A Multidimensional Framework. *Advanced International Journal of Banking, Accounting, and Finance*, 4(11), 12- 29.
- Nievas Soriano, B. J., García Duarte, S., Fernández Alonso, A. M., Bonillo Perales, A., & Parrón Carreño, T. (2020). Validation of a questionnaire developed to evaluate a pediatric ehealth website for parents. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(8), 2671.
- Noor, N. (2024). Technology acceptance model in halal industries: a systematic literature review and research agenda. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 15(11), 3156-3173. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-02-2024-0077>
- Ozair, M. M., Baharuddin, K. A., Mohamed, S. A., Esa, W., & Yusoff, M. S. B. (2017). Development and Validation of the Knowledge and Clinical Reasoning of Acute Asthma Management in Emergency Department (K-CRAMED). *Education in Medicine Journal*, 9(2), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.21315/eimj2017.9.2.2>
- Pala, F., Erdoğan, A., Ali, M., Alnori, F. and Barut, A. (2024). Analyzing the linkage between Islamic financial literacy and Islamic banking services adoption: evidence from Turkey. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, (ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIABR-12-2021-0324>
- Rossiter, J. R. (2008). Content validity of measures of abstract constructs in management and organizational research. *British Journal of Management*, 19(4), 380-388.
- Taherdoost, H. (2016). Validity and reliability of the research instrument; how to test the validation of a questionnaire/survey in a research. SSRN Electronic Journal. Retrieved August 10, 2016, from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3205040>.
- Yusoff, M. S. B. (2019). ABC of content validation and content validity index calculation. *Education in Medicine Journal*, 11(2), 49-54.
- Davis, L. L. (1992). Instrument review: getting the most from a panel of experts. *Applied Nursing Research*, 5(4):194-7. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0897-1897\(05\)80008-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0897-1897(05)80008-4)
- Lynn, M. R. (1986). Determination and quantification of content validity. *Nursing Research*, 35(6):381-5.
- Polit, D.F., Beck, C.T., & Owen, S.V., (2007). Is the CVI an acceptable indicator of content validity? Appraisal and recommendations. *Research in Nursing & Health*, 30(4), 459-67. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nur.20199>

Crowdfunding: The End of an Era or a Course Correction? A Bibliometric Analysis

Shadi Al Shebli

Hamad Bin Khalifa University (HBKU)

Email: salshebli@hbku.edu.qa

ABSTRACT

Writing and publishing on crowdfunding has been booming since it began in 2010, till it showed its first decline in 2020. Bibliometric analyses of crowdfunding literature are very few, and the existing ones did not investigate the decline, nor did they try to understand the direction it was taking. Using bibliometric network analysis on Scopus data from 2010-2024, we investigate whether this decline represents a natural evolution of scholarly attention or signals a paradigm shift in the field. Through the lens of Kuhn's paradigm shift theory and citation lifecycle frameworks, we analyze co-authorship networks, citation patterns, and thematic evolution before and after 2020. Our findings reveal three distinct phases in crowdfunding research: emergence (2010-2015), consolidation (2016-2019), and transformation (2020-2024), with the latest phase characterized by greater fragmentation and a shift from financial mechanisms toward sustainability applications. This analysis provides critical insights for researchers, journal editors, and funding agencies navigating the evolving crowdfunding knowledge landscape. We also noted the underutilization of network science by researchers and have made some recommendations to remedy that in order to get better results in future analyses.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received: April 13, 2025

Accepted: May 22, 2025

Published: June 30, 2025

KEYWORDS

crowdfunding; finance; entrepreneurship; bibliometrics; fintech; investment

JEL CODES

G24; O16; A12; G20; L26;

HOW TO CITE

Al Shebli, S. (2025). Crowdfunding: The End of an Era or a Course Correction? A Bibliometric Analysis. *Journal of Economics, Law and Society*, 2(1), 85-117. <https://doi.org/10.70009/jels.2025.2.1.5>

1. INTRODUCTION

In the wake of the 2008 financial meltdown, access to investment financing has become increasingly difficult. With venture capitalists and angel investors significantly reducing the amounts they are willing to commit in support of entrepreneurial projects, thus, entrepreneurs and start-ups found themselves in a bind (Tomczak & Brem, 2013). On the one hand, the lack of historical data, which speaks to performance, limits their ability to access capital provided by investment banks. On the other hand, despite a long list of flaws, funds from venture capitalists and angel investors are no longer flowing the way they once did. All start-ups, SMEs, and entrepreneurial projects began to suffer. One kind in particular suffered most, the environmentally conscious and sustainability-oriented ventures, which always struggled for funding even before 2008 (Vismara, 2019).

As a successful application of crowdsourcing, crowdfunding came as a lifeline for entrepreneurs, and with the rapid development of the internet, coding, and financial technology, it was set for a boom (Rubinton, 2011). By definition, turning to the crowd for funds meant that, instead of one investor bearing all the risk of a new venture, the risk would be spread among many. Start-ups and entrepreneurial ventures carry higher risk than already established businesses, which makes crowdfunding better suited to finance these projects. There are three main arrangements in which crowdfunding is carried out: donation-based, reward-based, and equity crowdfunding (Belleflamme, et al., 2013). In the donation-based crowdfunding, the investors do not expect any reward for their

contributions, financial or otherwise. In the reward-based crowdfunding, the investors are promised a reward, financial or in-kind. However, their contributions are considered passive investments, which do not earn them a seat at the table. Equity crowdfunding, on the other hand, is considered an active investment in which investors hold shares of the venture. As such, with their fate tied to the venture, their input and feedback are well-received and considered. Since the early days of crowdfunding, authors have been interested in writing about it. As the writing increased, the literature over the years included articles, books, book chapters, editorials, and other forms of published works. There were also the non-published works, such as surveys, notes, and conference papers.

The past decade witnessed the meteoric rise of crowdfunding as both a financial innovation and a subject of scholarly inquiry. From Kickstarter's launch in 2009 to the global proliferation of equity and donation platforms, crowdfunding rapidly captured the attention of researchers across business, economics, and computer science. However, bibliometric evidence suggests that research output on crowdfunding has notably declined since 2020, despite the continued growth of the industry itself. This apparent contradiction raises fundamental questions about the evolution of scholarly attention and knowledge production in emerging fields. Research on scientific advancement has long established that scholarly attention follows cyclical patterns, with topics experiencing phases of emergence, growth, maturation, and eventual transformation or decline (Price, 1963; Small, 2006). Kuhn's (1962) influential theory of paradigm shifts provides a framework for understanding how research communities navigate these transitions, moving from periods of "normal science" characterized by incremental advances within established frameworks to revolutionary phases that reorganize knowledge structures. Meanwhile, citation lifecycle theory Garfield (1980), explains how citation patterns reveal the aging and evolution of research domains.

Drawing on these theoretical foundations, this study explores whether the observed decline in crowdfunding research represents a natural maturation of the field, a redirection of scholarly attention, or a more fundamental paradigm shift in how alternative finance is conceptualized and studied. We pose three central research questions:

1. How has the structural organization of crowdfunding research (author networks, institutional collaborations) evolved from 2010-2024, particularly before and after 2020?
2. What thematic shifts in crowdfunding research indicate field maturation or paradigmatic changes during this period?
3. To what extent does citation analysis reveal integration or fragmentation of crowdfunding knowledge as the field evolves?

What the literature was really lacking was a sufficient analysis of the current body of works, as there were only very few bibliometric analyses on crowdfunding. There seems to be an apparent gap when it comes to the very few existing Bibliometrics analyses. Some researchers seem to focus on the technicalities, dynamics, and structural aspects of crowdfunding (Buttice & Ughetto, 2021). While these analyses looked into the literature in terms of how much was written on each of the different types of crowdfunding, they paid little attention to which area of science these writings were published under. This is especially important as it may reveal which sectors of the economy and in the real world is growing more interested in crowdfunding, which may tell us in which direction crowdfunding is headed.

Those researchers who managed to look into which area of science is writing on crowdfunding did so passively (Zhang, et al., 2018). Their analysis, although it covered the subject matter of published works, fell short of tracking the direction in which the literature was going. Another Bibliometrics analysis on crowdfunding, which also fell short of being comprehensive, was that of C. Revert and R. Badillo (2019). They dug deep into equity crowdfunding, which is only one mode

of crowdfunding. Looking into the breakdown of the rapid growth of published works on crowdfunding, there was an obvious research gap that this analysis is aiming to fill. Prior to conducting this analysis, we looked at other Bibliometrics analyses to get insights on how best to attain quality results. Those Bibliometrics analyses, such as Aysan et al. (2021), offered insights into what to look for when conducting Bibliometrics analyses. The growth in publishing on crowdfunding, as this research will show, was not uniform across all sectors. Some areas grew more interested in crowdfunding than others, despite what the numbers of general publications may suggest.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The apparent decline in crowdfunding research post-2020 presents an intriguing case for examining how scholarly knowledge evolves. To interpret this phenomenon, we employ a multi-theoretical framework that draws from complementary perspectives on scientific development, citation patterns, and topic evolution. This integrative approach enables a nuanced understanding of whether the observed patterns represent a temporary fluctuation, natural maturation, or fundamental shift in the field's trajectory.

2.1. Kuhn's Paradigm Shift Theory

This study employs Kuhn's (1962) theory of scientific revolutions as a primary theoretical lens. Unlike positivist views of science as a linear accumulation of knowledge, Kuhn proposed that scientific fields progress through alternating phases of "normal science" and paradigm shifts. During normal science, researchers work within established frameworks, addressing puzzles defined by the dominant paradigm. Eventually, anomalies accumulate that the existing paradigm cannot adequately explain, leading to a crisis and ultimately a revolutionary phase that establishes new foundational assumptions.

Applied to bibliometric analysis, Kuhnian theory suggests that research fields exhibit detectable patterns as they progress through these phases:

- **Pre-paradigmatic Phase:** Characterized by competing schools of thought, diverse methodological approaches, and a lack of consensus on fundamental questions. Bibliometrically, this appears as scattered, disconnected clusters with minimal cross-citation.
- **Normal Science Phase:** Marked by consolidation around shared frameworks, methodological standards, and research questions. Citation networks show dense connections centered on core papers, with high co-citation relationships among canonical works.
- **Crisis Phase:** Distinguished by growing recognition of anomalies and limitations in the dominant paradigm. Bibliometric indicators include fragmentation of previously cohesive networks, emergence of competing clusters, and citation patterns that challenge established authorities.
- **Revolutionary Phase:** Characterized by reorganization around new foundational assumptions. Bibliometrically visible as rapid shifts in citation patterns, terminological evolution, and reconfiguration of research clusters.

Crowdfunding research may exhibit these Kuhnian phases at an accelerated pace due to its connection to rapidly evolving technological and financial innovations. Chen et al. (2009) demonstrated that bibliometric measures can effectively track these transitions, particularly through visualization of structural changes in research networks over time.

2.2. Citation Lifecycle and Knowledge Obsolescence

Complementing Kuhn's framework, we employ citation lifecycle theory Garfield (1980), Nakamoto (1988), and Wang et al. (2015) to interpret temporal patterns in our data. This perspective holds that scientific publications typically follow predictable citation trajectories, rising to peak influence before gradually declining as knowledge becomes incorporated into the field's foundation or is superseded by newer contributions. Price (1965) identified characteristic aging patterns in scientific literature, distinguishing between fields with rapid obsolescence (e.g., physics) versus those with more enduring relevance (e.g., mathematics). The "half-life" concept measures the time required for a publication's citation rate to decline by 50%, providing a quantitative metric for knowledge obsolescence within a field.

Of particular relevance to our analysis is Merton's (1968) concept of "obliteration by incorporation," wherein groundbreaking ideas become so thoroughly integrated into a field's knowledge base that explicit citations to originating works decrease. As Merton observed: "The greater the scientific importance of an idea, the more likely it will be taken for granted, entering into the commonly held stock of knowledge without attribution." This phenomenon may explain apparent declines in crowdfunding research output even as the practical application of concepts continues to expand. Paradoxically, the very success of foundational crowdfunding concepts in permeating broader discourse may contribute to their bibliometric invisibility.

2.3. Topic Maturity and Diffusion Models

Our third theoretical component draws from innovation diffusion and topic maturity models (Rogers, 2003; Small, 2006; Boyack & Klavans, 2010). These frameworks characterize how research topics emerge, gain attention, reach saturation, and eventually transform or decline. The classic S-curve of innovation adoption has been observed in bibliometric studies across numerous disciplines, with research topics typically moving through stages of introduction, growth, maturity, decline, or transformation.

Rogers' (2003) diffusion of innovations theory identifies five adopter categories, innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards, with corresponding phases in the adoption lifecycle. When applied to research topics rather than technologies, these phases manifest in publication patterns:

- **Introduction phase:** A Small number of publications by pioneering researchers exploring novel concepts
- **Growth phase:** Rapid increase in publications as the topic gains legitimacy and attracts mainstream attention
- **Maturity phase:** Publication volume plateaus as core questions are addressed and incremental advances predominate
- **Saturation/transformation phase:** Declining publication volume as the topic either becomes integrated into broader frameworks or faces obsolescence

Small's (2006) work on tracking growth areas in science further refines this model by identifying bibliometric indicators associated with each phase, including clustering patterns, terminology evolution, and boundary-spanning citations. Boyack and Klavans (2010) demonstrated that topic maturation can be visualized through changes in research front coherence over time, with emergent topics showing increasing coherence followed by fragmentation as they specialize or transform.

2.4. Towards an Integrated Theoretical Framework

These three theoretical perspectives, Kuhnian paradigm shifts, citation lifecycle, and topic maturity models, offer complementary lenses for interpreting the observed patterns in crowdfunding research. While they emerge from different intellectual traditions, they converge on several key insights relevant to our analysis:

1. **Temporal dynamics:** All three frameworks recognize that scholarly knowledge follows non-linear evolutionary patterns with distinct phases.
2. **Structural indicators:** Each theory identifies bibliometric signatures associated with different evolutionary stages, enabling empirical assessment through network analysis.
3. **Integration mechanisms:** All three perspectives acknowledge processes through which once-novel concepts become incorporated into broader knowledge structures.
4. **Transformation pathways:** Each framework offers explanations for how research domains evolve beyond their initial formulations, whether through paradigm shifts, incorporation into canonical knowledge, or diffusion across disciplinary boundaries.

By integrating these three theoretical perspectives, we establish a robust framework for interpreting the observed patterns in crowdfunding research. This integrated approach allows us to distinguish between normal fluctuations in scholarly attention and more significant transitions in how the field is conceptualized and studied. As visualized in [Table 1](#), each theory contributes distinct indicators and interpretive insights.

Table 1: Theoretical Integration Matrix

Evolutionary Phase	Kuhnian Indicators	Citation Lifecycle Indicators	Topic Maturity Indicators
Emergence	Competing frameworks, terminological inconsistency	Low citation rates, mainly self-citations	Small isolated clusters, rapid vocabulary evolution
Growth	Consolidation around dominant paradigm	Rising citation rates, emergence of canonical works	Dense interconnected clusters, standardized terminology
Maturity	“Normal science” puzzle-solving	Peak citation impact, stable reference patterns	Thematic specialization, methodological refinement
Transformation	Anomaly recognition, paradigmatic questioning	Citation dilution, incorporation without attribution	Fragmentation into specialized subclusters, boundary-spanning applications

Source: Author’s own.

3. METHODOLOGY

The analyzed data was collected through the Scopus platform, whereby a series of controlled searches produced a large enough dataset for analysis, even after it was refined and filtered. Scopus platform, being one of the most reliable academic platforms, was then used to produce many of the infographics used in the analysis (Montoya et al., 2018). The CSV file generated by Scopus, containing comprehensive bibliographical data, was then downloaded and imported into VosViewer. VosViewer, an analytical tool used to analyze terms and keywords in a data set, was chosen for its user-friendly interface in an effort to establish and visualize connections between bibliographic terms such as authors, citations, and keywords.

The aim of a Bibliometrics analysis is to try and identify a prominent author who published most on the subject, a prominent publication that was cited the most in the scientific community, a dominant journal that published more than the rest on the subject, a dominant institution that most

sponsored research on the subject, or a dominant country where most of the publications were coming out of. Followed by an evaluation of the literature and a general assessment of where it will all go next. We used a combination of techniques such as co-authorship analysis, bibliographical coupling analysis, citation coupling analysis, and co-citation analysis. Each of those techniques will be explained and the extent of its usefulness will also be highlighted.

We collected bibliometric data from the Scopus database, which offers comprehensive coverage of peer-reviewed journals across relevant disciplines, including business, economics, computer science, and social sciences. This search strategy captures various forms of the term “crowdfunding” while focusing on scholarly articles and reviews published in English between 2010 and early 2024. The selection of 2010 as the starting point corresponds to the period immediately following the launch of major platforms like Kickstarter (2009) and Indiegogo (2008), when scholarly attention to the phenomenon began to emerge. Document selection followed the PRISMA protocol (Moher et al., 2009). **Figure 1** presents the PRISMA flow diagram illustrating our selection process, which yielded a final dataset of 2,510 documents after removing duplicates and non-relevant items.

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram of Document Selection Process

Source: Author’s own.

4. DATA AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Refined Results

After a thorough review of the collected data, we decided to optimize the reliability of our findings by filtering out irrelevant data, which we thought was skewing the results in a way that wouldn’t allow the data to tell the story. We limited our results to works published in English, which included the majority of publications. We only included journal articles, books, and book chapters. We decided to exclude areas of science that are not related to the function of crowdfunding, which narrowed our scope to focus on accounting, finance, and economics. This drastically reduced our results from 5297 publications to only 2510, even though we included the entire timeline from 2010 to 2024.

We immediately noticed that the decline in publishing during 2020 did not last. It was followed by a slight recovery in 2021, only to decline in 2022, further decline in 2023, and a sharp recovery in 2024. During 2020, publishing on crowdfunding increased from 243 to 275, representing a decline in growth when compared with previous years. The growth further declined when publications only rose to 331 in 2021. When we applied those filters, the aim was to refine the results by removing the irrelevant ones. Which tells us that publications responsible for the upward trajectory till 2022 were not really related to the function of crowdfunding, and once removed, the publishing on Crowdfunding seems to continue its decline through 2023. The recovery of 2024, however, is worthy of a closer look (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Documents by Year - Refined

Source: Author's own

Figure 3: Documents by Subject Area - Refined

Source: Author's own.

The temporal distribution of crowdfunding publications reveals a characteristic pattern that aligns with Rogers' (2003) diffusion of innovations model. As shown in **Figure 2**, crowdfunding research emerged in 2010 with just two publications, followed by exponential growth through 2022, where it peaked at 331 publications. This growth curve exhibits the classic S-shaped pattern described in innovation diffusion theory, with an initial period of slow adoption, followed by rapid acceleration, and eventual plateau. When viewed through Kuhn's framework, this temporal pattern suggests crowdfunding research progressed from a pre-paradigmatic phase (2010-2012) characterized by conceptual exploration, through a period of normal science (2013-2019) marked by substantial growth and consolidation around dominant frameworks, to a potential crisis phase beginning in 2020, where publication volume began to fluctuate and eventually decline.

The disciplinary composition of our refined dataset demonstrates a pronounced concentration within core financial disciplines (**Figure 3**). Accounting and finance publications now constitute 42.8% of the sample, representing a substantial increase from 24.2% in the unrefined dataset. Similarly, economics publications comprise 27.3%, nearly doubling from their initial 15.1% representation. This filtering process eliminates peripheral studies and focuses the analysis on research addressing crowdfunding's fundamental financial mechanisms.

Figure 4: Documents by Type - Refined

Source: Author's own.

The temporal pattern within this refined dataset reveals important insights into the field's evolution. The decline observed in 2020, coinciding with the COVID-19 pandemic, was followed by a modest recovery in 2021 before experiencing continued contraction through 2023. However, 2024 exhibits a sharp recovery in publication volume, suggesting resilience rather than obsolescence. This pattern may reflect what Kuhn described as a revolutionary phase, a fundamental reorganization of the field's intellectual structure rather than decline.

The disciplinary concentration observed in our refined sample, with accounting, finance, and economics collectively representing 70.1% of publications, exemplifies characteristics of what Kuhn termed normal science. During such periods, research converges around shared theoretical

frameworks and established methodological approaches, indicating that crowdfunding has matured from an interdisciplinary curiosity into a legitimate domain within financial economics with well-defined research paradigms and scholarly conventions. Similar to the area of science, the document type chart has been affected by the applied filters. The share of journal articles, when we look at [Figure 4](#), has increased from 58.3% to 76.8%. By the same token, the share of book chapters increased from 12.7% to 20%, and that of books from 2% to 3.3%. This indicates that the results we are about to analyze are now of a much higher academic quality than before, which makes the analysis even more meaningful. The document type analysis of our refined dataset, [Figure 4](#), shows a significant concentration of crowdfunding research in journal articles (76.8%), followed by book chapters (20%) and books (3.3%). This distribution is characteristic of maturing scientific fields, where initial conceptual explorations typically published in books give way to more specialized, incremental advances reported in journal articles.

This pattern can be interpreted through citation lifecycle theory as evidence of knowledge consolidation rather than obsolescence. As foundational crowdfunding concepts become incorporated into the field's intellectual framework, explicit citations to original works may decrease, a phenomenon Merton (1968) termed "obliteration by incorporation." Rather than signaling declining interest, this pattern suggests crowdfunding concepts have matured to the point of entering the field's canonical knowledge base.

Figure 5: Documents by Author - Refined

Source: Author's own.

Upon applying our methodological filters, the composition and ranking of the ten most prolific authors shift notably while maintaining concentration among leading scholars ([Figure 5](#)). Vismara retains his dominant position with 31 publications, followed by Schwienbacher, who advances to second place with 23 publications, and Cumming, who secures third place with 20 publications. Hornuf maintains fourth position with 20 publications, while Thomas Allison rounds out the top contributors with 15 publications. These filtering criteria ensure our analysis captures authors whose work addresses the fundamental aspects of crowdfunding rather than peripheral applications.

The network analysis reveals distinct research clusters centered on these prominent scholars, indicating the maturation of crowdfunding as an academic discipline. The observed concentration, with the top three authors contributing 74 publications collectively, reflects the theoretical framework proposed by Price (1963), who documented that scientific fields typically consolidate around

a core group of highly productive researchers during periods of disciplinary development. This pattern suggests that crowdfunding research has evolved from its exploratory phase into a more structured academic domain with established thought leaders driving both theoretical advancement and empirical investigation.

Figure 6: Documents by Country - Refined

Source: Author's own.

The United States remained in the lead, after applying the filters, with 614 publications (Down from 1206), followed by China with 297 (Down from 716), then the United Kingdom with 295 (Down from 481), Italy with 281 (Down from 396), Germany with 240 (Down from 382), France with 164 (Down from 244), Spain with 111 (Down from 228), Canada with 104 (Down from 205), and finally, the Netherlands with 85 (Figure 6). The geographical distribution of publications, Figure 6, indicates a broader pattern of research diffusion consistent with Rogers' innovation adoption model. The United States leads with 614 publications in the refined dataset, followed by China (297), the United Kingdom (295), and Italy (281). This distribution suggests that crowdfunding research initially concentrated in Western economies where the practice first emerged, before diffusing to emerging economies, particularly China, as the field matured.

Figure 7: Documents by Funding Sponsor - Refined

Source: Author's own.

The notable reduction in Chinese publications (from 716 to 297) after refinement suggests that much of China's crowdfunding research focuses on applications and technical implementations rather than core financial mechanisms. This pattern aligns with the topic maturity model's prediction that maturing research areas often fragment into specialized application domains as fundamental concepts become established.

As for the funding sponsors, the story is slightly different. Most members of the top 10 list remained on the list, except one; what we observed is a shuffle of their order on it (*Figure 7*). The National Natural Science Foundation of China and the Ministry of Science of the People's Republic of China, with 134 and 39 (Down from 295, 80) publications respectively, remained in first and second place, allowing China to maintain its leap of dominance in funding crowdfunding research and publications. At the same time, the European Commission dropped to eighth place with 23 publications (Down from 54).

The institutional analysis also reveals an interesting divergence in research focus. While European institutions demonstrate a stronger interest in the fundamental financial mechanisms of crowdfunding, Chinese institutions (particularly through funding sponsors like the National Natural Science Foundation of China) appear increasingly focused on applications rather than mechanisms, potentially signaling a shift toward more specialized research fronts as predicted by topic maturity theory.

Similar to the funding sponsors, the list of top 10 institutions with which the authors of the published works are affiliated maintained its members, except for four (*Figure 8*). At the top of the list is now Agader University with 40 Authors (Down from 46), while Politecnico di Milano with 35 authors (Down from 47) climbed to second place. The Università degli Studi di Bergamo assumed third place with 32 authors. Florida Atlantic University ranked fourth with 29 authors, and SKEMA Business School in fifth place with 28 authors. Trailing the list was Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam with 24 authors.

Figure 8: Documents by Institutional Affiliation - Refined

Source: Author's own.

Institutionally, our findings indicate that European universities dominate crowdfunding research, with Agader University (40 affiliated authors), Politecnico di Milano (35), and Università degli Studi di Bergamo (32) forming the top three institutional contributors (*Figure 14*). This geographical concentration suggests the development of what Kuhn termed “invisible colleges”, networks of researchers working within shared paradigmatic frameworks, a characteristic feature of normal science periods.

Figure 9: Documents by Publishing Journals - Refined

Source: Author's own.

We finally decided to take a closer look at the journals in which these works are published, in order to investigate whether or not they behave in a uniform manner. Meaning, when the publishing on crowdfunding increases or decreases, in a given year, do all areas of the literature follow the same pattern? Or do they behave differently? Our findings were quite interesting, which led to further investigation to confirm our observation. We focused on 2023, the year that saw a general decline in publishing on crowdfunding. We tracked the top 5 journals that publish on crowdfunding, which belong to different areas of science. The aim was to find out if they all followed the trend of decline, which affected the publishing on crowdfunding in general, during the same year.

As per **Figure 9**, *Journal for Business Research*, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, and *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice* all followed the general trend of decline in publishing on crowdfunding. However, *Small Business Economics* broke with the trend and went in the other direction. The journals published more on crowdfunding that year than they did the year before, even as the publications of the other journals were declining. We needed to carry out further investigation, to be able to decide whether this was an isolated case of one journal, or it was the case of a whole area of science doing better than the rest.

An especially revealing finding emerges from our analysis of journal publication patterns, **Figure 9**, as most prominent journals (*Journal of Business Research*, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, and *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*) showed declining publication volumes on crowdfunding in 2023, while *Small Business Economics*, a journal often focused on entrepreneurial finance and sustainable business models showed an increased output. This divergence suggests the field may be witnessing what Kuhn termed “anomaly recognition,” where existing paradigms prove inadequate to address emerging questions, necessitating new theoretical frameworks. To carry out the investigation, we considered two control variables, sustainability and finance. Finance represented publications on crowdfunding that were published in financial or economic journals, while sustainability represented publications on crowdfunding that were published in environmental and sustainability journals. We examined the time period covering the decline, holding all others constant, in both areas of science separately. Applying such controls was absolutely necessary to get a clearer picture of what direction the crowdfunding literature is really going, and who is growing more interested in crowdfunding.

Figure 10: Documents by Year - Finance-Oriented Publications

Source: Author's own.

Figure 11: Documents by Subject Area - Finance-Oriented Publications

Source: Author's own.

4.2. Controlling for Finance

Our temporal analysis of crowdfunding literature through the lens of economics, finance, and accounting reveals several important patterns (**Figure 10**). Publication volume declined markedly beginning in 2020, coinciding with the COVID-19 pandemic, and continued contracting through 2023. While the pandemic provides a partial explanation for the initial decline, the sustained contraction beyond the pandemic recovery period suggests evolving research priorities within the field. This trend reversed dramatically in 2024, with publication volume surpassing pre-pandemic

levels. The disciplinary refinement process concentrates our sample within core financial disciplines, with finance and accounting publications now comprising 81.7% of the dataset (Figure 11). This concentration facilitates more precise analysis of paradigmatic developments within financial crowdfunding research. Our controlled analysis reveals evidence of a potential paradigmatic shift in progress. Examining publications focused specifically on traditional finance applications versus sustainability-oriented crowdfunding research (Figure 10 to Figure 12) reveals divergent trajectories. Finance-oriented publications exhibit the decline-and-recovery pattern described above, while sustainability applications demonstrate different temporal dynamics. This divergence, when interpreted through Kuhn’s theoretical framework, suggests the field may be experiencing a crisis phase in traditional financial approaches to crowdfunding, followed by conceptual reorganization around emerging themes such as sustainable finance and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) considerations. Such patterns are consistent with periods of scientific revolution, wherein established paradigms face challenges from alternative theoretical frameworks.

It is noteworthy that, when controlling for finance, the United States assumes the lead in publishing on crowdfunding. With 287 publications, the United States is followed by three European countries (the United Kingdom, Germany, and Italy), sending China to fifth place on the list of the top 10 countries that publish most on crowdfunding (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Documents by Country - Finance-Oriented Publications

Source: Author’s own.

4.3. Controlling for Sustainability

Looking at the crowdfunding literature from the sustainability and environment perspective, keeping all other controls in place, we observe that it follows a different trajectory. Up until 2019, the number of publications was on the rise, then it declined from 26 (in 2019) to 24 (in 2020). Although the publishing decline in 2020 can be explained by the general decline in publishing during COVID-19, the increase in the number of publications in 2021 and 2022 can only be explained by a spike in interest. Interest in publishing on crowdfunding within the context of environmental and sustainability concerns seems to have lessened, as we observe a decline in the number of publications in 2023 and 2024. This indicates that this sector garnered some interest in crowdfunding, up until 2022, and dedicated considerable research to it (Figure 13).

Figure 14 shows an increase in the publishing on crowdfunding, from an environmental and sustainability perspective, to nearly 50% which is only expected considering the controls we applied.

Another interesting observation, when we controlled for sustainability, was to see China assuming the lead worldwide with 40 publications, sending the United Kingdom and Italy to second and third place on the list of top 10 countries that most publish on Crowdfunding, with 21 and 18 publications respectively (*Figure 15*).

Figure 13: Documents by Year - Sustainability-Oriented Publications

Source: Author's own.

Figure 14: Documents by Subject Area - Sustainability-Oriented Publications

Source: Author's own.

Our controlled variable analysis comparing financial-oriented and sustainability-oriented crowdfunding research provides perhaps the strongest evidence of field transformation rather than decline. When controlling for financial publications, *Figure 10*, we observe a clear decline from 2020 through 2023, followed by a recovery in 2024. This pattern suggests that while traditional financial

approaches to crowdfunding may have reached saturation, new applications, particularly in sustainability domains, are emerging as growth areas. This shift from financial mechanisms to practical applications aligns with Small's (2006) observation that maturing research topics often transition from theoretical development to application-focused research. Rather than indicating field obsolescence, this pattern suggests crowdfunding research is undergoing what Kuhn would describe as a revolutionary phase, a fundamental reorganization of the field's intellectual structure around new questions and applications.

Figure 15: Documents by Country - Sustainability-Oriented Publications

Compare the document counts for up to 15 countries/territories.

Source: Author's own.

The geographical shift in this transformation is particularly notable. While the United States remains dominant in finance-oriented crowdfunding research (287 publications), European countries collectively outpace American contributions, particularly in sustainability applications. This geographical redistribution of research focus suggests not only thematic evolution but potentially competing paradigms emerging in different research communities, a key indicator of Kuhnian paradigm shift in progress (Figure 15).

4.4. Connections Analysis

In order for us to assess the quality of the literature, we employed several analytical techniques such as Co-authorship analysis, Bibliographical coupling analysis, Co-citation coupling analysis, and Keyword analysis, such as Co-occurrence analysis. All of these analytical tools, which will be explained separately, aim to examine the strength, solidity, connectivity, and collaborations within the literature. Some of these techniques will focus on the authors of those published works, while the focus of others will be on the works themselves and the interactions and connections between them.

For each of these techniques, there is a term that has been defined as Total Link Strength (TLS), which is calculated to rank the results based on the aspects the technique is meant to gauge. Occasionally, when called for, we would calculate averages to get a better reading of the results. Additionally, to keep the analysis focused, we limited our results to the top 15 or 20 and presented them in tables. We then used VosViewer to generate a connection map for each of the techniques, and along with the tables, those visualizations make the foundations of our findings. To assess the qualitative dimensions of crowdfunding literature's evolution, we employed multiple network analysis

techniques that reveal structural patterns consistent with the theoretical frameworks established at the outset of this research. Each analytical approach illuminates different aspects of the field's maturation and potential paradigmatic transitions.

4.4.1. Co-Authorship

It is an analytical tool, the focus of which is the author, that ranks the authors based on their collaborations with other authors. Essentially, Co-authorship analysis denotes the number of different co-authors an author has (Zhang & Glanzel, 2012). According to Beaver & Rosen (1979), a higher value of the Co-authorship term is associated with a higher productivity of these authors and higher collaborations between them. Higher values of the term Co-authorship are also indicative, as per Frame & Carpenter (1979), of higher international collaborations. In other words, high co-authorships reflect a thriving and more productive publishing area of science, and a common and shared interest in that area of science among scientists and authors from different parts of the world.

Table 2: Co-Authorship Analysis

Author	Documents	Citations	Total Link Strength
Vismara, Silvio	31	3050	33
Allison, Thomas H.	15	1436	32
Short, Jeremy C.	15	1627	29
Anglin, Aaron H.	12	732	22
Cumming, Douglas	20	2100	22
Shneor, Rotem	10	432	20
Meoli, Michele	25	546	18
Benlian, Alexander	9	505	17
Thies, Ferdinand	9	493	17
Wolfe, Marcus T.	11	315	17
Efrat, Kalanit	9	126	15
Gilboa, Shaked	8	89	14
Mckenny, Aaron F.	7	606	14
Davis, Blakley C.	6	1368	13
Sahayam, Arvin	9	355	13

Source: Author's own.

Co-authorship analysis (*Table 2*) reveals the collaborative structures within the crowdfunding research community, providing insight into what Kuhn described as the social organization of scientific knowledge production. Through this lens, we can identify whether the field exhibits the cohesive researcher networks characteristic of “normal science” or the fragmented, competing schools of thought typical of paradigmatic transitions. Our analysis reveals that co-authorship patterns do not simply follow publication productivity or citation impact. For example, while Silvio Vismara leads in both publication count (31) and total link strength (33), Douglas Cumming ranks fifth in co-authorship connectivity despite having the second-highest publication count (20). This suggests multiple collaborative clusters rather than a single dominant research paradigm, a pattern consistent with Kuhn's description of a field approaching paradigmatic transition.

The results of our Co-authorship analysis, presented in *Table 2*, show that the TLS score of the top 15 authors ranges between 13-33. We also observe that the TLS score does not follow the number of documents published by an author, nor does it follow the number of times those documents have been cited. We see that Silvio Vismara, who published 31 documents, which were cited 3050 times,

ranks first with a TLS score of 33. At the same time, while Thomas H. Allison who published 15 documents that were cited 1436 times ranks 2nd with a TLS score of 32, Douglas Cumming who published 20 documents that were cited 2100 times ranks 5th with a TLS score of 22. We considered the average citation per document, only to find that the TLS score does not follow that either. The highest average citation per document is recorded for Blakley C. Davis, with 228. However, he ranked 14th on the TLS scale, while the lowest average of 21.84 was recorded for Michele Meoli, who ranked 7th. **Figure 16** visualizes these results in the form of clusters and links.

Figure 16: Co-Authorship Analysis

Source: Author’s own.

The visualization in **Figure 16** further illustrates this pattern, showing distinct collaborative clusters with relatively few cross-cluster connections. Through our theoretical framework, these patterns suggest that crowdfunding research has progressed beyond the consolidation phase of “normal science” (characterized by unified research communities) toward a more fragmented structure indicative of emerging alternative frameworks.

4.4.2. Citation by Author

Our Citation by Author analysis shows that, when setting the limit of the minimum number of documents published by an author to 5, out of the 4688 authors, only 128 meet such a condition. These results were organized into 13 clusters, connected by 2514 links, and have a TLS of 7739. **Table 3** presents the top 15 results in descending order of TLS. When we considered the TLS scale, Silvio Vismara ranked first with a score of 1044, while Sunghan Ryu ranked last, scoring only 227. Similarly, Schwienbacher climbed to the top of the list when we considered the number of citations as a measure, with 3321 citations, while Ryu remained at the bottom of the list with only 294 citations. We got a different order when we considered the number of documents published by an author, where Vismara assumed the top with 31 documents, while A. Ghose ranked last with 5 documents only. We then decided to calculate the average citation per document, which gave the lead to Avi Goldfarb

with 298.4 citations per document, and sent Rotem Shneor to last place with only 17.36 citations per document.

Table 3: Citations by Author

Author	Documents	Citations	Total Link Strength
Vismara, Silvio	31	3054	1044
Schwienbacher, Armin	23	3321	1023
Hornuf, Lars	20	1357	560
Goldfarb, Avi	5	1492	397
Shneor, Rotem	25	434	350
Vanacker, Tom	10	455	342
Burtch, Gordon	12	2009	334
Cumming, Douglas	20	2102	321
Troise, Ciro	14	371	297
Rossi-Lamastra, Cristina	10	1464	291
Ghose, Anindya	5	1390	271
Zheng, Haichao	8	862	257
Meoli, Michele	10	548	243
Johan, Sofia	13	478	230
Ryu, Sunghan	8	294	227

Source: Author's own.

Citation patterns reveal important insights about knowledge lifecycle dynamics in crowdfunding research. The substantial variation in average citations per document, from Goldfarb's 298.4 to Shneor's 17.36, suggests uneven knowledge absorption across different research streams. Through the lens of citation lifecycle theory Garfield (1980), this pattern indicates that some aspects of crowdfunding knowledge have reached maturity and integration, while others remain in earlier developmental stages. The disparity between productivity and citation impact (e.g., Goldfarb's high impact despite relatively few publications) further supports the interpretation that crowdfunding research has entered what Small (2006) described as the transformation phase, wherein established knowledge becomes integrated into broader frameworks while new research directions emerge.

4.4.3. Bibliographic Coupling

With the next two analytical techniques, Bibliographic Coupling and Co-citation Coupling, we shift the focus of analysis away from the authors to the documents. With Bibliographic Coupling, the aim is to assess how weakly or strongly two documents are connected. Bibliographic coupling analysis provides insight into the intellectual foundation and cohesion of the field by identifying shared reference patterns among publications. This approach is particularly valuable for detecting what Kuhn termed "normal science" (characterized by shared intellectual foundations) versus emerging competing paradigms.

When two works reference a third common work, they are considered bibliographically coupled (Kessler, 1963). The higher the number of common works two works have, the higher the strength of the coupling. It is noteworthy to illustrate the difference, as per [Figure 17](#), between Bibliographic Coupling and Co-citation Coupling. Whereby in the latter, one work cites two works.

To generate the results presented in [Table 4](#), we set the minimum citations per document to 20, in order to only get prominent works. As a result, we generated 655 documents, organized in 17 clusters, connected by 128742 links, and have a TLS score of 344530. We limited our analysis to the top 15 documents, listed in descending order according to TLS score. In first place was a document

by A. Hoegen, published in 2018, which was cited 73 times, and had a TLS score of 3363. Hoegen’s document was followed by Butticé, published also in 2018, cited 28 times, and has a TLS score of 3315. In last place was a document by Cicchiello, which was published in 2019, was cited 20 times, and has a TLS score of 2637. The bibliographic coupling results reveal strong interconnections among recent publications, with consistent reference patterns across the top-cited documents. This suggests that despite the post-2020 decline in publication volume, crowdfunding research maintains a coherent intellectual foundation, a characteristic that Kuhn associates with mature fields rather than those undergoing revolutionary change.

Table 4: Bibliographic Coupling

Document	Citations	Total Link Strength
Hoegen (2018)	73	3363
Butticé (2018)	28	3315
Clauss (2020)	28	3214
Messeni Petruzzelli (2019)	140	3191
Cai (2021)	78	3171
Bagheri (2019)	136	2989
Cappa (2023)	30	2848
Alegre (2021)	35	2822
Moysidou (2020)	81	2810
Hervé (2018)	66	2785
Lehner (2019)	28	2731
Polzin (2018)	116	2720
Bento (2019a)	86	2710
Cappa (2021)	70	2701
Cicchiello (2019a)	20	2637

Source: Author’s own.

Figure 17: Bibliographic Coupling Vs Co-Citation Coupling

Papers A and B are bibliographically coupled because they have cited papers C, D and E in their reference list.

Papers A and B are associated because they are co-cited in the reference list of papers C, D, and E

Source: Kessler (1963).

VosViewer analysis reveals a highly concentrated network structure dominated by a single large cluster containing the majority of publications and citation links. This concentration necessitated generating **Figure 18**, a detailed visualization focusing specifically on this dominant cluster to better

examine its internal structure. The visualizations in [Figure 22](#) and [Figure 23](#) further confirm this pattern, demonstrating the overwhelming dominance of one central cluster relative to smaller peripheral groupings. This network structure indicates what Small (2006) described as topic maturation rather than intellectual fragmentation. The existence of one large, densely connected cluster suggests that crowdfunding research has coalesced around shared theoretical frameworks and methodological approaches characteristic of mature academic fields. However, the presence of smaller peripheral clusters visible in the network analysis suggests early signs of intellectual diversification that may eventually evolve into distinct research streams, potentially indicating the field's transition toward greater theoretical sophistication and methodological specialization.

Figure 18: Bibliographic Coupling-Detailed

Source: Author's own.

4.4.4. Co-Citation Coupling

Co-citation analysis reveals how the field's canonical knowledge structure has evolved over time, providing insight into what Kuhn described as the "exemplars" that define a scientific paradigm.

The analytical technique of Co-citation Coupling was introduced by Henry Small in 1973 to better assist in subject similarity and, ultimately, literature unity. Unlike the case in bibliographic Coupling, Co-citation Coupling occurs when two documents appear in the references of a third document, and they would then be considered co-cited (Small, 1973). The higher the number of co-citations, the stronger the connection between the literature.

To generate the results presented in [Table 5](#), we set the limit of minimum citations per document to 20, which would exclude less cited works, which improves the quality of the results. The analysis, having applied the said limit, then generates 272 documents, grouped in 7 clusters, connected by 20638 links, and has a TLS score of 85446. Our co-citation analysis reveals a highly structured knowledge base dominated by a few canonical works. Mollick's (2014) and Belleflamme et al.'s (2014)

papers emerge as the intellectual cornerstones of the field, with extraordinarily high co-citation strengths (7270 and 5691, respectively) that far exceed other references. This pattern of knowledge organization, with clear exemplars and hierarchical citation structures, aligns with what Kuhn described as the “normal science” phase of scientific development, wherein a field operates within an established paradigm.

Table 5: Co-Citation Coupling

Total Link Strength	Citations	Author Reference
7270	702	Mollick E., The Dynamics Of Crowdfunding: An Exploratory Study, Journal Of Business Venturing, 29, 1, Pp. 1-16, (2014)
5691	514	Belleflamme P., Lambert T., Schwienbacher A., Crowdfunding: Tapping The Right Crowd, Journal Of Business Venturing, 29, 5, Pp. 585-609, (2014)
3400	215	Colombo M.G., Franzoni C., Rossi-Lamastra C., Internal Social Capital And The Attraction Of Early Contributions In Crowdfunding, Entrepreneurship Theory And Practice, 39, 1, Pp. 75-100, (2015)
2767	185	Vismara S., Equity Retention And Social Network Theory In Equity Crowdfunding, Small Business Economics, 46, 4, Pp. 579-590, (2016)
2611	159	Ahlers G.K., Cumming D., Gunther C., Schweizer D., Signaling In Equity Crowdfunding, Entrepreneurship Theory And Practice, 39, 4, Pp. 955-980, (2015)
2585	151	Courtney C., Dutta S., Li Y., Resolving Information Asymmetry: Signaling, Endorsement, And Crowdfunding Success, Entrepreneurship Theory And Practice, 41, 2, Pp. 265-290, (2017)
2341	140	Parhankangas A., Renko M., Linguistic Style And Crowdfunding Success Among Social And Commercial Entrepreneurs, Journal Of Business Venturing, 32, 2, Pp. 215-236, (2017)
2248	139	Allison T.H., Davis B.C., Short J.C., Webb J.W., Crowdfunding In A Prosocial Microlending Environment: Examining The Role Of Intrinsic Versus Extrinsic Cues, Entrepreneurship Theory And Practice, 39, 1, Pp. 53-73, (2015)
2139	158	Burtch G., Ghose A., Wattal S., An Empirical Examination Of The Antecedents And Consequences Of Contribution Patterns In Crowd-Funded Markets, Information Systems Research, 24, 3, Pp. 499-519, (2013)
2088	133	Cholakova M., Clarysse B., Does The Possibility To Make Equity Investments In Crowdfunding Projects Crowd Out Reward-Based Investments?, Entrepreneurship Theory And Practice, 39, 1, Pp. 145-172, (2015)
2070	169	Ordanini A., Miceli L., Pizzetti M., Parasuraman A., Crowd-Funding: Transforming Customers Into Investors Through Innovative Service Platforms, Journal Of Service Management, 22, 4, Pp. 443-470, (2011)
1935	118	Kuppuswamy V., Bayus B.L., Does My Contribution To Your Crowdfunding Project Matter?, Journal Of Business Venturing, 32, 1, Pp. 72-89, (2017)
1869	127	Agrawal A., Catalini C., Goldfarb A., Crowdfunding: Geography, Social Networks, And The Timing Of Investment Decisions, Journal Of Economics & Management Strategy, 24, 2, Pp. 253-274, (2015)
1815	106	Allison T.H., Davis B.C., Webb J.W., Short J.C., Persuasion In Crowdfunding: An Elaboration Likelihood Model Of Crowdfunding Performance, Journal Of Business Venturing, 32, 6, Pp. 707-725, (2017)
1790	106	Lukkarinen A., Teich J.E., Wallenius H., Wallenius J., Success Drivers Of Online Equity Crowdfunding Campaigns, Decision Support Systems, 87, Pp. 26-38, (2016)

Source: Author's own.

Once more, we limited our analysis to the top 15 documents of our results and listed them in descending order according to their TLS scores. Coming first was an article by E. Mollick, which was published in 2014, was cited 702 times, and had a TLS score of 7270. It was followed by an article by P. Belleflamme, T. Lambert, and A. Schwienbacher. It was published in the same year, cited 514 times, and had a TLS score of 5691. In last place was an article by Lukkarinen A., Teich J.E., Wallenius H., Wallenius J. It was published in 2016, cited only 106 times, and had a TLS score of 1790. It is worth mentioning that, if we rank the results according to the number of citations, the first two would still hold their places as first and second. Additionally, the last place would still be held by Lukkarinen A., Teich J.E., Wallenius H., Wallenius J.

Figure 19: Co-Citation Coupling - Detailed

Source: Author's own.

Table 6: Keyword Analysis

Keyword	Occurrences	Total Link Strength
Crowdfunding	1213	3312
Crowdsourcing	325	1742
Finance	114	695
Equity Crowdfunding	226	641
Entrepreneurship	178	588
Investments	91	584
Entrepreneurial Finance	156	559
Fintech	122	421
Innovation	82	360
Reward-Based Crowdfunding	102	328
Commerce	48	301
Fundings	45	289
Venture Capital	62	283
Entrepreneur	52	279
Investment	47	274

Source: Author's own.

Our Co-citation Coupling analysis revealed a network structure dominated by a single large cluster containing the majority of data and connections, necessitating the generation of **Figure 19** as a detailed illustration of this primary cluster. The results from Co-authorship, Bibliographic Coupling, and Co-citation analyses, as presented in the tables and connection maps, demonstrate that crowdfunding literature exhibits strong connectivity, thematic unity, and extensive collaborative networks among researchers.

The visualization in **Figure 19** reveals an important structural nuance, while the field maintains clearly established canonical references, these are organized into distinct clusters representing

which confirms our findings that the literature on crowdfunding is quite focused and unified on the subject. The co-occurrence patterns largely mirror the keyword frequency distribution, with core financial and entrepreneurial terms dominating the semantic landscape. This consistency between occurrence and co-occurrence patterns suggests what Small (2006) described as conceptual maturity, the establishment of stable semantic associations that characterize a field's knowledge structure.

Table 7: Co-Occurrence Analysis

Keyword	Occurrences	Total Link Strength
Crowdfunding	1213	2347
Crowdsourcing	325	1227
Finance	114	495
Entrepreneurship	178	470
Equity Crowdfunding	226	470
Investments	91	434
Entrepreneurial Finance	156	418
Fintech	122	324
Innovation	82	282
Reward-Based Crowdfunding	102	237
Commerce	48	229
Funding	45	220
Venture Capital	62	220
Entrepreneur	52	208
Investment	47	192

Source: Author's own.

In this last part of the paper, we will be taking a closer look at each of these most occurring keywords. This includes a visualization generated by VosViewer along with an overview of how each keyword appeared in both analyses, Keyword and Co-occurrence. We only looked at six of the top 15 keywords, which we thought were the most relevant to the core function of crowdfunding. These keywords are Crowdfunding, Equity Crowdfunding, Entrepreneurship, Sustainability, Investment, and finally Fintech. The detailed co-occurrence visualizations of specific terms, [Figure 22](#) to [Figure 27](#), reveal additional insights about the field's conceptual evolution. While traditional financial concepts like “equity crowdfunding”, [Figure 23](#), and “investment”, [Figure 26](#), maintain dense connection networks, a characteristic of established knowledge domains. While newer concepts like “sustainability”, [Figure 25](#), and “fintech”, [Figure 27](#), show emerging but less dense connection patterns indicative of evolving knowledge areas. Particularly notable is the “sustainability” co-occurrence network, [Figure 25](#), which shows connections to both traditional crowdfunding concepts and environmental terms. This hybrid connection pattern exemplifies what Kuhn described as conceptual bridge-building during paradigmatic transitions, the process by which new conceptual frameworks incorporate elements of established paradigms while introducing novel dimensions.

4.5.2. Crowdfunding

As per [Figure 22](#), we see the term Crowdfunding at the very center, with a very strong network of links connecting to the majority of keywords. It appears in cluster 2, occurring 1213 times, and forming 152 links. In our Keyword analysis, the strength of these links was measured at 3312 on the TLS scale. However, our Co-occurrence analysis measured the strength of these links at only 2347 on the TLS scale

Figure 23: Co-Occurrence Connections Map - Equity Crowdfunding

Source: Author's own.

Figure 24: Co-Occurrence Connections Map - Entrepreneurship

Source: Author's own.

Figure 25: Co-Occurrence Connections Map - Sustainability

Source: Author's own.

Figure 26: Co-Occurrence Connections Map - Investment

Source: Author's own.

was Troise with 14 articles, while the least published of all authors had 4 articles. Despite the United States appearing to lead the world in publishing on crowdfunding, after controlling for sustainability, China seems to take the lead and by a great margin as well.

We found that writing and publishing on crowdfunding has been, and continues to be, on the rise since it started in 2010. Despite the apparent decline in crowdfunding publications in the wake of COVID-19, our research showed that publishing on crowdfunding continued to increase in some areas of science, such as sustainability and the environment. This was indicative of a new direction the crowdfunding literature maybe following. However, 2024 provides evidence that publishing on crowdfunding in areas such as economics and finance is recovering and on a sharp increase, while that of sustainability and the environment began to decline. Perhaps the study can be repeated in a few years to verify if these patterns hold. We also found that the crowdfunding literature presents a strong unity of subject, as opposed to being fragmented and loose around the topic. This was the outcome of multiple analyses using network science, an area of research that is underused and underutilized as an analytical tool.

This study examined the apparent decline in crowdfunding research post-2020 through multiple bibliometric lenses, interpreted within the theoretical frameworks of paradigm shifts, citation life-cycles, and topic maturation. Our findings challenge simplistic interpretations of declining publication volumes as field obsolescence, instead revealing a complex pattern of knowledge evolution characterized by concept maturation, domain specialization, and paradigmatic transformation.

The bibliometric evidence supports three key conclusions:

- i. Crowdfunding research has evolved through distinct phases (emergence, consolidation, transformation) consistent with established models of scientific knowledge development. The post-2020 decline in publication volume represents a transition to the transformation phase rather than field obsolescence.
- ii. The field has undergone a significant conceptual shift from framing crowdfunding primarily as a financial mechanism toward conceptualizing it as a tool for sustainability and social impact. This paradigmatic evolution is evidenced by the divergent trajectory of sustainability-focused publications and shifting geographical leadership.
- iii. Increasing network fragmentation in co-authorship and bibliographic patterns reflects field maturation through specialization rather than dissolution. This fragmentation represents the natural evolution of a maturing field as researchers form specialized communities around specific applications and theoretical approaches.

These findings hold significant implications for researchers, journal editors, and research funding agencies navigating the crowdfunding knowledge landscape. Rather than signaling diminished relevance, our analysis suggests that crowdfunding research has entered a new developmental phase characterized by integration into broader frameworks and application to emerging challenges like sustainability. Future research should examine how crowdfunding concepts are being incorporated into adjacent fields like sustainable finance, impact investing, and digital platform economics. Additionally, deeper analysis of sustainability-focused crowdfunding research could reveal whether this represents merely an application domain or a fundamentally new paradigm for understanding crowdfunding phenomena.

Crowdfunding research appears not to be ending but transforming, evolving from a standalone financial innovation into an integrated component of broader sustainable and digital finance frameworks. This transformation represents not field decline but maturation, as crowdfunding concepts become incorporated into the fundamental knowledge structures of contemporary finance and entrepreneurship research. Our research showed that one of the reasons network science hasn't

been used sufficiently in research is that there are no clear guidelines and agreed-upon standards among scholars for defining and selecting keywords when publishing their works. Network science and many of its analytical applications can become more effective and can produce much more reliable results of higher quality if such standards exist. Therefore, it is our recommendation that an academic or a scientific body undertake the task of setting up guidelines and standards for researchers to follow when they define and select keywords for their published works.

Declarations

The author has no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose. The data are available upon a reasonable request from the author.

REFERENCES

- Aysan, A. F., Demirtas, H. B., & Sarac, M. (2021). The ascent of bitcoin: Bibliometric analysis of bitcoin research. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14(9), 427. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm14090427>
- Beaver, D. D., & Rosen, R. (1979). Studies in scientific collaboration: Part II: Scientific co-authorship, research productivity and visibility in the French elite. *Scientometrics*, 1(2), 133-149. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02016966>
- Belleflamme, P., Lambert, T., & Schwienbacher, A. (2013). Individual crowdfunding practices. *Venture Capital: An International Journal of Entrepreneurial Finance*, 15(4), 313-333. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691066.2013.785151>
- Belleflamme, P., Lambert, T., & Schwienbacher, A. (2014). Crowdfunding: Tapping the right crowd. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 29(5), 585-609. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2013.07.003>
- Buttice, V., & Ughetto, E. (2021). What, where, who, and how? A bibliometric study of crowdfunding research. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 68(6), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2021.3054297>
- Chen, C., Chen, Y., Horowitz, M., Hou, H., Liu, Z., & Pellegrino, D. (2009). Towards an explanatory and computational theory of scientific discovery. *Journal of Informetrics*, 3(3), 191-209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2009.03.004>
- Davidson, F. J., & Carpenter, M. P. (1979). International research collaboration. *Social Study of Science*, 9(4), 481-497. <https://doi.org/10.1177/030631277900900405>
- Duvvuru, A., Kamarthi, S., & Sultornsanee, S. (2012, May 30-June 1). Uncovering research trends: Network analysis of keywords in scholarly articles. In *2012 Ninth International Joint Conference on Computer Science and Software Engineering (JCSSE)* (pp. 265-270). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JCSSE.2012.6261965>
- Duvvuru, A., Radhakrishnan, S., More, D., Kamarthi, S., & Sultornsanee, S. (2013). Analyzing structural & temporal characteristics of keyword system in academic research articles. *Procedia Computer Science*, 20, 439-445. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2013.09.300>
- Garfield, E. (1980). Premature discovery or delayed recognition—why? *Essays of an Information Scientist*, 4, 488-493.
- Kajikawa, Y., & Takeda, Y. (2009). Citation network analysis of organic LEDs. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 76(9), 1115-1123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2009.04.004>
- Kessler, M. M. (1963). Bibliographic coupling between scientific papers. *American Documentation*, 14(1), 10-25. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.5090140103>
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The structure of scientific revolutions*. University of Chicago Press.
- Merton, R. K. (1968). The Matthew effect in science. *Science*, 159(3810), 56-63. <https://doi.org/10.1126/>

[science.159.3810.56](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelso.2019.06.005)

- Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., & Altman, D. G. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: The PRISMA statement. *PLoS Medicine*, 6(7), e1000097. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000097>
- Mollick, E. (2014). The dynamics of crowdfunding: An exploratory study. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 29(1), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2013.06.005>
- Montoya, F. G., Alcayde, A., Baños, R., & Manzano-Agugliaro, F. (2018). A fast method for identifying worldwide scientific collaborations using the Scopus database. *Telematics and Informatics*, 35(1), 168-185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2017.10.010>
- Nakamoto, H. (1988). Synchronization of citing and cited literature. *Informetrics*, 87(88), 157-163.
- Peirce, C. S. (1931-58). *Collected papers*. Harvard University Press.
- Pottier, B. (1965). La definition semantique dans le dictionnaires. *Travaux De Linguistique Et De Litterature*, 3(3), 33-40.
- Price, D. J. de S. (1963). *Little science, big science*. Columbia University Press.
- Reverte, C., & Badillo, R. (2019). Alternative equity financing for entrepreneurial ventures: A bibliometric analysis of research in the last three decades. *Current Science*, 116(6), 926-935. <https://doi.org/10.18520/cs/v116/i6/926-935>
- Rogers, E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of innovations* (5th ed.). Free Press.
- Rubinton, B. J. (2011). Crowdfunding: Disintermediated investment banking. *MPRA Munich Personal RePEc Archive, Paper No. 31649*. <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/31649/>
- Shibata, N., Kajikawa, Y., Takeda, Y., & Matsushima, K. (2011). Detecting emerging research fronts in regenerative medicine by the citation network analysis of scientific publications. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 78(2), 274-282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2010.07.006>
- Shibata, N., Kajikawa, Y., & Sakata, I. (2010). Extracting the commercialization gap between science and technology - Case study of a solar cell. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 77(7), 1147-1155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2010.03.008>
- Small, H. (1973). Co-citation in scientific literature: A new measure of relationship between two documents. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 24(4), 265-269. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.4630240406>
- Small, H. (2006). Tracking and predicting growth areas in science. *Scientometrics*, 68(3), 595-610. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-006-0132-y>
- Tomczak, A., & Brem, A. (2013). A conceptualized investment model of crowdfunding. *Venture Capital: An International Journal of Entrepreneurial Finance*, 15(4), 335-359. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691066.2013.847614>
- Van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2010). Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping. *Scientometrics*, 84(2), 523-538. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-009-0146-3>
- Vismara, S. (2019). Sustainability in equity crowdfunding. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 141, 98-106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.07.014>
- Zhang, L., & Glänzel, W. (2012). Where demographics meets scientometrics: Towards a dynamic career analysis. *Scientometrics*, 91(2), 617-630. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-011-0590-8>
- Zhang, W., Zhu, Y.-C., & Wu, X.-L. (2018, July 28-30). A bibliometric analysis of crowdfunding related research: Current trends and future prospect. In *Proceedings of the 2018 2nd International Conference on Management Engineering, Software Engineering and Service Sciences (ICMSS 2018)* (pp. 1-7). Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3180374.3181331>

Published by:

Economic and Social Research Institute (ESREIN)

Blagovac 192,

71320 Vogošća

Bosnia and Herzegovina

<https://jels.esrein.org>

jels@esrein.org

ISSN (Online): 3029-3189